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MASTER OF ARTS IN NURSING

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**NURSE COMPETENCE ON PATIENT SAFETY, WORK-RELATED QUALITY
OF LIFE, AND CARING BEHAVIORS AMONG NURSES IN A
TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY, PHILIPPINES**

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October 2023

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This thesis titled: “**NURSE COMPETENCE ON PATIENT SAFETY, WORK-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE, AND CARING BEHAVIORS AMONG NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY, PHILIPPINES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Nursing.

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Biographical Sketch

Frederick Orapa has worked as a critical care nurse for more than seventeen years. Originally hailing from General Santos City, Philippines. He earned a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) from Notre Dame of Dadiangas University in 2005 and is currently pursuing a Master of Nursing degree at UPOU (University of the Philippines Open University) with an expected graduation in 2024.

Frederick began his nursing career in Mindanao, specifically in the SOCCSKSARGEN region, often known as Region XII, in the city of General Santos. Between 2006 and 2008, he worked as a ICU Registered Nurse at Socsargen County Hospital. He works also as ICU Nurse in Dr. Sulaiman Al Habib Medical Center, a private hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia from 2008 to 2017. In August 2014, he studied and enrolled in UPOU's Master of Arts in Nursing (MAN) program.

In 2017, Frederick concluded his nursing profession in Saudi Arabia. Frederick immigrated to the United States in 2019, settling primarily in Dallas, Texas. Among the thousands of nurses who responded to the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic as a COVID nurse. He worked as a COVID-19 nurse for a year before deciding to become a full-time registered nurse (RN) specializing in critical care at the University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center in Dallas, Texas.

Frederick is a lifelong member of the Philippine Nurses Association. He is also an active member of the American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN). Frederick is a Progressive Care Certified Nurse (PCCN) with further certification in COVID-19 Pulmonary and Ventilator Care Micro-Credentials. Frederick is married to a nurse, and they live peacefully in the suburbs of Dallas-Fort Worth, Texas. They have one child and a pet dog named Simba.

Frederick, a critical care nurse from the Philippines, Saudi Arabia, and the United States, believes that critical care nursing necessitates delivering ethical care to patients from all backgrounds.

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overseeing, and assisting the participants throughout the whole of the research endeavor. The unwavering ardor and dedication she displayed in ensuring the success of this study were truly remarkable.

I also express my deep gratitude to my previous Hospital institution, Socsargen County Hospital, as well as the executive committee, for giving me the chance and aiding in my pursuit of professional development, enabling me to successfully undertake my study. We express our sincere appreciation to **Dr. Romeo Pastor, M.D.**, the medical director of Socsargen County Hospital, for kindly providing us permission to carry out our study within their esteemed healthcare facility. Lastly, the authors would like to express their gratitude to **Ms. Anne Niduelan, R.N.**, the chief nursing officer, and **Mr. Ray Sadang, R.N.**, the head nurse of the intensive care unit, for their unwavering support and active engagement in this research endeavor.

I am profoundly motivated by their fervor and unwavering commitment to their vocation. Despite having several responsibilities, they consistently impress and inspire me to strive for perfection.

The Researcher

Dedication

To conduct a study of this nature presents a formidable challenge.

Thank you to my cherished families, whose unwavering love and support have been my constant companions and source of inspiration throughout this endeavor. Being a part of my life has been a privilege, and my family and I are grateful for this.

To the All-Powerful God, the Creator of Heaven and Earth, and to the Lord Jesus Christ, who have conferred upon me the intelligence, grace, the guidance of the Holy Spirit, courage, and determination to overcome challenges and obstacles as I work to complete my research project.

Jeremiah 29:11. "For I know the plans I have for you, declares the Lord, plans to prosper you and not to harm you, plans to give you hope and a future."

The Researcher

Abstract

The concept of caring holds a universal and important role in the art and science of nursing practice, including all facets of providing care to patients. In the Philippines, the direct link of nurse competence on patient safety and work-related quality of life towards the caring behavior has not been plausibly investigated in the critical care unit during the pandemic malady. This study aimed to determine the correlation of nurse

competence on patient safety and work-related quality of life on the caring tertiary hospital in General Santos City, Philippines. A descriptive-correlational design was used to delineate their significant relationship. The respondents were seventy (70) ICU nurses who were chosen through simple random sampling technique. The Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety (C3Q-safety), Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale, and Caring Behavior Inventory (CBI-24 nurse version), were used as the research instruments in the study. The results revealed that in the aspect of nurses' competence on patient safety, the highest mean score was the principle of nursing care while collaboration domain received the lowest mean score. In terms of work-related quality of life, the job and career satisfaction domain of nurses got the highest mean score which specifically indicates that ICU nurses have a clear set of goals and aims to enable themselves to do their job. With regards to the caring behaviors of nurses, the knowledge and skills domain got the highest mean score while the domain of assurance of human presence got the lowest mean value of which it further explains on how nurses treated their patients as an individual. Significantly, nurse competence on patient safety and work-related quality of life showed a strong and positive relationship on the caring behavior of nurses. It suggests that nurses' competence on patient safety and work-related quality of life are correlated with an increase in the level of caring behavior of nurses, thereby promoting safe and quality nursing care among critically ill patients. Consequently, a recommendation was also considered such as the establishment of a culture that promotes continuous learning which is crucial for enhancing the safety competency among critical care nurses and potential intervention program like basic nursing critical care to address the nurses' caring behavior.

Keywords: Caring Behavior, Nurses, Patient Safety, Quality of Life

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Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

When a patient is in the hospital, nurses are the caregivers who interact with them and offer them the most direct care. Even up to the times of pandemic, nurses continued to perform their duties in rendering quality patient care despite of many challenges. When the rapid spread of COVID-19 hits throughout most countries across the globe, among the professions most affected by the shifts, the destruction, and the disease exposure is nursing (Davidson et al., 2020). The researcher's interest in researching nurses' competence in patient safety, work-related quality of life, and caring behaviors has been solidified by her clinical observations and experience caring for patients admitted to the critical care unit. On the preliminary observation, the researcher has started to note certain points from the narratives of ICU nurses and other staff nurses from one of the tertiary hospitals in locality of General Santos City, Philippines. Majority of them have articulated their shared experience on having complexity in terms of caring their patients because of the huge impact of the pandemic malady. On the current scenario, majority of the nurses have expressed commonalities such anxiety and having a degree of difficulty of caring their patients effectively as myriad of factors seemed to affect their caring capacities. There were at least three certain aspects in which the researcher has to elucidate them based on the preliminary identified problems of the nurses working from the said hospital. First, the researcher has pointed out such aspects being attributed among nurses' competence on patient safety. It is believed that nurses enhance patient outcomes, lower morbidity

and mortality, and lower total expenses, complications, and mistakes as a means of promoting patient safety. According to nationally recognized frameworks, as described by Lakanmaa et al. (2015), nurses regularly display clinical competence and a solid theoretical knowledge foundation in nursing practice. The researcher aptly described that the nurse competence on patient safety has certain aspects in which the researcher believed that they were compromised due to the varying degree of factors affecting the domains of nurses' decision making, collaboration, nursing intervention, and principles of nursing care.

Secondly, clinical nurses have expressed their concerns about the phenomena of multiple work-related stressors in their writings. It appears that the researcher believes additional study is needed in these areas, especially when it comes to the quality of life associated to one's profession, which includes working conditions, stress at work, job and career satisfaction, control at work, and overall nursing well-being. Given that this epidemic also serves as an example of the compassionate actions of nurses. This specific occurrence is linked to the COVID-19 pandemic, which directly impacted the nursing field and adversely affected many nurses' health (Esposito, 2021). Therefore, tracking the standard of care and assessing the efficacy of nursing practice depend heavily on the accurate measurement of caring behavior among nurses.

Thirdly, on that note, the researcher has also examined the issue at hand, namely how the multifaceted factors mentioned above have an impact on the domains expressed by the Caring Behavior Inventory Scale, including assurance of human presence, professional knowledge and skills, respectfulness, and positive connectedness. In relation to that presenting problem, a significant plausible literature

has been described limitedly in other countries like in Taiwan about the caring behaviors of nurses working in the intensive care unit which found to have moderate level of caring behaviors which includes “knowing patients’ needs”, “helping patients through the trajectories of their illnesses”, and “serving as a patient advocate”. However, there were certain deficiencies that such study was not fully addressed. According to the study, it has been shown that some behaviors that were significant were not regularly carried out by ICU nurses in their day-to-day work (Yang, Huang, & Chen,2019).

Up to the present, there is still paucity of nursing research which focuses on the correlational design between the caring behavior of nurses and nurse competence on patient safety, and work-related quality of life. Therefore, the goal of this research is to ascertain the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and their proficiency in patient safety, including work-related quality of life.

A research was carried out to identify the critical link between nurses' caring behaviors and their competency in patient safety and work-related quality of life in order to address this knowledge gap. Despite this, there aren't enough correlational research on Asian countries—including the Philippines—that examine the compassionate conduct of nurses. Therefore, it's critical to look at how much tertiary hospitals in the General Santos City, Philippines, area value the compassionate actions of its nurses. In addition, the study's findings will support the upkeep of an institution's culture of care by assisting researchers, clinicians, and nursing educators in measuring the compassionate behaviors of nurses assigned to the critical care unit.

Statement of the Problem

There is a need for a thorough explanation of the specific relationship between the caring behaviors of nurses assigned to the intensive care unit of a tertiary hospital in General Santos City and their competence in patient safety and work-related quality of life. This study is within the immediate post COVID/ pandemic period and aimed to delve into three situations such as patient safety, work-related stress situations and well-being, and caring attributes as an important aspects of direct nursing care in the clinical context.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to determine the relationship between nurses' compassionate actions and their proficiency in patient safety and work-related quality of life. The specific goals of this investigation were to ascertain the following:

1. To describe the nurse competence on patient safety according to their:
 - 1.1 Decision making;
 - 1.2 Collaboration;
 - 1.3 Nursing intervention; and
 - 1.4 Principles of nursing care.
2. To describe the work-related quality of life among nurses according to their:
 - 2.1 General Well-Being;
 - 2.2 Work-Home Interface;
 - 2.3 Job and Career Satisfaction;
 - 2.4 Control at Work;
 - 2.5 Working Conditions; and

2.6 Stress at Work.

3. To describe the caring behaviors of nurses according to their:

3.1 Assurance of human presence;

3.2 Professional knowledge and skills;

3.3 Respectfulness; and

3.4 Positive connectedness.

4. To determine the relationship between the nurse competence on patient safety and caring behaviors.

5. To determine the relationship between the work-related quality of life and caring behaviors.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study was evaluated by the following beneficiaries:

Nurses. This study will advance nurses' understanding of how to provide compassionate care in terms of ensuring human presence, professional knowledge & skills, respect, and positive connectedness—all of which will eventually aid in patients' recovery.

Nursing administrator. This study would also help the nursing administrator of the healthcare institution in order to enhance their existing nursing educational program by means of highlighting the aspects of caring behavior and the factors affecting it to help measure how their nurses execute effectively in caring their patients during the times of the pandemic.

Patients. As the sole recipient of care, the findings of the study would help explain how the caring behavior of nurses affect the effectiveness of the treatment plan

in terms of compliance to treatment procedures. This will also help promote better patient interaction and sound understanding to the care rendered by the nurses towards them.

Nursing Profession. While studies have been done in nursing during COVID-19 time, this paper looks into how nurse competence on patient safety and work-related quality of life significantly correlated the caring behavior of nurses in order to help explore other recommended measures and how the related sound theoretical assumptions of Dr. Jean Watson's Carative theory about the seventh clinical caritas that delves on taking part in a real teaching-learning process that considers significance and wholeness while making an effort to remain in the context of others. As applied in the correlational study, that it would play a pivotal role in emphasizing how the caring behavior can be enhanced through a learning process and helped improve nurses' caring behaviors and care perspectives.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The primary focus of this study was on nurses' acts of compassion, their expertise in patient safety, and their job-related quality of life. This study also sought to determine if nurses' compassionate disposition and their proficiency in patient safety and work-related quality of life are connected. Furthermore, the only nurses who cared for patients in the critical care unit at SOCSARGEN County Hospital (SCH) in General Santos City, Philippines, during the Covid-19 outbreak are included in the study's population.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

The relevant literature on the compassionate actions of intensive care unit nurses, nurse competency for patient safety, and work-related quality of life was reviewed in this chapter. Additionally, it emphasized the important studies and associated literature that are pertinent to elucidating the present state of knowledge on the ideas of caring behaviors, which were utilized to provide an understanding of the areas pertinent to this investigation.

Pertinent data from the International Journal of Caring Sciences databases were all thoroughly searched for related studies. Only peer-reviewed, English-language publications were included in the search. The terms "nursing caring," "caring behavior," "nurse's perception of care," "caring behavior inventory," and "Jean Watson's theory of human caring" were used often. Subsequently, manual and online searches of the stated references in a few chosen papers produced a large number of additional references, many of which had to do with theory and instrument development. The review was restricted to theoretical and empirical research on the compassionate conduct of intensive care unit nurses, nursing competence in patient safety, and the quality of life at work. This chapter of the study was arranged according to the research variables discussed. First, is the discussion about the major variables such as concepts of caring and caring behaviors, with its sub-heading appertaining on the ICU nurses' caring behaviors from the international and national perspectives. The

second is the conversation that offers essential information on the significance of Watson's Theory of Human Caring. The third section discusses how the Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (CBI-24) was used to gauge the level of caring behavior shown by the nurses in this research. Fourth, is the discussion related to the demographic profile of nurses. The fifth sub-section discusses about the nurse competence on patient safety in connection to the Synergy Model. Lastly, is the discussion of relative information work-related quality of life as supported by an array of reviewed, published studies.

The Concepts of Caring and Caring Behavior

Caring is a basic human need and a vital component of the nursing profession. The multidimensional nature of "caring" makes it difficult to describe, hence some nursing researchers have attempted to define "caring behaviors" instead of "caring." Sensitivity, comfort, careful listening, honesty, and nonjudgmental acceptance are examples of caring behaviors that are focused on the well-being of a patient (Salimi & Azimpour, 2013). Helping patients with fundamental human needs and providing a healing atmosphere where the caring behaviors nurses reported the least (Thomas et al., 2018). On the other side, because nurses may not always ask patients about the significance of various aspects of care, they could create and carry out a care plan purely solely on their own opinions (Romero et al., 2019).

In a previous study, it also indicates that concepts of caring should be explored on a continual basis (Bergdahl & Berterö, 2016) and that caring should be regarded as relatively nuanced and multidimensional (Finfgeld-Connett, 2008, as cited in Sebrant & Jong., 2020). Additional study comparing the views of caring between patients and nurses has shown certain gaps in the literature and demonstrated that

patients' perceptions of care may not always align with nurses' perspectives (Thomas et al., 2017).

The findings from a systematic mixed-method review by Tobiano et al (2018), supports prior evidence of incongruence between patient and nurse perceptions of care. It was noted that the majority of research on nursing care quality has been performed from the perspective of nurses. Caring behaviors include two primary components from a conceptual standpoint. The first category of behaviors are instrumental behaviors, which are connected to technical and physical tasks. According to Arthur and Randle (2007), the second element is expressive conduct, which includes psychological and emotional actions such showing patients emotional sympathy, optimism, loyalty, and confidence. Nurses can provide more compassionate care when they are aware of how patients view their nursing care. Additionally, recognizing and accurately comprehending the perspectives of those who provide and receive care can help to raise the standard of both care and services. Examining patients' viewpoints, priorities, and demands on nursing care is essential to providing patient-centered care that is founded on gaining and improving knowledge (Hegedus, 1999 as cited in Kiliç & Öztunç, 2015). Patient happiness and well-being can be enhanced by compassionate conduct that goes beyond the actions of healthcare institutions or a certain type of professional and interpersonal interaction (Kau et al., 2013). When caring is lacking, there may be consequences from non-caring people as well as dissatisfaction with care, which makes the individual feel like an object. Watson (2009) asserts that as lack of caring poses a serious risk to the standard of healthcare, caring needs to be studied and practiced. Rapid advances in knowledge and technology necessitate continuous reexamination of our understanding of clinical care (Pajnkihar, 2003).

ICU Nurses' Perceptions of Caring Behavior

Seriously sick patients get direct treatment from nurses working in intensive care units (ICUs), as previously detailed in another study by Pickett (2009). When providing care for patients, they need to be able to evaluate all pertinent data, draw conclusions, and quickly provide timely, suitable therapies. A certain study conducted in Iran by Zamanzadeh et al (2010), found that patients served for varied instances have varying interpretations of the concept of caring and caring behaviors. The results showed that while patients in critical care appreciated both technical and compassionate services equally, they gave more weight to impactful caring gestures. As mentioned by Drahošová and Jarošová (2016), nurses in the intensive care unit put emphasis on providing information, which decreases patient anxiety, as well as activities to help patients overcome challenges, such as when the patient is unconscious, unresponsive, or intubated. Also, it was being described by Yam (2009), that Asian nurses place a high value on good communication, which includes active listening, comprehension, and compassion to the patient.

In an international study conducted in Taiwan found that the intensive care unit nurses have moderate level of caring behaviors which includes “knowing patients’ needs”, “helping patients through the trajectories of their illnesses”, and “serving as a patient advocate”. However, the relevant behaviors based on that study were not routinely performed by the ICU nurses in daily practice (Yang, Huang, & Chen, 2019). However, research has demonstrated that there are disparities in the views of care between nurses and patients, and that personal traits of nurses have a substantial impact on their caring behavior. These variations may be the consequence of several elements, including socioeconomic and cultural background, religious convictions,

disparities in the nations' nursing education programs and standards of care, or personal traits of the individuals (Kiliç & Öztunç, 2015).

The focus of empirical research on nursing care has been on nurses' ideas of what it means to care for patients, patients' ideas of what is essential to feeling taken care of, and comparisons between patient and nurse views of what key nursing behaviors are (Greenhalgh, as cited in Zamanzadeh et al., 2010). Numerous researchers have discovered that there are significant differences between the ways in which patients and nurses perceive the importance of different caring behaviors. These differences may lead to unmet patient needs and dissatisfaction with the care received (Chang et al., 2005).

As cited by Yang et al. (2019) that at different levels of caring behavior, nurses make evaluations and decisions based on their professional knowledge and abilities. Nurses, for example, demonstrate compassion when they support patients through the stages of their illnesses. Furthermore, caring necessitates nurses' sensitivity when assessing patients' potential and immediate needs. Nurses must also stress the importance of patients' rights, satisfaction, and needs, as well as problem-solving abilities that enhance patient health. In a descriptive-comparative study by Omari et al. (2013), their objectives included comparing the perspectives of patients and nurses about caring behaviors in critical care units and finding out how Jordanian nurses felt about these kinds of activities. Patients in critical care units believed that physical and technical behaviors were the most essential types of care, whereas nurses considered instructional behaviors to be the most significant forms of care.

In other context in terms of measuring the caring behaviors of ICU nurses, a certain study was conducted among the three Critical Care units at a large teaching

hospital in Ireland using a descriptive-comparative approach (O'Connell & Landers, 2008). Researchers utilized the Caring Behaviors Assessment instrument (CBA) created by Cronin and Harrison in 1988 to evaluate nurse caring behaviors on a convenience sample of 33 nurses from all the Critical Care units. The Caring Behaviors Assessment tool is a 62-item questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale that follows Watson's theory. On the seven subscales of the Caring Behaviors Assessment, the Cronbach's alpha ranged from 0.66 to 0.90: human needs assistance (.89); humanism/faith-hope/sensitivity (.84); supportive/protective/corrective environment (.79); teaching/learning (.90); expression of positive/negative feelings (.67); existential/phenomenological/spiritual forces (.66); and helping/trust (.66). (.76). The nurses who understood what they were doing had the highest caring behavior (Mdn score=5) for 33 nurses, on a scale from 1 = little significance to 5 = significantly important. Nurses assessed treating each patient as a person and treating them equally with respect (Mdn score=5) as two of the ten most important care behaviors. Then, even if the median scores were the same, the total amount of points was ranked. According to Watson (1985), nurses are suggestive of the subscale humanism/faith-hope/sensitivity and provide individualized care for their patients. These behaviors are consistent with Watson's carative factor number two. The nurses ranked discussing life experiences (Mdn=2), discussing life outside of the hospital (Mdn=4), and paying the patient a visit when they leave the unit (Mdn=4) as the least significant caring behaviors because stabilizing the patient had been the priority of care (O'Connell & Landers, 2008).

According to research done in Sweden by Von Essen and Sjoden (2003) (cited in O'Connell & Landers, 2008), 81 patients and 105 nurses had significantly different assessments of caring behaviors. The highest mean items among the patients were

knowing when to call the doctor, giving injections, being honest with the patient, putting the patient's needs first, and speaking in a language the patient could understand. According to nurses, talking to patients, prioritizing their needs above all else, listening to them, touching them when needed, and using simple language while conversing with them were the top five caring behaviors.

Regardless of the method used to analyze them, nurses' evaluations of nurse care behaviors still differ from one another. Although many nurses were unable to fully define nurse caring and caring behaviors, some perceived signs of care, such as "making some eye contact, smiling a bit, or even offering some coffee" (Kihlgren et al., 2005). As varied as the environments in which care is given are the views of nurses on their compassionate actions. For instance, critical care nurses have said that being knowledgeable and skilled in one's field are essential aspects of nursing care (Kilgren et al., 2005; O'Connell & Landers, 2008).

Similar studies in patients having invasive procedures have found a very strong relationship between patient satisfaction and nurse care practices (Wolf et al, 2003). On the day of the surgery, several hours after being placed under anesthesia, patients from an Interventional Cardiac unit (n=73) were requested to complete the Caring Behaviors Inventory-42 (Wolf et al., 1994) and the Patient Satisfaction Instrument (PSI) (Hinshaw & Atwood, 1982). In this correlational, descriptive comparative design, there was a moderate but statistically significant correlation ($r=.53$, $p=.01$) between patient satisfaction and assessments of the caring behaviors of nurses.

Warelow's 2008 study (cited in Alikari 2021) described that before particular care behaviors develop, each nurse's personal thoughts, values, and beliefs are blended

with his or her educational background and technical abilities through an internal process. The manner and expression of behaviors determine how a nurse applies his knowledge and recognizes the patient's uniqueness on the physical and emotional levels to assist him in managing the disease. Most nurses, according to Molina-Mula and Gallo-Estrada (2020), feel that providing care to patients requires the nurse's personal involvement, and that the nurse's personality and personal beliefs influence how the nurse provides care and builds a therapeutic relationship with the patient. Furthermore, according to a qualitative- phenomenological study by Stanley (2018), found that nurses' personal experiences and beliefs impact how they care for patients. In a study conducted by Kartini and Putri (2019) in Surabaya Jemursari Islamic hospital found that emotional intelligence seemed to have a significant impact on caring behaviors, but demographic features of nurses had little influence. In other clinical setting in United Kingdom, a descriptive study by Flynn (2016) about caring behaviors was also conducted. Her research sought to define and elucidate the essential compassionate behaviors valued by patients and healthcare providers in a UK district general hospital orthopedic environment. The results showed that the importance of caring behaviors demonstrated during caring interactions varied and exhibited both similarities. Healthcare professionals in the orthopedic context recognized the significance of comparable positive caring behaviors to those observed in the patient group but evaluated their relevance differently.

Patients' Perceptions of Nurses' Caring Behavior

Patients ranked nurses' "professional knowledge and skills" as the most caring behavior in previous study on patient perceptions of caring behaviors (Hsia et al., 2011). Four themes emerged from a grounded theory analysis of patients' views of

nursing care behaviors in Finch's 2008 study (quoted in Aziz-Fini et al., 2012): following through, reacting when necessary and without prompting, doing additional "little things," and attending to patients' needs. According to research by Wilkin and Slevin (2004), which was referenced by Suliman et al. (2009), different patient categories had different definitions of caring and caring behaviors. They went on to say that patients in intensive care units believed that compassion and technical proficiency were equally important. Nurses (n = 33) and family members (n = 19) of patients in three Intensive Care Units in Ireland were compared (O'Connell & Landers, 2008 as cited in Rafii et al., 2008). According to relatives surveyed for this study, the top five caring behaviors were: treat the patient like a person; know what you are doing; know how to provide injections, IVs, etc.; know how to manage equipment; and give the patient's prescriptions and treatments on time. These behaviors were listed in decreasing order. The most crucial caring behaviors, according to the nurses polled, were knowing what you're doing, treating the patient with respect, treating the patient as an individual, and being kind and sympathetic. More recently, a study has been done by (O'Connell and Landers, 2008 (as cited in Youssef et al., 2013) the most crucial caring behaviors were identified as having the following qualities: "knows what you're doing," "treat the patient with respect," "treat the patient as an individual," "reassure the patient," "is kind and considerate," "know when the patient has had enough and act accordingly," and "maintain a calm manner.", according to the findings of a survey conducted among 40 critical care nurses in an intensive care unit in Ireland. The (humanism/faith—hope/sensitivity) subscale has these items. Put another way, the study's conclusions demonstrated that nurses employed in intensive care units thought the most significant part of their profession was giving emotional support. In a different research, patients from six European countries were polled to determine

whether or not caring actions affect satisfaction (Finch, 2008). According to this study, the most crucial caring behavior is "knowledge and skills," whereas the least crucial caring activity is "positive connectedness."

A previous study by Marini (1999) examined the kinds of nursing care that are important to older people living in residential settings (long-term care facilities and assisted living facilities). In this descriptive study, a convenience sample of 21 patients, ages 74 to 97, answered the 63-item Caring Behaviors Assessment (CBA) questionnaire. A five-point Likert scale, with 1 being the least important activity and 5 the most essential, was used to evaluate caring behaviors. Human needs assistance (.89), humanism/faith-hope/sensitivity (.84), supportive/protective/corrective environment (.79), teaching/learning (.90), expression of positive/negative feelings (.67), existential/phenomenological/spiritual forces (.66), and helping/trust (.66) were the seven subscales, with Cronbach's alphas ranging from 0.66 to 0.90 on each. (.76). Out of a maximum score of 4,57, the average was 2.76. The most significant nurse care behaviors identified by older patients were that the nurse understands what she's doing (M=4.57; SD=.50) and knows when to contact the doctor (M=4.52; SD=.67). Furthermore, elderly patients stated that nurses treated them with respect and as individuals (M=4.47; SD=.67), which was critical. Using grounded theory, Turkel (2001) and Schmidt (2003) examined the nurse-patient interaction and nurse-caring attitudes in a medical-surgical hospital setting. From a sample of 10 patient interviews, Turkel (2001) distinguished three primary themes: "feeling scared by the new reality, being in the connection, and understanding the nurses' concern." In her study of eight patients, Schmidt (2003) discovered four themes: perceiving the unique patient, explaining, reacting, and looking over. The meanings are the same even though the themes are different. A trusting relationship between the nurse and the patient is

implied by the phrase "being in the relationship" (Turkel, 2001). Schmidt (2003) defines this as "watching over" or "feeling safe or someone being there" (p. 395). Turkel (2001) illustrated what it means to be in a relationship with the example of "nurses coming back when they promised" (p. 75). According to Turkel (2001), the most important conduct for a patient is a humanistic compassion relationship once their basic needs have been met. Additionally, nurses concurred that, even if it is just for a small period of time, caring happens during that "unique time when the nurse and the patient are together" (Turkel, 2001, p. 72). Watson (1985) refers to this as the "caring moment/caring occasion" (pp. 59–60). According to Watson (1985), at this stage, the patient and the nurse have a bond that is beyond distance and time. Patients may distinguish between a caring and a non-caring nurse, according to Turkel's second theme, comprehending the caring. Finally, feeling threatened by the new reality suggests that patients were aware of the nurses' workload but did not hold it against them. Patients, on the other hand, blamed administrative demands imposed on nurses.

Watson's Theory of Human Caring

Theoretically, further elaborating, Watson (1979) defined caring as human acts of doing something with, for, to, or as others. This is a key and unique term in nursing. It is feasible to illustrate and carry out in a way that personally satisfies human requirements. It indicates a focus on work, a compassionate, accountable, and empathetic attitude toward others. A professional nurse's act, behavior, or quality that shows concern, protection, and attention to patients is known as nursing care conduct. The nurse's perspective on nursing care conduct is also mentioned.

Watson's Human Caring Theory (1979) emphasized the humanistic components

of nursing by balancing scientific and caring viewpoints. Watson is largely recognized with the creation of the ten "carative" elements, the human science of caring, and, more recently, caring healing. Watson proposed caring as the essence of nursing practice in his philosophy and science of caring.

Nursing caregiving behaviors are defined by a concern for the patient's comfort and well-being and include actions like active listening, honesty, and nonjudgmental acceptance (Kornhaber et al., 2016). The actions of individual nurses are influenced by a multitude of factors and will almost probably provide radically diverse results. Therefore, one of the most urgent issues is what might affect nurses' compassionate actions (Kieft et al., 2014).

In addition to scientific knowledge and clinical abilities, Watson suggests 10 caring components that nurses might use to promote health, prevent disease, and aid in recovery from sickness. Examples of these include the humanitarian and altruistic value system, building trustworthy relationships, bolstering people's self-belief and optimism, expressing emotions, and upholding a safe and encouraging environment to foster peace and wellbeing. The aforementioned components make up the humanitarian value system, which is based on the idea of humanity, which is the primary notion in care (Bielecki, 2017).

The Caring Behavior Inventory

The Care Behavior Inventory has been shown by researchers to be highly dependable, user-friendly, and beneficial for quantifying nursing care in both global and dimensional contexts (Coulombe et al, 2002). In a previously conducted test-retest reliability study by Wu et al. (2006), they put emphasis that the old version, CBI-42 is used to evaluate five domains of caring: (1) "Assurance" of human presence; (2)

professional "Knowledge and Skill"; (3) "Respectful" respect to others; (4) positive "Connectedness"; and (5) "Attentiveness" to the other's experience. Conclusively, the former version of CBI has a good level of test-retest reliability ($r = .96$) and internal consistency ($\alpha = .96$). Hajinezhad and Azodiin (2014) conducted comparison research and discovered that there were notable distinctions between the viewpoints of nurses and patients on subscales including "Assurance of human presence" and "Attentiveness to other people's experiences." Furthermore, there was a significant difference in the overall scale of nurse care behaviors between the patient and nurse perspectives ($t = 2.559$, $P = 0.011$). In other country like Indonesia, Aupia et al. (2017) revealed that nurses and patients all have similar perspectives on caring behaviors after utilizing the CBI-42. The respect ($r = 0.282$, $p < 0.05$) and connectivity ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.05$) domains were positively linked with the patients' age. They have suggested that their research can be utilized as a supplement to existing understanding about caring behavior and can be used to nursing practice and nursing education.

Indeed, Wu et al. (2006) created an extended version of Wolf et al. (1998)'s 42-item "Caring Behavior Inventory (CBI-42)," which is appropriate for bidirectional identification (Kilic, 2018). Similar to this, the Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (CBI-24), which is now in use, was developed to ascertain how nurses and patients perceive providing care in a range of contexts. It is regarded as an empirical tool for evaluating care with a solid conceptual–theoretical framework. The CBI-24 has demonstrated great test-retest reliability, convergent validity, and excellent internal consistency when given to nurses and hospitalized patients. For this CBI-24 version, there was evidence of high test-retest reliability ($r = .88$ for patients, $r = .82$ for nurses), convergent validity ($r = .62$ for patients), and internal consistency ($\alpha = .96$ for both patients and nurses). The

CBI-24 is a helpful brief version that assesses acts of caring and has the potential to measure several dimensions of caring (Kang et al., 2021).

In a pilot study conducted by Burnell and Agan (2013), they discussed that it was on year 2000 in which in one West Virginia academic health facility, 90 registered nurses (RNs) from medical, surgical, and critical care step-down units as well as 362 hospitalized patients completed a 42-item version of the Caring Behaviors Inventory (CBI), which was first created by Wolf et al. The same hospital then adopted a condensed version (CBI-24) in 2004 that demonstrated strong test-retest reliability ($r = .88$ for patients). Patients were asked to rate the level of care they received from nurses on a six-point Likert type scale, ranging from never to always (Wu et al., 2006). The list included things like being empathetic, attending to patients' concerns, projecting confidence, answering calls from patients promptly, and assisting with pain management.

The CBI-24, which still bears many similarities, is regarded as an instrument made up of four correlated subscales, as clarified by Klarare et al. (2021): (I) the Assurance subscale, which includes being available to patients' needs and security (8 items); (II) the Knowledge and Skill subscale, which includes demonstrating conscience and competence (5 items); (III) the Respectful subscale, which includes attending to the person's dignity (6 items); and (IV) the Connectedness subscale, which includes continuously assisting patients with readiness (6 items). Each item is rated by participants on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (always). The mean value within each individual scale is used to calculate the caring behavior for each subscale and the overall scale.

According to a study by Papastavrou, Efstathiou, and Charalambous (2011) titled

"Nurses' and Patients' Perceptions of Caring Behaviors: Quantitative Systematic Review of Comparative Studies," there is a lot of evidence to support the notion that patients and nurses have different ideas about what defines compassionate conduct and that patients do not always view deliberate care as such. To find out more about the relationship between compassionate actions, patient outcomes, and medical or nursing expenses, more research is necessary.

Papastavrou et al. (2011) performed a cross-cultural study on the concept of caring via behaviors in 88 wards across 34 hospitals in Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Finland, Greece, Hungary, and Italy. They found substantial changes in patient-nurse views after using the CBI-24. Using a descriptive comparative survey technique, this study looked at a sample of surgical patients (n = 1659) and their nurses (n = 1195) in 88 wards throughout the participating nations. Papastavrou et al. (2011) also observed that, in comparison to the patients, the nurses' means were higher in both circumstances. Among the variables that changed in the results were the CBI-24 elements that showed significant variations, the different nations, and whether the mean of the nurses was greater than the mean of the patients or vice versa. The results indicate that there were notable disparities in the means of nurses and patients in the following scenarios: (a) Cyprus, where patients outnumbered nurses in the second (Knowledge and Skills) and fourth (Positive Connectedness) factors; (b) Italy, where nurses outnumbered patients in the first (Assurance of Human Presence) and third (Respectful Deference to Others) factors; and (d) Finland, where there was a noteworthy difference in component two (Knowledge and Skills), with patients exceeding nurses in mean. Their study's conclusions have the potential to provide a foundation for further research aimed at establishing a global understanding of patient-nurse caring behaviors.

In the Philippines, a previous descriptive study was conducted by Laurente (2002) about the caring behavior as perceived by patients towards the nurses' caring behavior. It was noted that there were patients' top five caring behaviors: (1) respect; (2) patience; (3) various helping acts; (d) gentleness; and (5) guidance. This conclusion had supported Spangler's (1992) study that respectfulness, patience, and gentleness, among other things, are caring modalities of Filipino nurses that they acquired early in life and use in their services to patients. According to the study, Filipino-American nurses associate patience with respect. These nurses claimed that they were naturally patient, and that these traits affected their interactions with others as well as their care of patients, particularly difficult patients. Competence is placed sixth (n=217) (70 percent). Patients expect nurses to be skilled at performing treatments and to be able to properly explain these processes. They are at ease since they have placed themselves in the hands of capable nurses. Patients also want nurses to exhibit therapeutic touch (69.35%), verbal communication (64.84%), close proximity/accessibility (64.19%), active listening (63.55%), smiling/cheerful/with humor (60.32%), and encouragement (48.71%). Although these caring actions need additional time and work on the part of nurses, they would pave the path for clients to have a higher quality of life. They believe that they are dignified individuals, and that it is during their illness that they require the most care. Patients' perceptions on the effects of nurses' caring behaviors differed. Some of them are happy/satisfied (99.53%), secure/relaxed (7.42%), have an enhanced fighting spirit (92.58%), hope for an early recovery (86.77%), and trust the nurse (55.16%). According to a different research that is still being done in the Philippines, patients were still happy with the quality of care they received from the hospital's nurses, even if Filipino nurses thought more highly of their own caring behaviors than Filipino patients did. The opinions of

Filipino patients and nurses differed significantly in terms of the degree of compassionate conduct (Calong Calong & Soriano, 2018).

Demographic Profile and Caring Behavior

According to Kiliç and Öztunç (2015), The perceptions of caring that patients and nurses have varies. These variations may be the consequence of several elements, including socioeconomic and cultural background, religious convictions, disparities in the nations' nursing education programs and standards of care, or individual personality traits. According to Yang et al. (2019), the age of the ICU nurses in this study significantly impacted the way they provided care, which is in line with findings from studies by Li et al. (2017), Lin (2011), and Lee et al. (2011).

The results showed that senior nurses had more clinical expertise and were thus more qualified to treat patients according to their qualifications, improve their health, and exhibit more compassionate conduct. Meanwhile, previous research has indicated that married individuals feel a greater sense of duty in caring for their families than unmarried persons.

As mentioned by Kaddoura et al (2016) that in their research, married nurses exhibited better caring behaviors than unmarried nurses. The major aspects of variables impacting nurses' perceptions of caring behavior were the nurse's characteristics, educational background, workload, job satisfaction, and working environment (Salimi & Azimpour, 2013; Hajinezhad & Azodiin, 2014). According to prior research by Mahmoodi (1998), there were no appreciable behavioral variations depending on age, gender, education, duration of hospital stays, or number of hospital admissions. The study's goal was to find out how patients perceived the caring

behaviors of nurses. When comparing married and single persons, there were no statistically significant differences. Married patients were perceived as having less caring behavior on the humanism helping/trusting and teaching subscales. A significant finding was that patients in the critical care situation perceived all actions of nurses in the critical care setting.

According to a qualitative study carried out in Tehran, Iran by Oskouie et al., 2008 (quoted in Salimi & Azimpour, 2014), personal characteristics such as conscience, religious convictions, personal philosophy, sense of obligation, and altruism may influence nurses' compassionate actions. It was discovered that nurses with these characteristics were more cooperative, sympathetic, and patient. Additionally, they have mentioned that a number of factors, including patient characteristics and age as well as staff shortages, a lack of organizational support, a demanding workload, low pay, pressure, and a lack of desire, might affect nurses' ability to provide compassionate care. In other countries like in the Western Region of Saudi Arabia, it has been discovered that intensive care unit nurses' work experience may also have an impact on their compassionate tendencies, and that this experience is positively correlated with the nurses' compassionate tendencies (Azizi-Fini et al., 2012). A prior study found a connection between compassionate conduct and professional experience. These results also suggested that more acceptable caring behavior was exhibited by nurses at higher clinical levels.

Additionally, this study found that the nurses' general clinical and ICU significantly influenced their caring behaviors, with higher seniority corresponding to better caring behaviors (Chi et al., 2005, as cited in Yang et al., 2019). These findings are consistent with those of Lee et al. (2011), although they differ from the study of Lin

et al. (2011). The reason for this might be that the ICU nurses in the present study were able to improve their caring behavior since they were continuously learning and gaining experience in providing care while working, in addition to successfully accomplishing their care chores.

There was a strong link between educational background and caring behaviors in previous research (Chang et al., 2011). Their results, however, were different from similar earlier studies in that they demonstrated that the caring behaviors of ICU nurses had nothing to do with their educational background. The fact that just 10 nurses (3.8%) in their investigation lacked a university degree or a higher level of education might help to explain this discrepancy. There are much more ICU nurses in the second educational category than in the first. As a result, the results did not change noticeably. However, the overall findings of their study showed that personal traits affected the ICU nurses' caring behaviors. According to Malate (2020), a nurse's educational background plays a significant role in how well they are able to care for their patients and guarantee that they receive high-quality, safe care. In a comparative-descriptive study done in Indonesia, Aupia et al. (2017) looked at how patients and nurses perceived each other's compassionate actions. Additionally, using the Caring Behavior Inventory-42, which consists of five domains—respect, assurance, connectivity, knowledge and abilities, and attentiveness—they looked at the relationship between sociodemographic traits and caring perceptions.

Nurse Competence on Patient Safety from the Perspective of Synergy Model

The American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN) highlighted the Synergy Model, a nursing professional practice model based on eight universal characteristics: stability, complexity, predictability, resilience, vulnerability,

involvement in decision-making, involvement in care, and resource availability (AACN, 2016). It has been shown that the Synergy Model is a highly effective conceptual framework for directing nursing care in all facets of healthcare. The core tenet of the Synergy Model is that nurse interventions are shaped and affected throughout time by the needs of patients and their families. (Montgomery, Sutton, & Pare, 2017). When a nurse's traits are based on what patients and their families need, synergy occurs. When the model is used in clinical settings, it enhances collaboration, makes the most of personnel to increase patient safety, analyzes health care costs, and yields the best possible outcomes for patients (Butts & Rich, 2018). Conversely, synergy results in inefficient patient assessments, a system that is no longer reliable, and inadequate health care overall. According to Montgomery et al. (2017), the Synergy Model may be utilized eternally if nurse qualities are matched to patient care demands. However, Butts and Rich (2018) identified a flaw in the Synergy Model, despite the literature's overwhelming support for the model's adaptation for a range of aims and contexts. In terms of identifying nursing expertise or patient status, Butts and Rich (2018) thought that levels two and four still lacked clear criteria. This is problematic because both the nurse and the patient's qualities at those levels will be unknown if all five levels of characteristics—from novice (one) to expert (five)—are not mentioned. A Synergy Model with predetermined attributes at every level establishes a framework for assessing and pinpointing potential weak points in patient care. Patients obtain optimal treatment when synergy occurs, irrespective of their degree of susceptibility (Montgomery et al., 2017).

Because of the higher patient acuity, several demanding procedures, and complicated equipment, critical care provides particular obstacles for assessing competency. Eight nursing competencies—knowledge, abilities, experience, and

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attitudes—are identified by the Synergy Model for Patient Care. These competencies are necessary to deliver safe and efficient care. They can serve as a foundation for developing critical care competencies. Better patient outcomes will result from incorporating these competences into practice in addition to helping to satisfy patients' needs and provide a healing environment. (Zupanc & Beltran, 2017). Based on the study by Khalifehzadeh, Jahromi, and Yazdannik (2012), concluded that using the Synergy Model as a foundation for receiving nursing care improved patient satisfaction and nurse performance in cardiac intensive care units. The Synergy Model was utilized by Swickard et al. (2015) to guide triage choices for transport and assess if it was suitable for essential patients to be transferred to other hospitals. Although the tool proved to be useful, the authors conceded that further research is required to establish a connection between their tool and quantifiable results. When Amenudzie et al. (2017) implemented the Synergy Model in an inpatient hematology unit, they observed improvements in patient care quality and increased nurse engagement, as well as a decrease in safety incidents like lab errors and patient falls. Similarly, Ho et al. (2017) employed a quality improvement strategy to successfully integrate using the Synergy Model in their company. Using a staff empowerment paradigm, they measured staff satisfaction, overtime rates, and patient safety incidents to quantify the effects of their efforts over time. According to Cordon et al. (2021), nurse leaders and their teams successfully implemented the Synergy Model in their different organizations through the use of a quality improvement method. Staff empowerment and patient-centered decision-making were made possible by the Synergy Model's implementation. Interestingly, they also found in their study that The Synergy Model's implementation resulted in a rise in staff engagement, a fall in workload complaints, a change in the focus of talks from finding the proper healthcare provider to addressing patient

requirements, and the availability of real-time clinical decision-making tools for choosing the best healthcare provider.

In a previously conducted qualitative study by Yellen (2007), three results were reached regarding the impact of using the Synergy Model. Patients' satisfaction with treatment improved, as did their tolerance for pain and intermittent claudication. They also gave up smoking, altered their performance and conduct, and generally enhanced their quality of life. Findings for nurses included developing a successful therapeutic relationship with the patient, while the findings for the system included minimizing adverse events, complications, mortality rate, and duration of stay in the hospital. According to Smith (2006), using this strategy to satisfy the cultural demands of patients is critical. Furthermore, implementing cultural cares based on this model may be very beneficial in creating these circumstances and delivering theory-driven care, as it can be challenging to create a therapeutic and healing atmosphere, especially in critical care units. A notable previous quasi-experimental study of Kuriakose, 2008 (cited in Khalifehzadeh, et al., 2012) discovered that using approved characters in this model improves nurse patient care and improves patient prognosis by enhancing interactions between patient and family, nurse and nurse, and nurse and system. According to Khalifehzadeh et al. (2012), the Synergy Model articulates a framework that defines the nurse's interactions with patients, other nurses, and the rest of the care team. It is a professional care model. Furthermore, this approach provides nurses with a shared vocabulary to define and relate patients' requirements. This model is a great foundation for allocating patient care inside the healthcare system.

Work-Related Quality of Life

New treatments and technology are always being developed in the critical care

environment to help patients recover from their sometimes-fatal illnesses. In order to address the obstacles that are given, nurses must make sure that they acquire and retain competence in practice (Osman, Ibrahim, & Diab, 2019). As similarly stated by Minuzzi, Salum, and Locks (2016), the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) is a conducive setting for the occurrence of adverse events due to the intricacy of the care provided, the severity of the patients treated in these units, and the work done—often under stressful circumstances and with the assistance of a multidisciplinary team. As mentioned by Scholtz, et al. (2016), Critical care nurses must work within their own culture in order to adapt to a fast-paced, high-stress situation. The special environment of the critical care unit (CCU) includes high stress levels, moral dilemmas, and crucial judgments. There are nurses who choose to work in such environments in spite of this hard reality. According to research by Ashenafie and Tebeje (2015), which was quoted by Oluma and Abadiga (2019), one of the main elements impacting nurses' caring behaviors is the care environment in which they execute their work. The multivariate outcome of their worldwide hospital research sample was.

Another study revealed a significant correlation between nurses' levels of professional devotion and clinical stress and their experience interacting with patients (Chen et al., 2021). Samuelsson and Thach (2018) conducted a qualitative study on the experience of Filipino nurses regarding work-related factors influencing their health. The study found that psychological health factors included working with novice nurses, excessive demands from supervisors and relatives, and work overload. While physical health factors included aggression from family, patient exposure, and inadequate ventilation.

Pointing back from the previous study, the caring behavior of nurses in Indonesia is still in the low category (Rumagit et al., 2017). According to numerous prior research, Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 29

the caring behavior of nurses are impacted by a variety of variables, both external and internal to the individual nurse. Internal variables include educational attainment, work experience, caring efficacy, emotional intelligence, and spirituality (Haryani & Lukmanulhakim, 2019). Aside from internal characteristics, numerous external elements have been studied to see if they have an impact on nurses' caring behavior. Work stress is one of these variables (Lestari, Kumboyono, & Dyta, 2010). Factors like occupational stress has been shown to impact caring behavior in studies by Desima (2013) and the higher level of occupational or work stress causes lower nurses caring behavior (Kurniyant et. al., 2015).

Many people think that being a nurse is a difficult job with many responsibilities. The combination of too much responsibility and insufficient authority, together with high job expectations, have been identified as some of the primary causes of occupational stress among nursing professionals (Mark & Smith, 2012). Stress at work may negatively impact a nurse's level of care and quality of life. Skilled nursing, interpersonal sensitivity, close connections, constructive communication, and the use of professional knowledge and abilities are among the interpersonal processes that characterize care. Stress at work negatively affects the quality of treatment because it causes people to lose empathy for their patients and makes mistakes in practice (Teng, Hsiao, & Chou, 2010). In a previous study of Harris, 2001 (cited in Mark & Smith, 2012), demonstrated how work-related stress affects patient outcomes and the provision of treatment, either directly or indirectly.

According to the American Nurses Association, having a sufficient and effective workforce is crucial for health care professionals' job satisfaction, preventing burnout syndrome, and managing stress at work in addition to being necessary for delivering

high-quality treatment. Because revenue production is crucial, nursing staffing expenses are always being examined. Because staffing patterns are established with a high patient-to-nurse ratio—from six patients to one nurse during the week to one: four on weekends—nurses wind up working long hours without breaks. A research conducted in Pennsylvania by the American Nurses Association [ANA] (2014: 2) on 232,342 surgery patients found that 4,535 of them passed away within 30 days of being discharged. Additionally, the research implies that variations in the nurse-to-patient ratios (4:1–8:1) might have contributed to the demise of these individuals (ANA, 2014).

The results of other studies, such as those carried out by Duffield et al. (2012), indicate that it is likely impossible to determine the best patient-to-nurse ratios or staffing patterns if the workload and working environment are not considered. This is because these factors also seem to have varying effects on nurses. The survey also reveals that the existing staffing arrangements have led to physical burnout, emotional strain at work, and increasing absenteeism—all of which are signs of discontent among the workforces. According to a prior study by Garrett (2008), nursing staff was unnecessarily burdened by insufficient staffing patterns and unrealistic workloads, which also decreased the quality of care and resulted in excessive weariness, unmet expectations, and unfinished assignments.

Ball and Pike (2009), who agree with Garret, state that a majority of nurses—more than 55 percent—said that their workload was closely correlated with the number of patients to nurses, and that they were too busy to give the necessary level of care. According to Garret, Ball, and Pike's findings—which are corroborated by Kalish and Lee's (2011) report—a nurse's quality of care declines and turnover rates rise when they are overworked and under stress. Staffing levels are seen to be the most

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fundamental element influencing the quality of nursing care, having a direct impact on nurses' experiences and patient care, according to research by Numataya et al., 2006 (quoted in Malatji, Ally, & Markhene, 2017). The authors go on to say that in addition to making it more difficult to provide the scheduled treatment, understaffing raises the possibility of human mistake, which puts patient safety and unfavorable staffing experiences at risk.

Synthesis

In summary, several authors have pointed out the potential factors that may affect the caring behaviors of nurses. Notably, there are particular unknown aspects have been identified more especially towards the correlation between the caring behavior of nurses and nurse competence on patient safety, and work-related quality of life. Because of this prevailing scarcity of research on caring behavior in the intensive care unit, the researcher had investigated further about the factors that influence nurses' caring behavior paying particular attention in filling the gap on the correlational aspects between caring behaviors and nurse competence on patient safety, and between the caring behaviors and nurses' work-related quality of life.

Accordingly, majority of research on caring behavior is limited to studies that link few factors to caring behavior. There hasn't been any research that looked at both internal and external elements that influence nurses' caring behavior at the same time, so it's difficult to predict which ones are more influential. Moreover, there is also a dearth of literature specifically in the Philippine setting. Additionally, previous studies revealed that nurses with better clinical skills exhibited more empathetic conduct. There has been an established substantial relationship between educational background and caring behaviors only. It has been found, however there were distinct

from those of comparable earlier studies in that they demonstrated in which ICU nurses' caring behaviors were independent to their educational level. In essence, a nurse's educational background plays a major role in patient care and guaranteeing the provision of high-quality, safe treatment. It's interesting to note that nurses have already identified the top five caring behaviors. These consist of paying attention to the patient, prioritizing the patient above everything else, and providing contact to the patient when necessary for comfort. These actions also align with the second caring component proposed by Watson, which holds that nurses treat patients differently and give them individualized care. The manner and expression of distinct caring behaviors determines how a nurse uses his/her knowledge and recognizes the patient's individuality both physically and emotionally to assist him manage the condition.

In view of the relative importance on nurses' competence on patient safety, it has pointed out that the synergy model's nurse characteristics provide a full and up-to-date picture of nurses' work. The eight competencies that make up the nurse side of the paradigm are clinical judgment, caring practices, advocacy/moral agency, responsiveness to diversity, clinical judgment, facilitator of learning, cooperation, and systems thinking. They give nurses a framework for explaining what they do and make it possible to distinguish between different skill levels. These may be applied to the creation of job descriptions for nurses that distinguish between various nursing practice levels in order to advance their careers, advance their professional development, and enhance their skill sets.

Furthermore, it is predicated on the core element of nursing, which emphasizes care as the cornerstone of the majority of nursing interventions, essential to healing, the moral and ethical foundation of nursing, and the essence of nursing. Accordingly, it is believed that caring conduct includes acts like empathy, consoling, listening

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intently, being honest, and accepting a patient without passing judgment.

Theoretical Framework

In this study, the researcher adopted the “Theory of Human Caring” as the theoretical framework developed by Dr. Jean Watson. Among the ten Watson’s Clinical Caritas, the researcher focused on the seventh (7th) Caritas known as “Balance (Learning)” which further states “engaging in transpersonal teaching and learning within context of caring relationship; staying within other’s frame of reference; shift toward coaching model for expanded health/wellness”. In these forms of Clinical Caritas, the researcher believed that it would play a pivotal role in emphasizing how the caring behavior can be enhanced through a learning process. According to Watson, the compassionate nurse has to pay equal attention to the teaching and learning processes.

In her seventh caritas, she also underlined that when nurses incorporate compassion and love into their work, nursing will transcend beyond a profession and that knowing the patient’s perspective of the circumstance helps the nurse to build a cognitive strategy. For a lifetime of development and learning, it will provide a job that is both life-giving and life-receiving (Watson, 2014). Watson’s theory of human caring is the most comprehensive and is frequently used in healthcare settings since the carative factors fully describe the behaviors necessary in the caring relationship between the nurse and the patient (Bucco, 2015).

According to Watson’s Theory, the fundamental goal of nursing is to assist the patient in achieving a greater level of body, mind, and soul harmony. This harmony is attained via compassionate interactions incorporating transpersonal caring

relationships. Being able to take care of oneself makes it easier for the nurse to engage in a tender moment with the patient. According to Jean Watson, the caring moment is characterized by a close human-to-human bond that transcends time and location (Watson, 2008). The carative aspects improve and strengthen the caring experience. The interactions between a nurse and a patient, as well as other modalities that may be used to enhance the quality of care, are considered Watson's carative variables. According to Watson's Human Caring Theory, the most important aspect of nursing practice is the interpersonal caring connection.

The nursing actions, behaviors, and outcomes linked to the ten carative variables guide interpersonal relationships. Watson's theory has been used by numerous researchers as a conceptual framework for nurse caring behaviors (Marini, 1999; Palese et al., 2011; Poirier & Sossong, 2010). Watson essentially provides 10 distinct factors that, when combined with clinical expertise and scientific understanding, enable nurses to assist patients in promoting health, avoiding disease, and recovering from sickness. Certain values are also frequently recognized as humanitarian and altruistic. Examples of these values include fostering trusting connections, bolstering one's own faith and hope, expressing emotions, and creating a safe and encouraging atmosphere. Since the fundamental idea of caring is founded on humanity's philosophy, these many elements make up the system of humanitarian ideals (Watson, 2008).

Conceptual Framework

The researcher clarified a few presumptions pertaining to human science, which holds that compassion is the foundation of nursing and a moral idea that highlights the significance of exchanges between nurses and patients. Also, the discussion of Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 35

different concepts in this chapter adapts the flow of thoughts relevant to the study.

The figure 1 below, best illustrates the conceptual paradigm of the study consisting of the interrelationship between the nurse competence on patient safety and caring behaviors of nurses, including the work-related quality of life.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

The link between the study's variables as they relate to the Watson Theory of Human Caring is further described in the diagram presented in Figure 1. In terms of (a) assurance of human presence; (b) professional knowledge & abilities; (c) respectfulness; and (d) positive connectivity, the caring behaviors were the dependent variable. Additionally, the two (2) independent factors that were taken into consideration were the nurse's competency in patient safety and work-related quality of life.

The nurse competence on patient safety in terms of (a) decision making; (b) collaboration; (c) nursing intervention; and (d) principles of nursing care reflects on the expected nurses' characteristics from the point on view of the Synergy Model wherein the decision making, and collaboration are elements of professional competence, whereas nursing intervention and principles of nursing care are elements of clinical competence. According to the Synergy Model, collaboration is defined as working with others (such as patients, families, and healthcare professionals) in a way that fosters and supports everyone's contributions to the achievement of the best possible outcomes for the patient or family. It entails working with colleagues and the community across disciplines as well as within them. The Synergy Model, which considers clinical judgment, advocacy, and moral agency, provides the foundation for the concept of decision-making. Clinical reasoning, which blends clinical decision-making, critical thinking, and a thorough comprehension of the situation with nursing skills acquired through the integration of formal and informal experiential knowledge with evidence-based recommendations, is what the previously mentioned model defines as clinical judgment. On the other hand, moral agency and advocacy entail acting as a moral agent in identifying and supporting the resolution of ethical and clinical concerns both inside and outside of the clinical setting, as well as speaking up for the patient, family, and nursing staff.

Furthermore, the nursing intervention and nursing care principles have an impact on the caring behaviors listed in the Synergy Model. In order to promote comfort and healing and stop needless suffering, these caring practices encompass nursing behaviors that establish a therapeutic, caring, and supporting atmosphere for patients and staff. includes, but is not limited to, family members' and medical professionals'

attentiveness, involvement, and alertness as caretakers.

On the other aspect of independent variable that includes the work-related quality of life was elucidated from the concept derived from the six psychosocial sub-factors of Work-Related Quality of Life. The concept derived from the six psychosocial sub-factors of the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale, which can be influenced by nurses' direct experience of work in their clinical field of work, was used to explain the other aspect of the independent variable, which includes the work-related quality of life. (WRQoL) scale which can be influenced by nurses' direct experience of work in their clinical field of work. These six factors that supports to explain the work-related quality of life among nurses involve: (a) general well-being; (b) work-home interface; (c) job and career satisfaction; (d) control at work; (e) working conditions; and (f) stress at work, which are believed to influence the caring behavior (dependent variable) among nurses.

Essentially, rooted from the 7th caritas of Watson theory, this helped explained that nurses with high level of patient safety and work-related quality of life may also demonstrate better caring behaviors in the clinical field especially in caring critically ill patients.

Operational Definition of Terms

There are terms in this study that appears to be technical. Hence, the researcher defined such terminologies conceptually and operationally and how they were measured within the context of the study:

Dependent variable

- a. Caring Behavior of Nurses- this is a dependent variable which is measured by Caring Behavior Inventory-24 Questionnaire. Additionally, this exemplifies how nurses should behave in the areas of knowledge and skill acquisition, respect, good connection, and guarantee of human presence. It also describes the acts of nurses who are concerned for a patient's welfare, such as empathy, consolation, careful listening, candor, and acceptance without judgment.
- b. Assurance of human presence – This category of caring conduct is centered on the security and needs of patients (items 1 through 8). "The nurse has returned voluntarily, encouraging the patient to call, responding quickly to the patient's call, and demonstrating concern for the patient," is the response to the inquiries.
- c. Knowledge and skills – The abilities and education of nurses are connected to this area of caring behavior (items 9–13). It reflects the technical components of treatment, like "handling equipment skillfully, being confident, knowing how to give shots, and treating patient information confidentially".
- d. Respectfulness- Items 14 through 19 in this category of caring behavior are related to how nurses demonstrate interest in their patients. It responds to inquiries such as "did the nurse listen to them intently, treat them as unique individuals, and show empathy for them?"
- e. Positive connectedness- this domain of caring behavior (items 20-24), corresponding to the need for nurses to be ready to help the patients". The nurse spent time with the patient, gave instructions or taught the patient, and was patient with them" is another insightful response to the issue.

Independent variables

1. Nurses' Competence on Patient Safety- this is an independent variable which is Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines

measured by the Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety: C3Q-Safety. Also, this represents an over-all characteristic of nurses that involves decision making, collaboration, nursing intervention, and principles of nursing care influencing the caring behavior.

- a. Decision making- this domain (items 16,15,13,17,12,11,14) is one of the elements of professional competence of nurses. In order to achieve a desired outcome, it also refers to the process of choosing a proper and efficient course of action among two or more options. It requires a thorough grasp of the circumstances in addition to nursing abilities acquired via a process of integrating formal and informal experiential knowledge and evidence-based standards.
- b. Collaboration- this domain (items 8,9,6,10,7) is also one of the elements of professional competence of nurses. It can also mean collaborating with others (such as patients, families, and healthcare professionals) in a way that values and motivates each person's efforts to reaching the best possible outcomes for the patient or family. involves working across and among disciplines with coworkers and the community.
- c. Nursing Intervention- this domain (items 3,2,4,1,5) is one of the elements of clinical competence of nurses. These are also the steps a nurse takes to carry out the treatments, operations, or educational opportunities meant to enhance the patient's comfort and well-being.
- d. Principles of Nursing Care- this domain (items 19,18,21,20,22) is also one of the elements of clinical competence of nurses. In order to promote comfort, healing, and the avoidance of needless suffering, it entails nursing practices that establish

a therapeutic, caring, and supporting atmosphere for patients.

2. Work-related quality of life – this independent variable, which is assessed using the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale, may have an impact on the compassionate conduct of nurses. The Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale has six psychosocial sub-factors or domains, which are as follows: overall well-being, work-home interface, job and career satisfaction, control at work, working circumstances, and stress at work.

a. Job and career satisfaction - this domain (items 1, 3, 8, 11, 18, and 20) represents the nurses' opinions and feelings regarding how satisfied or happy they are with their work, profession, and the training they have received to perform it. Clarity of objectives and job ambiguity, evaluation, acknowledgment, and reward, career advantages for personal growth, upgrading, and training requirements all have an additional impact.

b. General well-being- This domain, which includes items 4, 9, 10, 15, 17, and 21, relates to how happy or pleased nurses feel about themselves, maybe regardless of their working environment. In addition, problems related to mood, anxiety and depression, life satisfaction, overall quality of life, optimism, and happiness among nurses are included in this category.

c. Home-work interface - The extent to which nurses believe their employer recognizes and strives to support them in managing challenges outside of work is reflected in this area (items 5, 6, 14). Having some choice over the where, when, and how nurses work is connected to the work-life balance of nurses. It is attained when nurses have a greater sense of fulfillment in their lives, both within and

outside of their paid jobs, to the mutual advantage of both.

- d. Stress at work- the degree to which nurses believe they are under undue pressure and experience stress at work is indicated by this domain (items 7, 19).

- e. Control at work- The degree to which nurses believe they can influence their job by having the freedom to voice their ideas and participate in decision-making at work is reflected in this domain (items 2, 12, 23). This sense of control may be related to a number of facets of the job, such as the chance to influence decisions that have an impact on nurses.

- f. Working conditions- this domain (items 13, 16, and 22) gauges how satisfied nurses are with the fundamental equipment, security, and workspace requirements need to accomplish their duties properly. This includes aspects of the working environment such the amount of heat and noise, the hours worked and shift patterns, pay, tools and equipment, security, and safety.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the investigation was described in this chapter. The demographic, setting, and sampling strategy were all described together with the research design. In a similar way, it covered the tools utilized, the process for collecting data, the data analysis strategy, and the ethical issues.

Research Design

The research design, which is the overarching strategy used to combine the many study components in a logical and cohesive manner, ensures that it will successfully solve the research topic and serves as a blueprint for data collecting, measurement, and analysis (De Vaus, 2001; Trochim & Donnelly, 2006).

In this quantitative study, a descriptive-correlational design was used in terms of establishing a significant relationship between the nurse competence on patient safety and caring behaviors, and between work-related quality of life and nurse caring behaviors. Polit and Beck (2010) state that the goal of a descriptive-correlational study is to characterize the correlations between variables rather than to draw conclusions about their causes. As per Waters (2017), a correlational study is a quantitative research method that involves examining two or more quantitative variables from the same participant group to ascertain whether there is a relationship, also known as covariation, between the variables. Covariation refers to the similarity in score patterns between the variables rather than the difference in their means. This type of study design also seeks to ascertain the extent of any relationship or connection, if any, between two or more variables. Some of the methods utilized in this type of research

design include surveying people, analyzing historical data, and monitoring specific individuals (Grinnell, 2016). Nieswiadomy and Bailey (2018) go on to say that the researcher looks at the degree of correlation between variables by figuring out how changes in one are related to changes in another. The degree of relationship between one variable (X) and another one (Y) is shown by a correlation.

Figure 2. Research Design.

Moreover, the researcher also employed the use of focus group discussion (FGD) as a method to further explain the research objectives. Within the context of the study, there were ten nurses subjected for focus group discussion. Focus groups, in the opinion of Gundumogula (2020), are an expansion of the interview process that involve a more thorough, in-depth group interview with discussion. Nurses who are knowledgeable or talented in the specific subject matter and who could furnish information on the targeted issue to get the required data were selected to participate in the focus group. Focus groups are regarded as a specific type of group interview when a small group of individuals is assembled to discuss one or sometimes several fascinating subjects.

Sampling Technique

The researcher employed a probability-based sample strategy in this study, namely simple random sampling, in which each nurse in the community has an equal chance of being chosen using an impartial selection process (Simkus, 2023). The Raosoft sample size calculator yielded the required sample size of 70 with a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and a population of 85 responders. In order to verify the overall number of staff nurses in the study, a master list of all nurses was collected from the head nurse with consent from the nurse supervisor of the relevant unit. Additionally, the researcher worked in tandem with the Nursing Service Department to schedule the nurses' availability for participation in the study and to assemble them.

Study Population

The study's target population consisted of nurses. Nurses employed by SOCSARGEN County Hospital were expressly chosen by the researcher to be Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 45

included in the study's target population. Based on the preliminary investigation in terms of the totality of the number of nurses working from the said tertiary hospital, the researcher planned a target potential participant of at least seventy (70) nurses out from the total population. They were also ascertained by means of appropriate liaison with the Office of the Medical Director via the Nurse Supervisors and Nursing Service Department. Proper identification of the probable number of participants was identified to allow study participation after working with the executive, so as not to jeopardize staffing at the indicated unit. The head of each nursing unit and the supervisor were requested to list the staff members who willingly took part in the study. To be included in this study, the intended participants must also agree to sign the informed consent form and fulfill the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

- A registered nurse of SOCSARGEN County Hospital, General Santos City, Philippines, whether regular/casual assigned in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Moreover, the staff nurses who are rotated in the ICU whether acting as the bedside nurse and medication nurse in caring such critical patients during the Covid-19 pandemic were included in the study.
- those who willingly consent to take part in the study's operations.

Exclusion criteria:

- Staff Nurses who had no direct care to the patients diagnosed to have critical condition in the intensive care unit.

Withdrawal Criteria:

- Throughout the study, the nurses who are participants may withdraw at any moment; this will not have an impact on their job position, promotion, or performance rating.

Research Setting

The SOCSARGEN County Hospital is a tertiary and accredited by the Department of Health-Health and Facility Management Bureau and Philippine Health Insurance Corporation. It is situated in Bula-Lagao Road corner Arradaza St., General Santos City, in the southern part of Mindanao, Province of South Cotabato, Philippines. Notably, this tertiary hospital has a bed capacity of 240 beds, formerly owned and operated by Mt. Matutum Medical Center, Inc. As a tertiary healthcare facility, its goals are to increase access to high-quality healthcare among their clients in this southern region of the Philippines and to as many patients as possible at acceptable and accessible costs. Moreover, in terms of an array of social welfare services, the SOCSARGEN County Hospital has six (6) accredited agencies for financial assistance request namely: (a) Philippine Charity Sweepstakes Office; (b) Philippine National Red Cross; (c) Auxiliaries and Medical Program for Individuals and Needy Generals; (d) Municipal Social Welfare Development; (e) Provincial Social Welfare and Development Office; (f) and Department of Social Welfare and Development.

The researcher selected the SOCSARGEN County Hospital due to its accessibility and it caters neighboring municipalities in Sarangani, South Cotabato provinces and of public especially the underprivileged. It is equipped with 10 modern ventilators, 10 infusion pumps, and electrocardiogram machine and several other necessary apparatuses for acute care admissions. To note, their apparatus and

machines have currently upgraded to Siemens Imaging for more faster and accurate imaging of their patients. These include 32-slice Computed Tomography Scan; Digital Radiography; and Ultrasonography. Their institution is also staffed by the country's leading and most experienced health care practitioners. Currently, the Intensive Care unit of this health care institution operates with ten (10) ventilators allotted for critically ill patients. This nursing unit can cater approximately 10 critical patients per day that delivers primary care nursing for all critical and patients under ICU monitoring.

Data Collection

Figure 3. Data Collection Process.

In gathering pertinent information throughout the course of the study, the researcher followed a sequence of steps for the conduct of data gathering:

Following clearance from the University of the Philippines graduate school, data gathering got underway. As a first step, the researcher will write a letter to the graduate school dean and the relevant research supervisor requesting permission to perform the data collection.

- a. The researcher requested authorization to conduct a study and explained its goal in a letter sent to the Institutional Review Board and the Medical Director of the hospital.
- b. Following approval, nurses who meet certain inclusion criteria were identified for the research in order to begin participant recruiting. Through the Chief Nurse, the Intensive Care Unit Head Nurses, and the Nurse Supervisor, the researcher cooperated with the Nursing Service Department.
- c. The selected staff nurses who met the study's eligibility requirements were compiled into a master list. The study also classified nurses into two groups in order to determine the number of participants: ICU nurses and Covid Ward nurses.
- d. Upon confirming the participants, the researcher personally gave a letter of invitation orienting them about the full content of informed consent that would fully explain to them and would assure that the respondents were not forced to participate in research study.
- e. The questionnaires were given to the participants and allotted an approximate time of 30-45 minutes. The respondents were first oriented to answer the brief

demographic survey that would ask their age, sex, education, years of experience, and attendance in nursing conference, then followed by the questionnaire which was given to them about the nurse competence on patient safety which will objectively evaluate their actions at ICU. Second, they were informed to answer the Work-Related Quality of Life Scale to assess their quality of working life. And third, they were instructed to answer the Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (Nurse Version) to measure their caring behaviors in terms of assurance of human presence, professional knowledge and skills, respectfulness, and positive connectedness. Then all the questionnaires answered by the nurses were then collected by the researcher. In addition, after having the respondent answers the said questionnaires, they were given a simple token of appreciation and snacks as a sort of gratitude.

- f. A day after answering the three sets of questionnaires, the researcher asked the respondents' permission to audiotape the interview (*group interview*) using digital audio recording. Respondents' identities were protected, and they were informed that a pseudonym was used for them to ensure utmost confidentiality. Moreover, to do the focus group discussion for two groups of nurses, there were at least five (5) nurses per group with similar characteristics (homogeneous) to generate sufficient interaction. Participants were selected on the basis of being a registered nurse of SOCSARGEN County Hospital, General Santos City, Philippines, whether regular/casual assigned in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). This group interview lasted for about 45 minutes to 1 hour per session of interviewing regarding the topic of interest of the study. In an event that they would not be available for face-to-face interview, they would be instructed to have the scheduled interview done thru online media platform (Zoom

applications) and was recorded for the purpose of documentation. The researcher served as the moderator and the co-researcher served as the timekeeper/recorder throughout the two focus group discussions.

- g. All the responses of the nurses during the focus group discussions were transcribed first, read multiple times to get the general understanding of their statements, and certain significant statements were extracted to help explain the research objectives especially during the analysis of data.
- h. The gathered quantitative data were then subjected for in-depth statistical analysis that involved correlations of the study variables and interpretation.

Research Instrument

The researcher has adopted questionnaires to measure the nurse's caring behavior, nurse competencies on patient safety, and work-related quality of life. The researcher did not undergo content validation of the adopted questionnaires as their psychometric properties such as validity and reliability (a Cronbach alpha of >0.07) were already established based on the literatures (*see pages 62-68*). The first section of the research instrument contained essential details about the respondent's brief personal profile, age, sex, education, years of experience, and attendance in nursing conference. The second section included the Caring Behavior Inventory (CBI)-24 with a five-question response sheet that aims to measure the caring behavior of nurses assigned in the ICU. Each of those questions consisted of six options that ranges from 1 to 6.

Caring Behavior Inventory (CBI)-24

Based on Watson's Ten Carative Factors, this six-point Likert-type (1=never to
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6=always) is a condensed version of the CBI, which was first designed by Wolf (1986) to gather patient evaluations of nurses' caring behaviors. The frequency of caring behaviors that nurses' practice is presently investigated using the CBI-24 (the higher the mean of responses, the more frequently their caring behaviors are practiced). It is safe to provide nurses in the same version that has been used in cancer and surgery departments, among other therapeutic contexts.

Four subscales that reflect the various nursing caregiving behaviors are measured by the CBI. The first is the guarantee of human presence (items 1–8), which addresses the security and requirements of the patients. A subscale consisting of eight questions inquires about if the nurse has willingly returned to work, encouraged the patient to call, promptly answered the patient's call, and demonstrated compassion for the patient. The second set of knowledge and abilities relates to the abilities of educated individuals and nurses (items 9–13). These five subscale items, which include "knowing how to give shots, being confident, managing equipment skillfully, and treating patient information confidentially," are representative of the technical components of treatment. The third category, which deals with how nurses demonstrate interest in their patients, is respect (items 14–19). This six-item subscale inquires about if the nurse "listened intently to them, treated them as a person, and showed empathy for them; and finally, positive connectivity (five items), which relates to the need that nurses be available to assist patients. This five (5) items and asks if "the nurse spent time with the patient, gives instructions or teaches the patient, and was patient with them."

Higher scores reflect more favorable perceptions of one's own compassionate behavior. Scores are likely to fall between 24 and 144. For this CBI-24 version, there

was evidence of high test-retest reliability ($r=.88$ for patients, $r=.82$ for nurses), convergent validity ($r=.62$ for patients), and internal consistency ($\alpha=.96$ for both patients and nurses). A helpful short version for assessing caring behaviors is the CBI-24, which may assess several dimensions of caring (Kang et al., 2021). The researcher got the author's written consent before using the Caring Behavior Inventory. In addition, the Filipino translation of the CBI-24 patient version will enable appropriate comprehension among research participants during the study's execution. The weighted value listed below was used to interpret the tool.

Table 1

CBI-24 Weighted Values

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
6	5.16-6.00	Always
5	4.33-5.15	Almost Always
4	3.50-4.32	Usually
3	2.67-3.49	Occasionally
2	1.84-2.66	Almost Never
1	1.00-1.83	Never

Nurse Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety

The Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety (C3Q-safety) was used by the researcher to assess nurses' competence for patient safety as one of the independent variables. The factors were named as follows: decision making (Factor 1, seven items), collaboration (Factor 2, five items), nursing

intervention (Factor 3, five items), and principles of nursing care (Factor 4, five items) based on Aari et al.'s classification of critical nursing competence areas and the content of the questionnaire items. While nurse intervention and nursing care principles are components of clinical competence, decision-making and teamwork are aspects of professional competence.

According to Okumura et al. (2019), the questionnaire was successful in identifying four elements or domains: nursing care principles (five items), decision making (seven items), cooperation (five items), and nursing intervention (five questions). The C3Q-Safety may be used for effective instruction as well as to test critical care nursing competency with ease.

Moreover, as explained by Okumura et al (2019), the C3Q-safety's internal consistency reliability was deemed satisfactory, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.73 to 0.83. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of more than 0.7 was seen as a sign of respectable dependability. Because the C3Q-safety is made up of brief, easily understood questions that have been thoroughly examined by critical care specialists, some degree of content validity may be preserved.

Table 2

C3Q-Safety Weighted Values

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Always
4	3.41-4.20	Usually
3	2.61-3.40	Almost Half the Time
2	1.81-2.60	Seldom

Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale

The researcher used the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale: A Measure of Quality of Working Life to measure the work-environmental elements. Using six psychosocial sub-factors, a 23-item psychometric scale is used to assess employees' reported quality of life. Researchers, businesses, consultancies, and individuals all utilize the WRQoL scale to measure and comprehend the quality of working life for those who are employed (Easton & Van Laar, 2013).

The QoWL is an appropriate construct to evaluate an employee's attitudes about their job and the work environment, or the work itself, according to Brooks and Anderson, 2004 (quoted in Dudley, 2015). Additionally, QoWL was described by Gurses et al., 2009 (quoted in Vagharseyyedin et al., 2015) as the nurses' responses to the intricate interactions and results of the many components of the ICU work system. According to Easton and Van Laar (2013), the Quality of Working Life (QoWL) aims to capture the essence of a person's (nurses') work experience in the broadest sense. In this case, the direct experience of work and the direct and indirect elements influencing that experience have an impact on an individual's quality of life (QoWL), such as nurses. An individual's evaluation of their Quality of Working Life is influenced by their job as much as their contributions, ranging from organizational policy to personality, from emotions of overall well-being to actual working circumstances. The WRQoL scale uses ordinal-scale assessment as its data level. The WRQoL scale has

six components that are based on responses to twenty-three items, and each factor serves as an outcome variable to gauge the validity and reliability of the items. The items in the WRQoL scale are displayed to the participants in random order with a five-point Likert scale comprising: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, and Strongly Agree. The coding of the data indicates that Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, and Strongly Agree = 5. Higher scores designate more agreement. The scores of questions 7, 9, 19, the three negatively phrased items, are reversed. Once data are coded, higher scores suggest greater perceived QoWL (Easton & Van Laar, 2014). As cited in the study of Duyan et al. (2013), the Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale originally consists of six (6) independent psychosocial subscales or factors. These include Job and Career Satisfaction (*items 1,3,8,11,18,20*), *General well-being (items 4,9,10,15,17,21)*, Home-Work Interface (*items 5,6,14*), Stress at Work (*items 7,19*), Control at Work (*items 2,12,23*), and Working Conditions (*items 13,16,22*). The Job Satisfaction Career and Subscale (JCS), the first independent psychosocial subscale, measures how satisfied or contented an employee is with their job, career, and the training they get to do it. CJS is represented in the Work-Related Quality of Life (QoWL) measure, which asks respondents about their level of job satisfaction. The QoWL model measures the Positive Job Satisfaction component, which is impacted by factors such as job ambiguity and goal clarity, as well as assessment, recognition, and reward, as well as personal growth, career advantages, enhancement, and training needs. Second, the General Well-Being (GWB) measures an individual's level of satisfaction or well-being, maybe regardless of their employment circumstances. GWB is impacted by work and is influenced by it. Mental health issues, including anxiety and depression, are widespread and can significantly affect both the population's overall well-being and its

use of health care resources. A person's overall sense of wellbeing may determine whether they give their job a favorable or bad review. Mood, anxiety and sadness, life satisfaction, overall quality of life, optimism, and happiness are all factors that are related to the GWB factor. Third, an employee's assessment of their level of pleasure or contentment with their profession, work, and the training they get to do it is reflected in the profession and work pleasure (CJS) measure. CJS is represented in the Work-Related Quality of Life (QoWL) measure, which asks respondents about their level of job satisfaction. The QoWL model measures the Positive Job Satisfaction component, which is impacted by factors such as job ambiguity and goal clarity, as well as assessment, recognition, and reward, as well as personal growth, career advantages, enhancement, and training needs. Fourth, an individual's perception of their level of excessive strain and stress at work determines their Stress at Work (SAW). Stress at work is increasingly recognized as a health issue linked to employment. Demand, stress perception, and real demand overload are the items used to measure the QoWL SAW factor. While it is possible to experience pressure at work without also experiencing stress—in fact, some writers contend that stress may arise from a lack of pressure—high stress is typically linked to high pressure. Fifth, the degree to which an employee thinks they have control over their job is reflected in the Control at job (CAW), which measures their freedom to voice ideas and participate in decision-making. The notion of perceived control in the workplace is becoming more widely acknowledged as a key component in the comprehension of the connections between stressful events, behavior, and health.

Within the present QoWL paradigm, decision making, decision control, and workplace communication all have an impact on control. Sixth, the Working Conditions (WCS) measure how satisfied a person is with the basic tools, safety, and working

environment required to perform their job well. It may seem apparent that physical work environments that impact how employees perceive their health and safety would have an impact on their quality of work life. The connection between work cleanliness, QoWL, and the resources you have available to do your task may not be as evident.

Table 3

WRQoL Weighted Values

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41-4.20	Agree
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree

Plan for Data Analysis

As shown in tables below, it presented the objectives of the research, tools to measure the objectives, variables and level of measurement, and the statistical procedures employed in order to summarize the collected data.

Table 4

Plan for Data Analysis

Research Objectives	Tools to Measure the Objectives	Variables & Level of Measurement	Statistical Procedure
1. To describe the nurse competence on patient safety according to their: 1.1 Decision making 1.2 Collaboration 1.3 Nursing intervention and 1.4 Principles of nursing care	Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety (C3Q-Safety)	Nurse Competence on Patient Safety (<i>Independent Variable</i>) - Ordinal	Central Measures of Tendency (Mean)
2. To describe the work-related quality of life among nurses according to their: 2.1 General Well-Being 2.2. Work-Home Interface 2.3 Job and Career Satisfaction 2.4 Control at Work 2.5 Working Conditions 2.6 Stress at Work	Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale	Work-Related Quality of Life (<i>Independent Variable</i>) - Ordinal	Central Measures of Tendency (Mean)
3. To describe the caring behaviors of nurses according to their: 3.1 Assurance of human presence 3.2 Professional knowledge and skills	Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (Nurse Version)	Caring Behavior (<i>Dependent Variable</i>) - Ordinal	Central Measures of Tendency (Mean)

3.3 Respectfulness

3.4 Positive
connectedness

4. To determine the relationship between the nurse competence on patient safety and caring behaviors

Statistical
Package for the
Social Sciences
(SPSS) Version
17.0

Nurse
Competence on
Patient Safety
(*Independent
Variable*)
Caring Behaviors
(*Dependent
Variable*)

Spearman-rho
correlation
formula
*Spearman-rho
was used since
the tends to be not
normally
distributed based
on the
Kolmogorov-
Smirnov test of
normality

5. To determine the relationship between the work-related quality of life and caring behaviors.

Statistical
Package for the
Social Sciences
(SPSS) Version
27

Work-Related
Quality of Life
(*Independent
Variable*)
Caring Behaviors
(*Dependent
Variable*)

Spearman-rho
correlation
formula
*Spearman-rho
was used since
the tends to be not
normally
distributed based
on the
Kolmogorov-
Smirnov test of
normality

Furthermore, to help explain the objectives of the study, the researcher did a focus group discussion (FGD) for two groups of nurses. There were five nurses per group of nurses with similar characteristics to generate sufficient interaction. It also serves as a way to bring people together who have similar experiences or backgrounds so they may discuss a certain topic of interest. Polit and Beck (2012) state that one advantage of a group structure is that it may generate a lot of discussion. The moderator, who was also the interviewer or researcher, directed the conversation in accordance with the prepared set of questions or topic guide. In this part, the researcher asked the respondents' permission to audiotape during the interview using digital audio recording which lasted for about 45 minutes to 1 hour of interviewing.

Their responses were transcribed, and certain significant information was extracted to help explain the research objectives especially during the analysis of data. Respondents' identities were also protected, and they were informed that a pseudonym was used for them to ensure utmost confidentiality. In an event that they would not be available for face-to-face interview, they would be instructed to have the scheduled interview be done thru online media platform such as Zoom applications for online conferencing.

Essentially, all the respondents were given an opportunity to respond which was moderated by the researcher the course of the group interview. Please see Appendices for the series of open-ended questions during the conduct of group interview.

Data Management

Data collected was kept in a password-protected laptop and was only accessed by the researcher. These data will be kept for five (5) years and will only be used for educational purposes. After five years, all data will be permanently deleted.

Ethical Considerations

In every field where doing research on human subjects is required, researchers must deal with ethical dilemmas. This should be observed as research ethics provides guidelines for the responsible conduct of research and ultimately protects the rights of the participants. Within the context of this study, the rights to self-determination, rights to informed consent, and research aspects of anonymity and confidentiality were observed. First and foremost, before to initiating participant recruiting, this study was authorized by the SOCSARGEN County Hospital's Institutional Review Board.

The potential research participants have the freedom to choose whether or not to engage in the study at their own discretion, in accordance with the concept of self-determination. This serves to highlight the absence of any kind of coercion, such as threats of punishment for refusing to engage in a research or unduly high rewards for consenting to participate. Additionally, the respondents in this study—nurses—were advised of their right to withdraw from participation at any time, to withhold information, or to request clarification on the goal of the study. In terms of informed consent, the respondents possess sufficient knowledge about the research, can understand the material, and have the freedom to choose whether or not to engage in the study (Polit & Beck, 2010). By having the respondents sign a consent form, the researcher in this study was able to document the informed consent procedure. The goal of the study, the expectations for involvement, the voluntary nature of participation, and the possible costs and rewards were all clearly communicated to the respondents in this form.

Throughout the course of the study, the aspects of anonymity and confidentiality were strictly followed. According to Polit and Beck (2010), anonymity occurs when research volunteers' identities are kept a secret, even from the study's investigator. According to Nieswiadomy and Bailey (2018), anonymity—which happens when even the researcher is unable to connect participants with their data—is the most secure way to preserve confidentiality. In essence, the study's anonymity was preserved by eliminating the written consent from the questionnaire and not disclosing the respondents' identities in research reports or the data collecting tool. A pledge of secrecy to a participant, according to Polit and Beck (2010), is an assurance that the participant's information won't be disclosed to other parties or made public. Therefore, in order to prevent any unintentional breach of confidentiality, researchers typically

create complex confidentiality procedures that include getting confidentiality assurances from all parties involved in the collection or analysis of research data, keeping identifying information in locked files that only a limited number of people can access, presenting only aggregate data for groups of respondents, hiding a respondent's identity in a research report or substituting identification (ID) numbers for respondents' names on study records and computer files. In this study, participants' identities were protected, and they were well-informed that they can choose a pseudonym, or one will be selected for them by the researcher to ensure utmost confidentiality.

Importantly, the study's results will be addressed with the nursing service department and staff nurses to see if the Caring Behavior Inventory-24 may be applied to the nursing unit. Finally, the researcher said that he had no conflicts of interest related to this work. For any form of queries and complaints, the following pertinent details could be reached out as shown below:

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Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study's main objectives were to ascertain the degree of nursing competence in terms of patient safety, work-related quality of life, and compassionate conduct among nurses at a General Santos City, Philippines, tertiary hospital. Additionally, the analyses and their presentation followed the study's goals.

Table 5

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents (n=70)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group		
21-30 years old	9	12.9
31-40 years old	44	62.9
41-above years old	17	24.3
Sex		
Male	25	35.7
Female	45	64.3
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelors	62	88.6
Masters	7	10.0
PhD	1	1.4
Years of Experience		
1-5 years	13	18.6
6-10 years	10	14.3
11-15 years	16	22.9
16-20 years	26	37.1
More than 20 years	5	7.1

Attendance in Nursing Conference

Yes	57	81.4
No	13	18.6

Table 5 shows the socio-demographic profile of respondents. Based on the data, most nurses (62.9%) were from ages 31-40. This was followed from the age bracket of 41 and above years old at 30.8%, and last is from 41 and above years old which accounts for 25.6%. It can also be seen that there was a preponderance of female nurses (64.3%) than male nurses (35.7%) out of 70 respondents. Most of the nurses graduated with a bachelor's degree in nursing (88.6%), followed by those who have master's degree (10%), and the remaining smallest percentage with PhD degree (1.4%). Moreover, majority of the nurses had 16 to 20 years of nursing experience (37.1%) and few of them had more than 6 to 10 years of nursing experience (7.1%). Lastly, a vast majority of the nurses attended trainings in the nursing conference (81.4%) while 18.6 % accounts for having no attendance in the nursing conference.

The Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety (C3Q-Safety) assesses a nurse's competency on four subscales: nursing intervention, decision-making, teamwork, and nursing care principles. A score of 1 indicates never, while a score of 5 indicates always. The competency in patient safety as evaluated by the nurses in a tertiary hospital in General Santos City, Philippines, was ascertained by taking the mean and standard deviation of each subscale.

Table 6

Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Competence on Patient Safety per Subscale

Subscale	Mean	Standard Deviation
Competence on Patient Safety	4.71	0.54
Decision Making	4.72	0.47
Collaboration	4.62	0.62
Nursing Intervention	4.69	0.68
Principles of Nursing Care	4.81	0.40

Interpretation:

Nurse competence on patient safety was described as “always” (M-4.71, SD-0.54). Notably, all four subscales were also described as “always” with mean scores above 4.2: a) decision-making (M-4.72, SD-0.47), b) collaboration (M-4.62, SD-0.62), c) nursing interventions (M-4.69, SD-0.68), and d) principles of nursing care (M-4.81, SD-0.40).

According to Stafseth et al. (2018), critical care nurses engage in a range of activities and interventions as part of their routine practice. These include monitoring and assessing patients, attending to their respiratory requirements, helping with various physiological processes, delivering basic nursing care, administering infusion and transfusion therapies, overseeing medication administration, managing drainage tube care, offering psychological support, and tending to the family members of patients. The "principles of nursing care," or the clinical competency part, was highly rated in prior research by Lakanmaa et al. (2015). This phenomenon can be attributed

to the observation that ICU nurses who provide direct patient care at the bedside, who possess a greater level of familiarity with safe and patient-centered practices, as they often employ these abilities in their daily nursing care routines. In contrast, the dimension of collaboration was identified as the best among the four sub-indicators. This discovery exhibits resemblances to many previous studies. In consonance to the study of Dikmen et al. (2022), it was shown that ICU nurses identified many elements, including nursing care, as integral components that define the essence of nursing care. The nurses emphasized the particulars of caring for critically ill patients in an intensive care unit (ICU) due to the severity of the patients' medical conditions. The results of their study indicate that maintaining the vital signs of critically sick patients is the main goal of nursing care in the intensive care unit (ICU). Once this objective is successfully accomplished, nurses can shift their attention towards addressing other dimensions of patient care.

In order to determine where the nurses scored well or poorly, the mean and standard deviation of their C3Q-Safety questions were also calculated in (score per question is indicated by its mean range where 1.00-1.80 is described as never; 1.81-2.60 as seldom; 2.61-3.40 as about half the time; 3.41-4.20 as usually; and 4.21-5.00 as always).

Table 7

Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Competence on Patient Safety per Item

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
COMPETENCE ON PATIENT SAFETY			
Decision Making			
1	After finishing a task, you independently find a new task.	4.64	0.48
2	You respond flexibly to changed orders.	4.76	0.43
3	You can fulfill your role.	4.74	0.47

4	You solve problems in clinical practice.	4.63	0.49
5	You can recognize your role and act accordingly.	4.80	0.40
6	You repeat oral instructions aloud.	4.73	0.56
7	You clean up empty medicines and organize complicated infusion lines.	4.76	0.46
Collaboration			
8	You frequently communicate with co-worker ICU nurses	4.71	0.76
9	You frequently communicate with other medical staff (e.g. pharmacist)	4.67	0.63
10	When you notice abnormal vital sign or specific physical findings, you tell a doctor or other nurses.	4.93	0.26
11	You share your anxiety with others	3.87	1.18
12	You prioritize a monitoring and an execution of doctor's orders according to the patient's condition.	4.94	0.26
13	You begin physical examination within 5 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU.	4.69	0.77
14	You begin patient monitoring within 3 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU.	4.63	0.82
15	You execute the doctor's orders on time (within 5 minutes)	4.59	0.63
16	Before a patient enters the ICU, you have prepared the items needed for the patient care.	4.64	0.80
17	You conduct a physical assessment using the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) approach.	4.89	0.36
Principles of Nursing Care			
18	You value what the patient says.	4.90	0.30
19	You do the thoughtful care of patients (e.g., smiling, touching)	4.77	0.42
20	You listen attentively to the patient's family anxiety	4.74	0.50
21	You actively provide patients with nursing that leads to their recovery.	4.83	0.38
22	You provide nursing equally to all patients.	4.79	0.41

Interpretation:

All items in each of the subscales of the nurse competence on patient safety were also measured using the mean and standard deviation of their responses to the C3Q-Safety questions. These items were all described as “always” with mean scores greater than 4.2 as seen on Table 7 above.

Decision-making subscale

The decision-making subscale items were all described as “always”, with mean scores that ranged between 4.2 – 5: a) After finishing a task, you independently find a new task (M-4.64, SD- 0.48), b) You respond flexibly to changed orders (M-4.76, SD- 0.43), c) You can fulfill your role (M-4.74, SD 0.47), d) You solve problems in clinical practice (M-4.63, SD- 0.49), e) You can recognize your role and act accordingly (M-4.80, SD- 0.40), f) You repeat oral instructions aloud (M-4.73, SD-0.56), g) You clean up empty medicines and organize complicated infusion lines (M-4.76, SD-0.40) with the highest mean score shown by the item, “You can recognize your role and act accordingly” (M-4.80, SD-0.40), and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “You solve problems in clinical practice” (M-4.63, SD-0.49).

It is noted that ICU nurses have always recognized their roles especially when placed at a crucial juncture in providing nursing care among critically ill patients during the pandemic. In a focus group discussion, it can be recalled that Participant B shared an important role of nurses during the time of pandemic. She said that *“if ever there’s no family beside the patient, then you will be the one to provide the sense of touch. Even just by touching their hands, it’s like there’s still somebody who looks for them (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 209-210)*. Also, nurses acted accordingly beyond their learned skills. As articulated by Participant H, *“I have worked here long time even pandemic. I dealt it professionally based on skills, knowledge, and attitude. I’m not emotionally*

attached; we need to set boundaries.” (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 243- 246).

Clinical problems encountered by ICU nurses are centered on the proper physical assessment prior to ICU transport. As verbalized by Participant C *“sometimes there are patients having GCS 15 or 13, then upon transferring in the ICU there’s no pulse and BP. So, if nurses from the ER will say GCS 15, I need to do thorough assessment and get back again to the patient. You really need to assess it” (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 311-313, 316-318).* Nurse A added that *“because the ER had just stabilized the patient, so you have to continue the medication that keep your patient alive by placing them on the ventilator while you give the adequate care physically.” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 282-285).*

Critical care has unique challenges for competence assessment due to increased patient acuity, several difficult procedures, and complex equipment. According to Higgs et al. (2019), the domain of decision-making is a complex and contextually dependent process as it involves several influencing factors. First is the attributes and the nature of the task such as the importance, urgency, and familiarity. Second is the features of the decision-maker like the cognitive and emotional capabilities). And third is the context in which the decision takes place like the environment.

Relatively, in a study of Laugesen et al. (2022), they have found certain factors resulting from the changes in the work environment caused by the COVID- 19 impact the decision making among nurses. These factors are usually influenced by the nurses’ competencies, such as their experience in care units. They also depend on their access to sources of knowledge including patients, colleagues, evidence-based guidelines, and context specific information. The context includes aspects like isolation rooms and newly established wards as well as broader concerns among healthcare

professionals regarding the virus. Additionally cultural factors play a role in terms of a predominant focus on COVID- 19. Similarly, in a study by Ali-Abadi et al. (2020) also found that ICU nurses who work in unique conditions encountered several challenges like stressful occupational factors like heavy workloads. They often deal with workloads providing care for ill patients responding quickly in emergency situations and utilizing various medical devices and techniques.

Collaboration subscale

The items in the collaboration subscale were described as “always” in four of five items, with mean scores that ranged between 4.2 – 5: a) You frequently communicate with coworker ICU nurses (M-4.71, SD-0.76), b) You frequently communicate with other medical staff (e.g. pharmacist, physical (M-4.67, SD- 0.63), c) When you notice abnormal vital sign or specific physical findings, you tell a doctor or other nurses (M-4.93, SD-0.26), and d) You prioritize a monitoring and an execution of doctor’s orders according to the patient's condition (M-4.94, SD-0.26); one item was described as “usually”, i.e., You share your anxiety with others (M-3.87, SD-1.18). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “You prioritize a monitoring and an execution of doctor’s orders according to the patient’s condition”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “You share your anxiety with others”.

In relation to the nurse competence on patient safety from the perspective of Synergy Model, Swickard et al. (2015) emphasize how important a nurse's skill set is while caring for critically sick patients and making decisions. By customizing such a model for the interfacility transport triage decision, the nurse continuity of care is extended from the sending critical care area to the receiving critical care area. Nurses have a role in the collaborative care process as members of the team that provide thorough, safe treatment for critical care patients, especially under the unstructured

conditions of travel.

Based on the articulations of one of the participants in focus group discussions, he put emphasis about the critical period of assessment monitoring to a patient with severe COVID-19 infection. Participant A was keen to express saying that *“because during the admission, there’s a lot of things you have to carry out. When the patient is brought to your unit, within 3 minutes, you have to establish your assessment and you have your mental picture about the case of the patient. Generally, during those hours are the most crucial.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 278-282). Also, participant J had given importance about the provision of nursing care and implementation of physician’s order. Participant J mentioned that *“promote holistic care approach to patient. And giving what they need and in terms of what need during the situation. In terms of proper care, proper referral to the doctor.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 130-133).

As cited by Belarmino et al. (2020), the field of nursing is a profession that strengthens collaborative interprofessional practice and promotes teamwork and communication with other members of the healthcare team. In a systematic review conducted by Vaismordi et al. (2020), they concluded that nurses’ collaboration in performing tasks and standardization of the care processes can help enhance the nurses’ adherence to patient-safety principles. Essentially, Henneman (2017) explains that the nurses’ assessment to the patient, care planning, monitoring, double-checking, and communication with other healthcare professionals are all steps that nurses are expected to follow in accordance with organizational strategies for recognizing risks and harms.

Anxiety is a phenomenon that has been observed among ICU nurses as they felt bouts of anxiety as a result of handling COVID-19 patients. Participant H expressed his

concerns saying “*well it impacts a lot especially usually when I go home and it is so difficult to adjust. I be afraid and anxiety when you have a little cough, it’s very bad experience in my part, everybody is walking away.*” (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 165-167). Based on this study, this is the only item in collaboration subscale which was described as “usually” done by ICU nurses. In terms of ICU nurses’ anxiety experienced during the time of pandemic, reflects a similar finding from a descriptive-phenomenological study conducted by Pogoy and Cutamora (2021) in which nurses’ concerns also revolved around the feelings of anxiety of possibly getting infected, not providing the appropriate level of care and worried about the welfare of their loved. According to Huang et al. (2020), The nurses' anxiety and panic were also heightened by their worry that they would become sick and spread the virus to their family members. According to Arnetz et al. (2020), the COVID-19 epidemic has exposed nurses to situations that jeopardize their health, welfare, and ability to work. In order to identify groups at risk for sickness and possible sources of organizational intervention, it is imperative that the experiences and well-being of nurses during the current crisis be studied.

Nursing intervention Subscale

All the items in the nursing intervention subscale were described as “always” with mean scores ≥ 4.2 : a) You begin physical examination within 5 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU (M-4.69, SD- 0.77), b) You begin patient monitoring within 3 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU (M-4.63, SD- 0.82), c) You execute the doctor’s orders on time (within 5 minutes) (M- 4.59, SD- 0.63), d) Before a patient enters the ICU, you have prepared the items needed for the patient care (M- 4.64, SD= 0.80), and e) You conduct a physical assessment using the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) approach (M-4.89, SD- 0.30). The highest mean score was shown by item, “You

conduct a physical assessment using the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) approach.”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “You execute the doctor’s order on time (within 5 minutes)”.

The ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) assessment approach is always used by ICU nurses to do a physical examination. According to one of the participants in a focus group discussion, it is part of their daily routine that a detailed and thorough physical assessment should be performed upon receiving COVID-19 patients in the ICU most especially from the emergency room department. As stated by participant A, “I need to check what could they have missed during the assessment in the ER” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 285-286). Moreover, participant H explained why physical assessment is vital to perform in their unit. He said that “as much as possible we assess properly because here in this hospital, we don’t have resident on duty assigned or IM doctors assigned here.” He also added a phrase “you know it...basic skills pa rin ABC.” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 118-120; 128).

In terms of conducting a physical assessment, Piccione (2021) emphasized the importance of using techniques like the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) approach, which is thought to be the best approach for quickly evaluating a potential critical care patient, particularly those who have been diagnosed with COVID-19 infection. This is done in order to identify a decline in vital signs early on and initiate resuscitation. Restoring stability, averting complications, and achieving optimal health necessitates ongoing intensive assessment, prompt critical care interventions, and ongoing management evaluation through multidisciplinary efforts, as stated by the Critical Care Nurses of the Philippines, Inc. (2016).

To execute the doctor’s orders on time like 5-minute period did not reflect to the

usual scenario among ICU nurses as the execution of doctor's order is highly dependent on certain scenario. During the time of pandemic, one of which is taking consideration about the complexity of patient's admission process from the ER like incompleteness of laboratory results and the clinical condition of the patient to be admitted in the ICU. Certain participant has verbalized that *"because during the admission, there's a lot things you have to carry out. And the moment you see the laboratories, there are a lot of things you need to correct interms of the patient. Kasi sometimes other departments would say that patient is okay, but in reality, in the ICU, there's a lot of things you need to monitor."* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 278-279; 287-291). Aside from that, Participant C has also said that *"you need to be a keen observer to your patient. If there's something wrong that you don't; understand, then you need to refer it back to the doctor."* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 61-63).

Despite the time-consuming nature of creating these plans, a systematic review by Cuzco et al. (2021) found that maintaining an organized, current care plan that promotes continuity of care requires ongoing assessment of the needs of patients admitted to the ICU throughout their stay and transfer to the general ward. Furthermore, research has demonstrated a connection between this kind of intervention and patients' increased readiness for both ICU and hospital release.

Principles of Nursing subscale

All items in the principles of nursing care subscale of the nurse competence on patient safety were described as "always" with mean scores ≥ 4.2 : a) You value what the patient says (M-4.90, SD-0.30), b) You the thoughtful care of patients (e.g., smiling, touching) (M- 4.77, SD- 0.42), c) You listen attentively to the patient's family's anxiety (M-4.74, SD- 0.50), d) You actively provide patients with nursing that leads to their

recovery (M-4.83, SD- 0.38), and e) You provide nursing equally to all patients (M-4.79, SD- 0.41). The highest mean score was shown by item, “You value what the patient says.”, and the lowest mean score was shown by item, “You listen attentively to the patient’s family’s anxiety.”

The basic clinical competence of ICU nurses on patient safety in terms of nursing care principles was found to be "high" in a previous similar study carried out in Finland by Lakanmaa et al. (2015). This pertains to moral principles like justice, safety, and patient-centeredness as well as the identification of anomalous vital signs, the need for pain management, skin condition alterations, and the requirement for fluid treatment. When these competencies are routinely applied in everyday care, ICU nurses at the bedside have greater experience providing safe, direct, patient-centered care, which helps to explain this. With regards to the valuing attitude of nurses towards their patients in the ICU like addressing patient’s needs seemed to be interrelated to the empathy they showed to their patients.

It could be noted that from the study of Bae (2021), in which it was found that ICU nurses consider empathy as a technique of interacting with patients. An empathic relationship with critically ill patients may provide them with satisfaction and well-being. This has been described as an attempt to visualize and understand what specific critically ill patients are experiencing and feeling in order to evaluate their care needs. According to one the participants in focus group discussion, participant A articulated that “you have to explain those things to your patient, put yourself on the shoes of the patients, and be therapeutic.” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 186-188). Also, participant F shares similar positive expression by saying that “aside from skills, you need to have compassion... right attitude is towards the patient is more important.” (FGD Transcript

2, Line No. 90; 93-94).

Attentive listening to the anxiety of the patient's significant member is also a challenging aspect on the part of ICU nurses more especially on how to address it since Covid-19 pandemic not only impacts the mental health of patients but also the family member. In a study conducted by Magro-Morillo et al. (2020), it was found that family members constantly prioritize critically ill patients in their lives and desire to be close to their patients, whether or not they participate in their care. Based on that study, it was also indicated that anxiety is one of the highlighted emotions. Moreover, ICU nurses noted that families sometimes have overly high expectations of nurses' caregiving. According to Hetland et al. (2018), critically- ill patients' family members are almost as important in their care delivery as the patients themselves. Family members' contributions to the critically ill patients care process are regarded to be a cause of stress for the nurse while helping the patient. Additionally, nurses emphasized the need of responding to the relatives of patients who are in critical condition, providing them with information to reduce their anxiety, and having to explain what is going on (Willemse et al., 2020).

Work-related Quality of Life

Table 8

Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Work-Related Quality of Life per Subscale

Subscale	Mean	Standard Deviation
Work-related Quality of Life	4.01	0.87
Job and career satisfaction	4.31	0.70
General well-being	3.87	0.97
Home-work interface	4.02	0.90
Stress at work	3.88	0.96

Interpretation:

In the domain of job and career satisfaction of nurses' work-related quality of life, the highest mean score ($M=4.31$, $SD=0.70$) is often seen. This suggests that ICU nurses have specific aims and aspirations that help them perform their jobs effectively. Conversely, the category of general well-being exhibited the lowest mean score ($M=3.87$, $SD=0.97$).

It can also be overserved that some nurses experienced stress during the pandemic but some of them showed optimism and resiliency. Hwang and Lee (2023) suggest that ICU nurses who exhibit higher levels of resilience associated to COVID-19 may have an easier time handling the stress and demands of their jobs during the pandemic, which might lead to improved mental health outcomes. In a study of Zhang et al. (2021), they conclusively stated that optimism could increase the chance of higher work satisfaction. However, in the study of Galanis et al. (2023), they found that nurses encountered diminished levels of job satisfaction, with the advent of the COVID-19 epidemic exacerbating the deterioration of their working conditions. Also, this was supported by the findings of Aiken et al. (2023) in which nurses have been found to experience higher rates of dissatisfaction during the pandemic.

In consonance with the study of Almeida et al. (2023), that despite of the disruptive environment, they discovered that nurses had significantly higher well-being scores. Their research during the epidemic revealed that mindfulness was an important personal resource that enhanced nurses' well-being at work. According to Gunasekara & Zheng (2019), nurses who practice mindfulness are more likely to be able to cope with high job demands and stressful situation.

Table 9*Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Work-Related Quality of Life per Item*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
COMPETENCE ON PATIENT SAFETY			
Job and Career Satisfaction			
1	I have a clear set of goals and enable me to do my job.	4.64	0.54
2	I have the opportunity to use my abilities at work.	4.51	0.61
3	When I have done a good job, it is acknowledged by my line manager.	3.91	0.83
4	I am encouraged to develop new skills.	4.43	0.63
5	I am satisfied with the career opportunities available for me here.	4.00	0.90
6	I am satisfied with the training I receive in order to perform my present job.	3.90	1.01
General Well-Being			
7	I feel well at the moment.	4.19	0.87
8	Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed.	3.37	1.31
9	I am satisfied with my life.	4.01	0.97
11	Generally, things work out well for me	4.03	0.80
12	Recently, I have been feeling reasonably happy all things considered.	3.83	0.87
Home-Work Interface			
13	My employer provides adequate facilities and flexibility for me to fit work in around my family life.	4.09	0.76
14	My current working hours/patterns suit my personal circumstances.	4.06	0.96
15	My line manager actively promotes flexible working hours/patterns.	3.90	0.97
Stress at Work			
16	I often feel under pressure at work.	3.99	0.91
17	I often feel excessive levels of stress at work	3.77	1.01
Control at Work			

18	I feel able to voice opinions and influence changes in my area of work.	4.17	0.76
19	I am involved in decisions that affect me in my own area of work.	4.20	0.73
20	I am involved in decisions that affect members of the public in my own area of work.	3.80	0.84
Working Conditions			
21	My employer provides me with what I need to do my job effectively.	3.96	0.94
22	I work in a safe environment.	3.97	0.92
23	The working conditions are satisfactory.	3.77	0.85

Interpretation:

The mean and standard deviation of their answers to the WRQoL statements were also used to assess all items in each of the subscales of work-related quality of life. (See table 9)

Job and Career subscale

Among the six items in Job and Career subscale, three items were described as “strongly agree” with the WRQoL statements: a) I have a clear set of goals and aims to enable me to do my job (M-4.64, SD- 0.54), b) I have the opportunity to use my abilities at work (M-4.51, SD- 0.61), c) I am encouraged to develop new skills (M- 4.43, SD- 0.63). The other three items were described as “agree”: d) When I have done a good job, it is acknowledged by my line manager (M-3.91, SD- 0.83), e) I am satisfied with the career opportunities available for me here (M- 4.00, SD- 0.90), and f) I am satisfied with the training I receive in order to perform my present job (M- 3.90, SD- 1.0). The highest mean score was shown by item, “I have a clear set goal and aims to enable me to do my job.”, and the lowest mean score was shown by item, “I am satisfied with the training I receive in order to perform my present job”.

As articulated by Participant A *“when we say work-related quality of life, given the fact that we are under the pandemic, it is also understandable that all healthcare workers are expected to do their part. For example, we are at war, the military will be put in charge, so this is the different war wherein the nurses are in the battlefield, in the forefront of the care situations. We are away, we have to endure wearing PPEs for the longer period of time. We have to endure being away to our loved ones, we cannot go home yet. And all we have to do is to be present in our workstation.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 83-91).

In other nations, such as Israel, nurses who worked during pandemics and expressed a desire to quit the nursing field reported lower mean job satisfaction scores (Savitsky et al., 2021). As a result, Allan et al. (2018) clarified that the high degree of satisfaction that has been observed is critical to the psychological and physical health of nurses, as well as to their preparedness to stay in the field and reduce turnover. The study's findings, on the other hand, are in stark contrast to a correlational study carried out in Finland by Sihvola et al. (2023), which discovered that nurses' overall job satisfaction was significantly low and that many had considered quitting their careers, raising serious concerns for the future of healthcare. Additionally, the same study revealed that nurses who treated COVID-19 patients had lower levels of work satisfaction than nurses who did not treat such patients (Lavoie-Tremblay et al., 2022). Nevertheless, Wargo-Sugleris et al. (2018) found that older nurses' job satisfaction is the primary motivator for continuing their employment rather than taking an early retirement in sizable research using a similar correlational approach. However, participant I voiced her concern particularly on the trainings offered in their hospital. She said that *“each nurse should have equipped with skills and understanding regarding the safety for the patient. For example, nurses should have these seminars*

and trainings before exposed to the nursing field so that safety is really... to be secure, most of the time. Especially when it comes to medical care, situations like emergency situations like situations that needs immediate actions, nurses should know how to handle these situations properly because we're handling life and we are not allowed to commit errors. During the pandemic, that's the time, which is very difficult for us, because we didn't know how to protect ourselves with regards to COVID-19 because it's very vague and it's very unknown to us. So, during those periods of time most of us undergone this special training for us to be protected against the viruses and the environment.” (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 67-76).

According to Vera San Juan et al. (2022), the COVID-19 pandemic presents unique problems in terms of developing flexible redeployment approaches and providing timely training while adhering to infection control recommendations. ICU nurses need enough care and assistance because of their critical role in the treatment of COVID-19 patients. A comprehensive study by Nikbakht Nasrabadi et al. (2022) found that hospital authorities and policymakers may contribute to ensuring that patients receive high-quality treatment during the COVID-19 pandemic by providing enough support and training and taking into account ICU nurses' work satisfaction.

General Well-Being subscale

Five out of six items in the General Well-Being subscale were described as “agree” with the WRQoL statements, with mean scores ranging from 3.41 – 4.2: a) I feel well at the moment (M-4.19, SD- 0.87), b) I am satisfied with my life (M- 4.01, SD- 0.97), c) In most ways my life is close to ideal (M-3.80, SD- 0.97), d) Generally, things work out well for me (M-4.03, SD- 0.80), and e) Recently, I have been feeling reasonably happy all things considered (M-3.83; SD- 0.87); and one of five items were

described as “neutral” with the mean score ranging from 2.61 – 3.40, i.e., f) Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed (M-3.37, SD- 1.31). The highest mean score was shown by item, “I feel well at the moment”, and the lowest mean score was shown by item, “Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed”.

Hwang and Lee (2023) suggest that ICU nurses who exhibit higher levels of resilience associated to COVID-19 may have an easier time handling the stress and demands of their jobs during the pandemic, which might lead to improved mental health outcomes. In a study of Zhang et al. (2021), they conclusively stated that optimism could increase the chance of higher work satisfaction. However, in the study of Galanis et al. (2023), they found that nurses encountered diminished levels of job satisfaction, with the advent of the COVID-19 epidemic exacerbating the deterioration of their working conditions. Also, this was supported by the findings of Aiken et al. (2023) in which nurses have been found to experience higher rates of dissatisfaction during the pandemic. In consonance with the study of Almeida et al. (2023), that despite of the disruptive environment, they discovered that nurses had significantly higher well-being scores. Their research during the epidemic revealed that mindfulness was an important personal resource that enhanced nurses' well-being at work. According to Gunasekara & Zheng (2019), nurses who practice mindfulness are more likely to be able to cope with high job demands and stressful situations.

According to Nikbakht Nasrabadi et al. (2022), ICU nurses were more worried than other nurses because they were dealing with problems like organizational support in addition to being in the middle of the crisis and risking infection for themselves and their loved ones. As a result, they attempted to save their lives and well-being by engaging in a variety of behaviors in order to remain safe and healthy. In some studies,

it was found that one of the nurses' coping techniques when caring for COVID-19 patients was an approach called responsible self-protection. In order to care for COVID-19 patients, these mechanisms include the willingness to participate in laboratory testing (Fernández-Castillo et al., 2021), the provision of personal protective equipment (PPE), and strict adherence to PPE guidelines. For instance, they usually used three pairs of gloves when doing operations (Hu et al., 2021). Additionally, they made an effort to preserve their physical and emotional well being by practicing positivity, attending religious events, spending time with friends and family, having fun, and accepting themselves for who they are (Aydin et al., 2021). As stated by participant A, he said *that “the tiredness, stress, and worry. that’s a different story. Some of us may cry to vent out our feelings. Some of us may laugh and some of us may sing. So that’s how we express ourselves.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 98-101).

Item, “Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed” which was described as neutral, implies the ICU nurses neither agree or disagree towards the feeling of unhappiness and depression during caring critically ill patient amidst the pandemic. As stated by participant B, she said that *“I felt sad and sorry for the patient. She did not even want to have COVID at first place it seems she’s too far away from her loved ones and nobody’s beside her.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 268-270). Some nurse displayed mixed emotional expressions like the experience shared by participant E, saying that *“so far, it’s very tiring, and there are times that you will be happy especially you have seen your patient improving and about to be discharge in the ICU. The feeling that you have something to do more for the patient.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 151-154).

The nurses in several studies reported conflicting emotions on their employment

in the intensive care unit. Negative emotional reactions, including tension, dread, and concern about contracting the infection and spreading it to loved ones, were expressed by almost all nurses (Andersson et al., 2022). Furthermore, during pandemic, nurses experienced worry, helplessness, pangs of conscience, loneliness, and anguish (Conz et al, 2021). They were also highly depressed and sad as they faced the patients' death (Green et al, 2022).

Home-Work Interface subscale

All three items in the Home-Work Interface subscale were described as “agree” with the WRQoL statements, with mean scores ranging from 3.41 – 4.2: a) My employer provides adequate facilities and flexibility for me to fit work in around my family life (M-4.09, SD- 0.76), b) My current working hours / patterns suit my personal circumstances (M- 4.06; SD- 0.96), and c) My line manager actively promotes flexible working hours/patterns (M-3.90, SD- 0.90). The highest mean score was shown by item, “My employer provides adequate facilities and flexibility for me to fit work in around my family life”, and the lowest mean score was shown by item, “My line manager actively promotes flexible working hours/patterns”.

These data showed that ICU nurses agree that the employers of nurses give them sufficient resources and flexibility so they may work around their personal life. The degree to which nurses feel their organization understands and makes an effort to assist them in addressing personal difficulties is the definition of the home-work interaction domain, according to Easton and Laar (2018). Having some choice over the where, when, and how nurses work is connected to the work-life balance of nurses. It is attained when nurses have more fulfillment both within and outside of their paid jobs, to the mutual advantage of their profession.

According to a study done in India by Poulouse and Sudarsan (2017), introducing flexible and family-friendly work practices may encourage employees to actively bring their families to work, which would successfully balance the demands of work and home life. The implementation of organizational practices, such as the provision of flexible work hours and the provision of assistance from supervisors and colleagues, contributes to the establishment of a work environment that is both meaningful and supportive. Consequently, this has a favorable effect on the general sense of well-being and personal pleasure of the personnel. Furthermore, the provision of managerial support and the implementation of flexible working arrangements have the potential to enhance social processes within the healthcare sector. These measures enable nurses to collaborate effectively as cohesive groups, hence emphasizing and enhancing the improvement of care quality (Kjellström et al., 2017).

Stress at Work subscale

On Stress at Work subscale, all two items were described as “agree” with the WRQoL statements: a) I often feel under pressure at work (M-3.99, SD- 0.91), b) I often feel excessive levels of stress at work (M-3.77, SD- 1.01).

During focus group discussion, the researcher noted participant’s I statement with regards to their work in the ICU while handling COVID-19 patients. She said that *“It’s very challenging to handle patients with COVID-19 before. Because... we are used to dealing with critical patients, yes! But critical patient with COVID is another thing. So, it’s very difficult to manage as you are also concerned with your health.”* (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 247-251). Also, participant E agreeably stated that *“my experience was the patient became so toxic along with other physicians that were also toxic. So, I couldn’t withstand on it, I burst out, then suddenly I cried.”* (FGD Transcript

2, Line No. 301-304). Consistent with the findings of Mailani et al.'s study from 2022, they discovered that nurses employed in intensive care units had a range of challenges among the COVID-19 epidemic. Working under pressure, running into problems when providing patient care, and trying to make ends meet in inadequate professional environments were a few of these difficulties.

Işık and Özdemir (2023) conducted qualitative research and found that while care for critically sick patients caused stress for ICU nurses, most of them did not consider quitting their jobs. In this study, the narratives of the participants seemed to express an act of quitting their profession due to the stress they encountered. Participant 1 mentioned that *“Our colleagues wanted to quit their job, they want to resign but unfortunately, they cannot because we are like... forced to work because we are front liners. So, you are not allowed to quit because it’s your profession.”* (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 181-184). Based on previous research, it has been established a link between the quality of working life among nurses and their job satisfaction, which in turn influences their decision to either remain in or leave from their profession. Job dissatisfaction and burnout can arise as a result of several problems and shortcomings in this particular domain (Abassi et al., 2017).

Additionally, Shechter et al. (2020) discovered that frontline nurses who are actively involved in patient care, such as those assigned to intensive care units, experience greater levels of stress. This is explained by the nature of their jobs, which require them to spend more time providing patients with social and emotional support in addition to direct medical care.

Control of Work subscale

On the Control of Work subscale, all three items were described as “agree” with

the WRQoL statements: a) I feel able to voice opinions and influence changes in my area of work (M- 4.17, SD- 0.76), b) I am involved in decisions that affect me in my own area of work (M- 4.20, SD-0.73), and c) I am involved in decisions that affect members of the public in my own area of work (M-3.80, SD-0.84). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “I am involved in decisions that affect me in my own area of work”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “I am involved in decisions that affect members of the public in my own area of work”.

According to what one focus group member articulated, he or she would formally handle issues that would develop in his unit by participating in a certain decision-making procedure. He greatly emphasized that “Since I am a senior, I opt to write a letter to address to my superiors what exactly has happened. So, I have to protect myself. and also, would really like to report something that the institution would change. So that it could affect change and in the future it will not happen.” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 294-298). In particular, the notion of control in the work domain concerns how much nurses believe they can manage their work environment, including having the flexibility to express their thoughts and take part in decision-making. The feeling of control may be associated with other facets of the nursing profession, such as the ability to actively participate in decision-making processes that impact nurses (Easton & Laar, 2018). In a qualitative study conducted by Rhéaume et al. (2022), nurses expressed a desire for increased involvement in the decision-making processes pertaining to patient care and unit policy. The participants regarded this as a reasonable right due to their exposure to potential harm while providing care for infectious patients within suboptimal conditions. Nurses held the belief that enhancing transparency in meetings with families was crucial for facilitating

discussions regarding the patient's prognosis, as this may contribute to informed decision-making and mitigate patient distress. According to Raftery et al. (2020), intensive care unit (ICU) nurses possess a favorable vantage point for instigating discussions pertaining to end-of-life matters with families. Additionally, Taylor (2020) highlights that these nurses frequently express a preference for involvement in treatment related decision-making processes.

Working Conditions subscale

On the Working Conditions subscale, all three items were described as “agree” with the WRQoL statements: a) My employer provides me with what I need to do my job effectively (M- 3.96, SD- 0.94), b) I work in a safe environment (M-3.97, SD- 0.92), and c) The working conditions are satisfactory (M-3.77, SD- 0.85). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “I work in a safe environment”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “The working conditions are satisfactory”.

Study participant H verbalized that “proper work-related quality of life is essential in a sense that we need to give our wholesome effort especially when it comes to environmental factors, cleanliness, emotional support, safety and security of the patient.” (FGD Transcript 2, Line No. 113-116). Essentially, the domain of working conditions pertains to the degree of satisfaction among nurses with the essential resources, working environment, and security required for the efficient execution of their duties. This encompasses various elements of the occupational setting, such as shift rotations and working schedules, remuneration, provision of tools and equipment, as well as measures pertaining to safety and security. Teixeira et al. (2020) define the idea of a nurse's working conditions as having access to social support, security, high pay, a reasonable workload, professional recognition, and opportunities for

advancement. And it's widely believed that these kinds of benefits have a big influence on nurses' decisions to stay in their profession, which keeps the team cohesive, skilled, and productive. As describe by Llop-Gironés et al. (2021), the working conditions experienced by numerous nurses across the globe are characterized by instability and uncertainty. The ongoing pandemic has brought about increased awareness regarding the susceptibility of nurses to various elements that pose risks to their health.

Caring Behaviors of Nurses

The mean and standard deviation of responses to the CBI-24 questions were calculated for the nurses to see where they scored well or poorly (score per question is indicated by its mean range where 1.00-1.83 is described as never; 1.84-2.66 as almost never; 2.67-3.49 as occasionally; 3.50-4.32 as usually; 4.33-5.15 as always; and 5.16-6.00 as always).

Table 10

Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Caring Behavior per Subscale

Subscale	Mean	Standard Deviation
Caring Behavior	5.69	0.57
Assurance of Human Presence	5.61	0.69
Professional Knowledge & Skills	5.75	0.51
Respectfulness	5.71	0.53
Positive Connectedness	5.67	0.55

Interpretation:

The table showed that among the four subscales of caring behavior, the knowledge and skills found to be the highest domain (M=5.75, SD=0.51) and is verbally interpreted as “always”. Essentially, in this domain, its high mean score reflects ICU nurses’ knowledge on how to give shots and intravenous lines. On the other hand, the domain of assurance of human presence tends to have a lowest mean

score (M=5.61, SD=0.69) of which it further explains on how nurses treated their patient as an individual. To note, the result of the study contradicts the study findings of Ferede et al. (2023) in which the assurance of human presence domain ranked highest and positive connectedness ranked as lowest.

According to Credland et al. (2021), to provide patients with optimal treatment, it is imperative that healthcare professionals possess the requisite knowledge and skills to operate at an advanced level, while ensuring uniformity throughout all critical care units. As cited by Ahmed et al. (2022) that in other countries like Jordan and United Arab Emirates, it revealed that the caring behavior of ICU nurses in terms of "assurance of human presence" and "respectfulness" were given greater importance compared to "knowledge and skills" and "connectedness". The results of their study suggest that critical care nurses prioritize the provision of psychological support through assurance of human presence and addressing professional and technical facets of care.

In the Philippines, Peramide (2023) found that the level of nurses' caring behavior as measured similarly via CBI-24 was very high and the domain of assurance of human presence was ranked as the highest while positive connectedness was ranked as the lowest. Additionally, based on a recent study conducted by Kibret et al. (2022), their findings also indicate that there is a generally positive level of caring behaviors exhibited by nurses working in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). The study further reveals that the overall level of caring behaviors is high, as measured by the CBI-24 assessment tool. Such results could be attributed to differences in educational attainment, attitudes, healthcare environments, and workload (Delmas et al., 2020).

Table 11*Means and Standard Deviations of Nurses' Caring Behavior per Item*

Item No.	Question	Mean	Standard Deviation
CARING BEHAVIOR			
Decision Making			
1	Attentively listening to the patient	5.81	0.75
2	Giving instructions or teaching the patient	5.79	0.70
3	Treating the patient as an individual	5.96	0.20
4	Spending time with the patient	5.37	0.76
5	Supporting the patient	5.49	0.78
6	Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	5.63	0.59
7	Helping the patient grow	5.51	0.74
8	Being patient or tireless with the patient	5.30	0.97
Knowledge and Skills			
9	Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	5.93	0.31
10	Being confident with the patient	5.74	0.61
11	Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill	5.77	0.52
12	Managing equipment skillfully	5.57	0.63
13	Allowing the patient to express feelings about his or her disease and treatment	5.76	0.46
Respectfulness			
14	Including the patient in planning his or her care	5.61	0.64
15	Treating patient information confidentially	5.87	0.45
16	Returning to the patient voluntarily	5.64	0.54
17	Talking with the patient	5.67	0.56
18	Encouraging the patient to call if there are problems	5.81	0.43
19	Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs	5.66	0.54
Positive Connectedness			
20	Responding quickly to the patient's call	5.64	0.54
21	Helping to reduce the patient's pain	5.73	0.59
22	Showing concern for the patient	5.90	0.30

Interpretation:

All Items in each of the subscales on caring behaviors of nurses were measured also using the mean and standard deviation of their responses to the CBI-24 questions.

(See table 11)

Decision-Making subscale

All the eight items in the Decision-Making subscale were described as “always”, with a mean score >5.16 : a) Attentively listening to the patient (M-5.81, SD- 0.75), b) Giving instructions or teaching the patient (M-5.79, SD- 0.70), c) Treating the patient as an individual (M-5.96, SD- 0.20), d) Spending time with the patient (M-5.37, SD- 0.76), e) Supporting the patient (M- 5.49, SD- 0.78), f) Being empathetic or identifying with the patient (M- 5.63, SD- 0.59), g) Helping the patient grow (M- 5.51, SD-0.74), and h) Being patient or tireless with the patient (M-5.30, SD- 0.97). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “Treating the patient as an individual”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “Being patient or tireless with the patient”.

Notably, participant C, elaborated that *“caring behaviors is important not only in the ICU but in general as a nurse. Because if you do not treat your patients properly, come to think about what others would also think towards your parents, your family, or even your relatives in general. So, you need to treat your patients like a family, letting them feel that you will not leave them.”* (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 169-174). Though the third item has the lowest mean value 5.37, it would also entail that critical care nurses have always demonstrated the act of spending time with their patients.

According to Watson's Theory, the essence of nursing is around facilitating the patient's attainment of a heightened state of equilibrium encompassing the physical, mental, and spiritual aspects, which is accomplished through compassionate interactions that entail a transpersonal caring connection. Relatively, applying the Watson's third *caritas* on the concept of being sensitive to oneself and others through the cultivation of personal spiritual practices, transcending one's ego to achieve a transpersonal presence, explains that critical care nurses can establish a more trusting

and caring relationship with patients by being attuned to their needs and emotions. This entails showing real interest in other people, turning everyday tasks into therapeutic relationships, acknowledging and embracing the underlying goodness of oneself and other people as fellow humans, and engaging in practice from a point of empathy and compassion (Watson, 2018).

In a narrative study conducted by Jimenez et al. (2020) found that Filipino nurses in the ICU reported that the physical presence was beneficial in providing comfort to the patient. The provision of an irreplaceable source of consolation was achieved through the facilitation of human interaction and emotional connection between the patient and their family. Redona (2018) also emphasized that generally, Filipinos are renowned for their genuine care, loving nature, and tender touch (Redona, 2018).

Knowledge and Skills subscale

All the five items in the Knowledge and Skills subscale were described as “always”, with a mean score >5.16 : a) Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc. (M-5.93, SD- 0.31), b) Being confident with the patient (M-5.74, SD- 0.61), c) Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill (M-5.77, SD-0.52), d) Managing equipment skillfully (M- 5.57, SD- 0.63), and e) Allowing the patient to express feelings about his or her disease and treatment (M- 5.76, SD- 0.40). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “Managing equipment skillfully”. This data indicate that nurses in the ICU always demonstrated their knowledge on how to give shots, intravenous lines, etc. As mentioned by participant A, *“nurse should be able to acquire skills not just physical skills but also the measured skills that is required being an ICU nurse. Example of*

these skills will be well-versed of the advanced cardiac life support, basic life support and IVT training. You need to be master in giving medications through various channels like intravenous, intra-osseus, Sub-Q, intramuscular.” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 34-39).

According to Watson's theory, providing care can also be thought of as "instrumental caring," which refers to using technical know-how to meet a patient's basic physical needs. Examples of this include starting an intravenous medication and giving patients the necessary painkillers (Kang et al., 2021). Such result appertaining to the first items had similar findings conducted by Hamdan et al. (2022) in Jordan, in which the ICU nurses demonstrated adequate knowledge in their in terms of intravenous medication preparation and administration. A significant proportion of intensive care unit (ICU) nurses hold the belief that the calculation of intravenous drug dosages plays a crucial role in mitigating errors during medication preparation. Likewise, findings conducted by Teshome et al. (2023) in Ethiopia also showed that nurses have an adequate knowledge on IVF administration. More specifically, nurses' skills like adjusting flow rate of fluid given, checking the amount of fluid, and type of fluid were always practiced by Ethiopian nurses. Furthermore, these nurses concur that the ongoing assessment of clinical skills pertaining to the safe administration of drug therapy via intravenous route is essential.

Essentially, Plutnská and Plevová (2019) found that nurses who received more than 10 hours per week of continuous education performed IV medication preparation and administration significantly more accurately. As highlighted, adequate knowledge is crucial for reducing medication errors. Nursing education was one of the interventions that reduced medication errors.

Respectfulness subscale

All the six items in Respectfulness subscale were described as “always”, with a mean score >5.16 : a) Including the patient in planning his or her care (M-5.61, SD-0.64), b) Treating patient information confidentially (M-5.87, SD- 0.45), c) Returning to the patient voluntarily (M- 5.64, SD- 0.54), d) Talking with the patient (M- 5.67, SD- 0.56), e) Encouraging the patient to call if there are problems (M- 5.81, SD-0.43), and f) Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs (M-5.66, SD-0.50). The highest mean score was shown by the item, “Treating the patient information confidentially”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “Including the patient in planning his or her care”.

These study results also share similar findings from a descriptive cross- sectional study of Abuhammad et al. (2020) in which they determined that the measures implemented by nurses to safeguard and preserve the confidentiality of patient data were deemed satisfactory. Also, a substantial percentage of the nurses demonstrated the implementation of suitable measures to safeguard data security. However, there is a need for improvement in the practices that safeguard patient confidentiality in terms of accessing, exchanging, and transferring patient data. According to their study's findings, most nurses have a good awareness of security and confidentiality issues and have positive opinions about them.

Tariq and Hackert (2023) explicate that healthcare professionals are advised under the quantity of information to protect patient privacy. When engaging in conversation in a patient's room, it is imperative to exercise discretion and refrain from

disclosing any detailed details. When it becomes necessary to convey the findings of

a certain surgical procedure, it is customary to request the patient's presence in a designated private space for the purpose of engaging in a dialogue. In this context, it is advisable to exclusively reveal information that is pertinent to the subject matter. When healthcare professionals like nurses encounter a scenario when there are other patients present, such as in the intensive care unit (ICU), it is advisable to engage in a comprehensive discussion that avoids details regarding procedures or diagnoses. Furthermore, nurses in critical care units have ethical challenges pertaining to the preservation of patient confidentiality in relation to health information. Frequently, patients may experience incoherence or physical instability, rendering them unable of independently making informed choices on the privacy of their personal health data. Families possess an inherent desire for information regarding their relatives, driven by a deep sense of love and worry. The complexity of this issue arises for individuals seeking medical care, their families, and healthcare professionals due to the presence of legislation pertaining to patient confidentiality (Newman & Kjervik, 2019).

Connectedness subscale

All the five items in Connectedness subscale were described as “always”, with a mean score >5.16 : a) Responding quickly to the patient's call (M-5.64, SD- 0.54), b) Helping to reduce the patient's pain (M-5.73, SD- 0.59), c) Showing concern for the patient (M-5.90, SD- 0.30), d) Giving the patient's treatments and medications on time (M-5.54, SD- 0.72), and e) Relieving the patient's symptoms (M-5.53,SD-0.58).

The highest mean score was shown by the item, “Showing concern for the patient”, and the lowest mean score was shown by the item, “Relieving the patient’s symptoms”.

The importance of showing genuine care by the nurse for their patients confined in the ICU was reflected from articulation of participant E, saying that “*giving care is* Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 97

too important to me, not just for myself but also for the patient and patient's family.....something that is for the best of your patient” (FGD Transcript 1, Line No. 195-197). This confirmed the notion that in a study by Karaca and Durna (2019), they found that patients expressed higher levels of satisfaction with the concern and caring rendered by the nurses and described nursing care offered during hospitalization as excellent.

According to Kwame and Petrucka (2021) when nurses neglect to attend to the concerns expressed by patients, the implementation of patient-centered care practices is compromised. Moreover, Atashzadeh-Shoorideh et al. (2021), emphasizes that the ability of nurses to allocate sufficient time to patients is crucial in facilitating an accurate assessment of patients' needs and providing an opportunity for patients to articulate their concerns. Additionally, applying the theory of Watson, the ICU nurses' attitude in showing concern for the welfare of their patients relates to the Watson's concept of humanistic caring under the first clinical caritas which pertains to the nurse's practice of loving, kindness, empathy, and equanimity for self and others, which are said to be the universal and altruistic values (Watson, 2018).

Nurse Competence on Patient Safety and their Caring Behaviors

Table 12

Relationship between Nurse Competence on Patient Safety and Caring Behavior of Nurses

Variable	Caring Behavior			Remarks
	r_s	p -value	Decision	
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	0.762	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ (Significant); r_s = Spearman-rho coefficient value; IV = Nurse Competence on Patient Safety; DV = Caring Behavior

Interpretation:

The relationship between nurse competence on patient safety and their caring behavior was shown in table 12. Specifically, the strength of correlation between the two variables is very strong ($r_s=0.762$. $p= 0.000$) and directly proportional. This further suggests that an increase in nurse competence on patient safety is correlated with an increase in the nurses' caring behavior.

This is consistent with the research of Asuncion (2020), which shows that professional nursing competency results in professional, compassionate conduct that has a direct impact on the provision of safe, high-quality healthcare. The idea of nurse competence, according to Zaitoun et al. (2023), includes the skills, knowledge, and abilities that nurses need to provide safe, effective care in a variety of areas, including patient safety. Essentially, the provision of safe care to patients can be compromised when nurses lack the necessary competence (Chang & Manojlovich., 2023).

As emphasized by Torkaman et al. (2020), ensuring patient safety is a fundamental aspect of the healthcare process as it aims to mitigate and prevent any potential harm to the patients. The study's conclusion supported the conclusions of Ambarika and Anggraini (2021), who found a strong correlation between compassionate conduct and patient safety. Additionally, they also elaborated that caring is a proactive action that seeks to deliver both physical care and emotional support, with the goal of enhancing the client's feelings of security and safety. Caring relates to the consistent provision of physical and mental care, with the aim of enhancing the patient's overall sense of security. Nurses possess the necessary skills and expertise to deliver comprehensive nursing care to patients, demonstrating a commitment to treating patients as human beings deserving of respect and appreciation.

Work-related Quality of Life of Nurses and their Caring Behaviors

Table 13

Relationship between Work-related Quality of Life and Caring Behavior of Nurses

Variable	Caring Behavior			Remarks
	r_s	p -value	Decision	
Work-related Quality of Life	0.555	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant

Note: $p < 0.05$ (Significant); r_s = Spearman-rho coefficient value; IV = Work-related Quality of Life; DV = Caring Behavior.

Interpretation:

The relationship between work-related quality of life and caring behavior of nurses has been shown by Table 13. The Spearman's rho (r_s) test revealed a coefficient value ($r_s = 0.555$, $p = .000$) that significantly shows a positive strong correlation between the work-related quality of life and caring behavior of nurses. Since the two variables shows direct proportionality with each other, it further implies that an increase in work-related quality of life is correlated with an increase in the nurses' caring behavior.

It was evident from the nurse's experience during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic in which they express their challenges and difficulties in handling critical patients which significantly affects their caring capacities. It can also be noted that the occurrence of stress in the workplace experienced by critical nurses during the pandemic also contributes a negative effect on their work-related quality of life. Notably, the impact of such stress on the quality of life of nurses is predominantly negative. Additionally, it has the potential to diminish the quality of care provided by nurses and thereby impact the caring behavior (Babapour et al., 2022).

Similar to this, Inocian et al. (2021) noted that nurses' opinions of care and the

satisfaction of their work life vary. Additionally, they discovered that the clinical nurses had a somewhat high professional quality of life, which was connected to their compassionate actions. Such findings were also congruent from the study of Shirvani et al. (2023), stating that quality of life among nurses was significantly and directly correlated with their caring behaviors during the time of COVID-19 pandemic.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In an effort to address each research topic, this chapter provides a summary of all the important findings from the study. It also provided relevant, and conclusions and recommendations made by the researcher on the basis of the identified findings of the study.

Summary

The primary objectives of this study were to characterize the caring behaviors of nurses, work-related quality of life, and nursing competence in patient safety. It also concentrated on whether the caring behavior of nurses is correlated with their skill in patient safety and work-related quality of life. The following were the significant findings derived from the study:

I – On Nurse Competence of Patient Safety

a) In the decision-making domain, all items were interpreted as “always” with an overall mean of 4.72. Its highest mean of 4.80 was attributed to the fifth item about the nurse’s recognition of their role and how they act accordingly. Conversely, the first indicator under decision- making domain got the lowest mean value (M=4.63, SD=0.49) indicating that nurses solve problems in the clinical practice.

b) In terms of all sub-indicators of nurses’ competence on patient safety in collaboration domain, it was interpreted as “always” with an overall mean of 4.62 and a standard deviation of 0.62. On the other hand, the fourth sub-indicator asking nurses if they share anxiety with others, got a lowest mean value (M=3.87, SD=1.18).

c) In terms of nursing intervention domain, it showed a verbal interpretation

of “always” with its fifth item having the highest average value ($M=4.89$, $SD=0.36$) demonstrating that ICU nurses always use the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) method when performing a physical evaluation. Furthermore, the lowest mean value ($M=4.59$, $SD=0.63$) for the third sub-indicator shows that nurses consistently carry out the doctor's directions within a 5-minute window. Regarding the nurses' competence on patient safety in principles of nursing care domain, its first item has the highest mean value ($M=4.90$, $SD=0.30$), and is verbally interpreted as “always”, implying that nurses valued what the patient says. On the other hand, the third sub-indicator under the domain of principles of nursing care got a lowest mean value ($M=4.74$, $SD=0.50$), which implies that nurses always listen attentively to the patient's family's anxiety.

d) In general, in the aspect of nurse's competence on patient safety, the highest mean score was the principle of nursing care ($WM=4.81$, $SD=0.40$) while collaboration domain received the lowest mean score ($M=4.62$, $SD=0.62$).

II – On Work-Related Quality of Life

e) With an overall mean score of 4.31, all items in the domain of work and career satisfaction were interpreted as "strongly agree." The first item, which measures job and career satisfaction out of the six, has the highest mean ($M=4.64$, $SD=0.54$), suggesting that nurses have specific objectives and want to empower themselves to do their jobs. On the other hand, the sixth item received a lowest weighted mean value ($WM=3.90$, $SD=1.01$) under the job and career satisfaction domain.

f) The general well-being category was assessed as "agree" overall mean ($M=3.87$, $SD=0.97$) for the nurses' work-related quality of life. The first item ($M=4.19$, $SD=0.87$) had the greatest weighted mean, suggesting that nurses were feeling well

at that particular time. The second question ($M=3.37$, $SD=1.31$) had the lowest mean value and is evaluated as "neutral" by voice.

g) The home-work interface domain was verbally interpreted as "agree". Its first item has the highest mean value ($M=4.09$, $SD=0.76$), and was read orally as "agree," meaning that the employer of nurses offers sufficient facilities and flexibility so that they may fit work around their personal life. Furthermore, the third item's mean value was the lowest ($M=3.90$, $SD=0.97$) with same verbal interpretation to the first item.

h) In terms of stress at work domain, it was verbally interpreted as "agree". The first item indicates under this domain indicates that nurses in the ICU often feel under pressure at work ($M=3.99$, $SD=0.91$). In similar way, nurses have also agreed responding towards their feeling of excessive levels of stress at work ($M=3.77$, $SD=1.01$).

i) With its greatest weighted mean value pointed toward the second item in the control at work domain, it was evaluated as "agree" ($M=4.06$, $SD=0.78$), suggesting that nurses involved in choices that impact themselves in their own field of work ($M= 4.20$, $SD=0.73$). Meanwhile, the third item received a lowest mean value ($M=3.80$, $SD=0.84$) indicating that nurses also agreed to the involvement in decisions that affect members of the public in their own area of work.

j) In terms of working conditions domain, it was generally interpreted as "agree" of which the second item got the highest mean value ($M=3.97$, $SD=0.92$), indicating that nurses worked in a safe environment. Also, nurses have a neutral response implying that they neither agree or disagree that working conditions are satisfactory ($M=3.77$, $SD=0.85$).

The job career satisfaction domain of nurses had the highest mean

score (M=4.31, SD=0.70) in the total work-related quality of life domain. This suggests that ICU nurses have distinct goals and objectives that help them do their jobs. Furthermore, out of the six indicators of nurses' work-related quality of life, the general well-being domain had the lowest mean score (M=3.87, SD=0.97).

III – On Caring Behaviors

k) In the assurance of human presence domain, all items had a positive result and is verbally interpreted as “always” (M=5.61, SD=0.69). Its third item has the highest score which implies that critical care nurses always treated the patient as an individual (M=5.96, SD=0.20).

l) With regards to the knowledge and skills domain, all items had an overall mean of 5.75 and was verbally interpreted as “always”. The first item had the highest mean score (M=5.93, SD=0.31, suggesting that ICU nurses consistently showed that they knew how to administer injections and IV lines.

m) In the respectfulness domain, all items were interpreted as “always” (M=5.71, SD=0.53) with the second item having a highest reported mean score (M=5.87, SD=0.45) indicating that ICU nurses always treated patient's information confidentially. On the other hand, its first item received a lowest mean score of 5.61 and still verbally interpreted as always, indicating that ICU nurses always include the patient in planning his or her care.

n) In terms of the positive connectedness domain, it was overall interpreted as “always” (M=5.64, SD=0.54) with the highest weighted mean value that was directed to the third item indicating that nurses always show concern for their patient (M= 5.90, SD=0.30).

o) Generally speaking, the knowledge and skills domain received the

highest mean score ($M=5.75$, $SD=0.51$) out of the four indications of nurses' compassionate conduct. However, the area of assurance of human presence, which further reveals how nurses handled each patient as a person, had the lowest mean score ($M=5.61$, $SD=0.69$).

p) In terms of the relationship between level of nurse competence on patient safety and caring behavior of nurses, it shows a significant positive relationship between self- concept and caring behavior ($r_s = 0.762$, $p = 0.000$). The very strong and direct proportionality of the strength of correlation between the variables implies that an increase in nurse competence on patient safety is correlated with an increase in the nurses' caring behavior.

q) The results of the study indicate that there is a significant positive strong correlation ($r_s = 0.555$, $p = .000$) and direct proportionality between the two variables, indicating that an increase in the quality of life at work and an increase in the caring behavior of nurses are correlated.

Conclusion

The study revealed that there are essential domains appertaining to the nurses' competence on patient safety, work-related quality of life and caring behavior of nurses. Primarily, it was found that the principle of nursing care domain was observed by the nurses as one of the elements of clinical competence of nurses that involves nursing interventions that foster a therapeutic, caring, and encouraging atmosphere for patients in an effort to ease their discomfort and minimize needless suffering. Also, the job and career satisfaction domain were highlighted to be important consideration towards contentment with their job, career, clarity of their goals and role

ambiguity while working in the ICU during the pandemic. With regards to the caring behavior of nurses, the domain on knowledge and skills were given emphasis as this area plays a pivotal role in rendering quality nursing care. This serves as an important element and the core of the nursing profession to maintain safe delivery of holistic care for the critically ill patients.

Significantly, the correlation exists between the nurses' competence on patient safety and caring behavior. Similarly, the nurses' work-related quality of life also showed a positive and strong relationship towards their caring behavior. As a result, an increase in a nurse's competence for patient safety and work-related quality of life is also correlated with an increase in the level of caring behavior exhibited by nurses, particularly in the areas of assurance of human presence, knowledge and skills, respectfulness, and positive connectedness, due to the direct proportionality between the two.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions led to the formulation of the following recommendations, which are provided for thought:

1. In the aspect of nursing profession, the researcher considers the establishment of a culture that promotes continuous learning which is crucial for enhancing the safety competency among critical care nurses. This culture should foster an environment where nurses are motivated and assisted in expanding their knowledge and honing their skills specifically in critical care concepts to ultimately ensure the delivery of a safe and high-quality care to their patients.

In the aspect of nursing research, the researcher strongly recommends doing further

study involving research designs like mixed method and regression analysis in order to carefully evaluate what other factors may have the potential to affect or influence the caring behavior of nurses working the in the critical care unit.

2. The research also recommends a proposed intervention program (Basic Nursing Critical Care Program) through utilizing the principle of 7th Caritas outlined from the Watson's theory of Human Caring, with the aim of enhancing the caring behavior of nurses across the four vital domains (assurance of human presence, knowledge and skills, respectfulness, and positive connectedness).

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

Part I. Nurses Demographic Profile

Age:	
Sex:	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/>
Education:	<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's Degree in Nursing <input type="checkbox"/> Master's Degree in Nursing <input type="checkbox"/> PhD Degree in Nursing
Years of experience:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Newly hired 1-5 years <input type="checkbox"/> 6-10 years <input type="checkbox"/> 11-15 years <input type="checkbox"/> 16-20 years <input type="checkbox"/> More than 20 years
Attendance in nursing conference:	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

Part II. Caring Behaviors Inventory-24 NURSE VERSION

Directions: Please read the list of items that describe nurse caring. For each item please **circle** the answer that stands for the extent that you made caring visible to patients.

Remember, **you** are the **nurse!**

1.	Attentively listening to the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
2.	Giving instructions or teaching the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
3.	Treating the patient as an individual.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
4.	Spending time with the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
5.	Supporting the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always

6.	Being empathetic or identifying with the patient	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
7.	Helping the patient grow.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
8.	Being patient or tireless with the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
9.	Knowing how to give shots, IVs, etc.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
10.	Being confident with the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
11.	Demonstrating professional knowledge and skill.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
12.	Managing equipment skillfully.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
13.	Allowing the patient to express feelings about his or her disease and treatment.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
4.	Including the patient in planning his or her care.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
5.	Treating patient information confidentially.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always

6.	Returning to the patient voluntarily.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
7.	Talking with the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
8.	Encouraging the patient to call if there are problems.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
9.	Meeting the patient's stated and unstated needs.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
0.	Responding quickly to the patient's call.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
1.	Helping to reduce the patient's pain.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
2.	Showing concern for the patient.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
3.	Giving the patient's treatments and medications on time.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always
4.	Relieving the patient's symptoms.	Never	Almost Never	Occasionally	Usually	Almost Always	Always

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Part III. Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety: C3Q-Safety

INSTRUCTION: Please read following statement carefully. Objectively evaluate your actions at ICU. For each statement, circle one number from 1 to 5.

	Items	Never	Seldom	About Half the Time	Usually	Always
	Before a patient enters the ICU, you have prepared the items needed for the patient care.	1	2	3	4	5
	You begin patient monitoring within 3 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU.	1	2	3	4	5
	You begin physical examination within 5 minutes of the patient arriving at the ICU.	1	2	3	4	5
	You execute the doctor's orders on time (within 5 minutes).	1	2	3	4	5
	You conduct a physical assessment using the ABC (Airway, Breathing, Circulation) approach.	1	2	3	4	5
	When you notice abnormal vital sign or specific physical findings, you tell a doctor or other nurses.	1	2	3	4	5
	You prioritize a monitoring and an execution of doctor's orders according to the patient's condition.	1	2	3	4	5
	You frequently communicate with co-worker ICU nurses.	1	2	3	4	5
	You frequently communicate with other medical staff (e.g. pharmacist, physical therapist, clinical engineering technicians).	1	2	3	4	5
0	You share your anxiety with others.	1	2	3	4	5
1	You repeat oral instructions aloud.	1	2	3	4	5
2	You can recognize your role and act accordingly.	1	2	3	4	5

3	You can fulfill your role.	1	2	3	4	5
4	You clean up empty medicines and organize complicated infusion lines.	1	2	3	4	5
5	You respond flexibly to changed orders.	1	2	3	4	5
6	After finishing a task, you independently find a new task.	1	2	3	4	5
7	You solve problems in clinical practice.	1	2	3	4	5
8	You take thoughtful care of patients (e.g., smiling, touching).	1	2	3	4	5
9	You value what the patient says.	1	2	3	4	5
0	You actively provide patients with nursing that leads to their recovery.	1	2	3	4	5
1	You listen attentively to the patient's family's anxiety.	1	2	3	4	5
2	You provide nursing equally to all patients.	1	2	3	4	5

Adopted from: Okumura, M., Ishigaki, T., Mori, K., & Fujiwara, Y. (2019). Development of an easy-to-use questionnaire assessing critical care nursing competence in Japan: A cross-sectional study. *PloS one*, 14(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.02256>

Part IV: Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale

This questionnaire is designed to assess your quality of working life. Please do not take too long over each question; we want your first reaction not a long drawn out thought process. Please do not omit any questions. This isn't a test, simply a measure of your attitudes to the factors that influence your experience at work.

**Please indicate your answers by filling in the circles like this: **

To what extent do you agree with the following? <i>Please fill in the appropriate circle.</i>		Strongly Disagree (1)	(2) Disagree	Neutral (3)	(4) Agree	Strongly Agree (5)
1.	I have a clear set of goals and aims to enable me to do my job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2.	I feel able to voice opinions and influence changes in my area of work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3.	I have the opportunity to use my abilities at work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4.	I feel well at the moment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5.	My employer provides adequate facilities and flexibility for me to fit work in around my family life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6.	My current working hours / patterns suit my personal circumstances	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7.	I often feel under pressure at work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8.	When I have done a good job, it is acknowledged by my line manager	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9.	Recently, I have been feeling unhappy and depressed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10.	I am satisfied with my life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11.	I am encouraged to develop new skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2.	I am involved in decisions that affect <u>me</u> in my own area of work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13.	My employer provides me with what I need to do my job effectively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14.	My line manager actively promotes flexible working hours / patterns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15.	In most ways my life is close to ideal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
16.	I work in a safe environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
17.	Generally, things work out well for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
18.	I am satisfied with the career opportunities available for me here	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
19.	I often feel excessive levels of stress at work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
20.	I am satisfied with the training I receive in order to perform my present job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
21.	Recently, I have been feeling reasonably happy all things considered	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
22.	The working conditions are satisfactory	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
23.	I am involved in decisions that affect members of the public in my own area of work.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Adopted from: Simon, E., & Laar, D.V. (2013). Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) Scale: A Measure of Quality of Working Life. 1st ed. www.qowl.co.uk

APPENDIX B

SEMI-STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE FOR FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION (FGD)

1. Can you describe to me your general understanding about the nurse competence on patient safety? How does it affect nurses working in the ICU during the Covid-19 pandemic?
2. Can you give me what are the specific competence necessary for the nurse to possess while caring patients in the ICU? Why do you say so?
3. Can you describe to me your general understanding about the work-related quality of life? How does it affect nurses working in the ICU especially during the times of the pandemic?
4. Amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, how such situation impacts your overall work condition and well-being? Can you please explain why?
5. Can you describe to me about the way you understand caring behaviors? How is it important for nurses working in the ICU? Can you tell me why?
6. Can you give me certain factors that can affect the caring behavior of a nurse while working in the ICU? Why do you say so?
7. What were you feeling and thinking during the last time you cared for a patient with critical care condition especially during the times of Covid-19 pandemic? Can you describe more how this made you feel?
8. What you found the most challenging about your experiences in caring patients in the ICU during the times of the Covid-19 pandemic? Please explain why.
9. How did you overcome those challenges you experienced?

Probing Questions:

- Can you elaborate on that?
- What does this mean to you?

APPENDIX C

INFORMED CONSENT

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program
University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication
& Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

This informed consent form is for hospital registered nurses in Socsargen County Hospital and who I am inviting to participate in my research entitled "**Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines**".

Name of Principal Investigator: **Frederick Orapa RN, USRN**

Name of Organization: **University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU)**

Name of Project: **Thesis N300**

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the study with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you choose to participate)

Part I: Information Sheet

Introduction

I am Frederick Orapa, taking master's degree in nursing. I am doing research on **Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines**.

You have the opportunity to participate in this research study as you describe your competence on patient safety, work-related quality of life, and caring behavior in the intensive care unit. In order for you to decide whether you wish to participate in this research, it is necessary that you will fully understand what is involved and what is expected of you if you wish to participate. This form gives the detailed information about the research being conducted to enable you to make informed decision whether to participate or decline.

Purpose of the research

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between the nurse caring behaviors and nurse competence on patient safety, and the work-related quality of life.

Participant Selection

You are being asked to participate in this study because you meet the inclusion criteria being a nurse handling critical patients and actively working in the intensive care unit of SOCSARGEN County Hospital, General Santos City.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary. It is your choice to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any point of time without any repercussion to your position. The researcher may withdraw you from this study if circumstances warrant removal. Withdrawing from this study will not affect your job in the institution. If you withdraw from this study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

Procedures

If you volunteer to participate in this study, you will be asked to answer questions on four surveys:

- a. Demographic Work Sheet which asks questions about your age, sex, education, years of experience, and attendance in nursing conference.
- b. The Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (CBI-24) which asks you to identify the caring behavior by answering 24 questions.
- c. Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety: C3Q- Safety to objectively evaluate your actions at ICU.
- d. Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale designed to assess your quality of working life.

Duration

The questionnaires will be given to you and I will allot an approximate time of 30-45 minutes to answer the survey. This will take place in the hospital inside your room.

Benefits

Although there are no benefits to you by participating in this study, it can result in increased nursing knowledge which can help to improve nursing care in the intensive care department.

Confidentiality

Your participation in this research is highly confidential. The data will be stored and secured in a locked filing cabinet in the researcher's office to which I have the single key. The UPOU and the SOCSARGEN County Hospital's Institutional Review Board may review records related to this research study. In an event that this

research is to be published, your identity will not be released or contain any identifying information.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so. Hence, such withdrawal will not affect your employment status nor promotion and performance rating.

Part II. Certificate of Consent

I have read (or had read to me) all the above information. The name and the purpose of this study have been explained to me. I fully understand it and agree to take part of the study without any form of coercion and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: _____

Statement by the researcher/person taking consent

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and confirmed that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study. Moreover, all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly to the best of my ability. I confirm that the participant has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

Signature of Researcher /person taking the consent:

Date: _____

APPENDIX D

LETTER OF PERMISSION TO USE THE CBI-24 AND APPROVAL OF OWNER

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program
University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication &
Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

July 14, 2021

ZANE ROBINSON WOLF, PhD, RN, FAAN

Dean Emerita and Professor
School of Nursing and Health Sciences La Salle University
Philadelphia, PA 19141 USA Dear Dr. Wolf,

I am a graduate student at the University of the Philippines Open University writing my proposal study titled “Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines”.

I would like to ask your permission to use the Caring Behavior Inventory Nurse Version necessary for my proposal research study.

The objectives of my study are:

1. To describe the nurse competence on patient safety according to their:
 - 1.1 Decision making;
 - 1.2 Collaboration;
 - 1.3 Nursing intervention; and
 - 1.4 Principles of nursing care.
2. To describe the work-related quality of life among nurses according to
 - 2.1 General Well-Being;
 - 2.2 Work-Home Interface;
 - 2.3 Job and Career Satisfaction;
 - 2.4 Control at Work;
 - 2.5 Working Conditions; and
 - 2.6 Stress at Work.
3. To describe the caring behaviors of nurses according to their:
 - 3.1 Assurance of human presence;
 - 3.2 Professional knowledge & skills;
 - 3.3 Respectfulness; and
 - 3.4 Positive connectedness.
4. To determine the relationship between the nurse competence on patient safety and caring behaviors

5. To determine the relationship between the work-related Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines

quality of life and caring behaviors.

For any question or concerns please feel free to contact my research adviser:

ARACELI O. BALABAGNO, PhD, RN

Professorial Lecturer

University of the Philippines-Open University, and University of the Philippines-Manila, College of Nursing Tel.no.: +63 (2)523-1633 ; Telefax: +63 (2) 528-4014

Thank you very much and God bless!

Sincerely yours,

Frederick E. Orapa, RN

MAN-Adult Health Nursing

Appendix E

LETTER OF REQUEST TO SCH INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD

LETTER OF REQUEST TO THE ASSISTANT MEDICAL DIRECTOR OF SCH

University of the Philippines
Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program
University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication & Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

November 15, 2021

To: ROMEO PASTOR
Assistant Medical Director
SOCSARGEN County Hospital
General Santos City

Dear Sir,

Good day!

I am writing this letter to formally inform you regarding my research study about *"Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines"*.

In line with this, I would like to ask your good office to allow me to conduct my research study in your institution which will include nurses assigned in the intensive care unit.

Rest assured that all pertinent data will be gathered will remain absolutely confidential. I am looking forward for positive response on this humble matter. Your approval to conduct this study will be greatly appreciated.

If you have any queries or concerns regarding my study, please feel free to contact me at +1 469-714-1727 or my email address: frederick.orapa@gmail.com. You may also reach out my adviser:

ARACELI O. BALABAGNO, PhD, RN
Affiliate Faculty – Master of Arts in Nursing – Adult Health Nursing
UP Open University – Learning Center Manila
Chairman, Department of Research, Philippine Nurses Association
Tel.no: +63 (2)523-1633
Telefax: +63 (2) 528-4014

Thank you very much and more power!

Respectfully yours,

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN
MAN-Adult Health Nursing Student

DR. ROMEO PASTOR

LETTER OF PERMISSION TO THE NURSING DIRECTOR OF SCH

University of the Philippines
Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program
University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication & Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

November 5, 2021

To: **Anne Marie V. Niduelan, RN MAN**
Nursing Director
SOCSARGEN County Hospital
General Santos City

Dear Ma'am;

Good day!

I am a student currently enrolled in Master of Arts in Nursing program of the University of the Philippines and is pursuing my study about "Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines".

With this, may I humbly ask regarding the lists of nurses assigned in the ICU and those staff nurses who have been rotated in the ICU. I would like also to formally ask and inform your good office with your sound permission to allow me to conduct my study within your institution.

Rest assured that all pertinent data will be gathered will remain absolutely confidential and will be used for academic purposes only.

I believe that you are with me in my enthusiasm to finish this research endeavour necessary for the successful completion of my research requirement and hopefully graduate my master's degree in nursing. I'm positively looking forward for your response on this humble matter. Your approval to conduct this study will be highly appreciated.

For any queries or concerns, regarding my study, please feel free to contact me at at +1 469-714-1727 or my email address: frederick.orapa@gmail.com.

Thank you very much and more power!

Sincerely yours,

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN
MAN-Adult Health Nursing Student

approved!

Anne Marie V. Niduelan, RN
PIC # 0418193
12/7/21

Appendix F

LETTER OF REQUEST TO THE INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD OF UPOU

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program

University of the Philippines,
Department of Information Communication & Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

(Date)

(Name)

I am Frederick E. Orapa, RN who is pursuing my thesis about “*Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines*”.

In connection with this, I would like to formally ask your permission to conduct my research study. If you may review the population of my study, my participants will include nurses assigned in the intensive care unit of SOCSARGEN County Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines.

Rest assured that all pertinent data will be gathered will remain absolutely confidential and will be used for academic purposes only.

I believe that you are with me in my enthusiasm to finish this research endeavour necessary for the successful completion of my research requirement and hopefully graduate my master’s degree in nursing. With this, I’m positively looking forward for your response on this humble matter. Your approval to conduct this study will be highly appreciated.

For any queries or concerns, regarding my study, please feel free to contact me at +1 469-714-1727 or my email address: frederick.orapa@gmail.com. You may also reach out my adviser:

ARACELI O. BALABAGNO, PhD, RN

Professorial Lecturer

University of the Philippines-Open University, and University of the Philippines-Manila,
College of Nursing Tel.no.: +63 (2)523-1633 ; Telefax: +63 (2) 528-4014

Thank you very much and more power!

Sincerely yours,

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN

MAN-Adult Health Nursing Student

Appendix G

LETTER OF INVITATION TO PARTICIPANTS TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH STUDY

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program

University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication &
Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

(Date)

Dear Participant; Greetings!

My name is Frederick E. Orapa. I am a registered nurse and a graduate student of the University of the Philippines where I am currently working with my study about *“Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines”*. This study is a partial fulfillment of the requirements for my Master’s of Arts in Nursing degree. With this, it has always been interesting and exciting. There has always been something new to learn. That is why, I am inviting you to participate in my research study.

Your participation is completely voluntary. If you agree to participate, you will be expected to complete all the forms in the study packet which includes the Informed Consent, Demographic Information Sheet and the three additional brief questionnaires that measure the study concepts. The entire packet of questionnaires should not take more than 45 minutes to complete. If you do not wish to participate in this study, or decide to withdraw after starting to complete the questionnaires, you may return them to me.

Participation or non-participation in the study will not result in any difference in care that you receive in the ICU today.

First, you will be asked to answer the questions on three surveys:

- a. The Caring Behavior Inventory-24 (CBI-24) which asks you to identify the caring behavior by answering 24 questions
- Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines*

b. Critical Care Nursing Competence Questionnaire for Patient Safety: C3Q- Safety which will objectively evaluate your actions at ICU.

c. Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQoL) scale designed to assess your quality of working life.

Please keep in mind when completing the questionnaires, there are no right or wrong answers.

There are no risks in participating in this research beyond those experienced in everyday life. All of the information that you have provided will remain confidential. There will be no monetary payment for participation in this research study; however after the surveys are filled you will receive a simple token of appreciation as a sort of my gratitude. Your identity will remain confidential and will not be shared with anyone.

Should you have any concerns about my research study, you can reach me thru my mobile phone number at +1 469-714-1727 or my email address: frederick.orapa@gmail.com . You may also reach out my adviser:

ARACELI O. BALABAGNO, PhD, RN

Professorial Lecturer

University of the Philippines-Open University, and University of the Philippines-Manila, College of Nursing Tel.no.: +63 (2)523-1633 ; Telefax: +63 (2) 528-4014

Thank you for your participation! Respectfully yours,

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN

MAN-Adult Health Nursing Student

Appendix H

LETTER OF INVITATION TO PARTICIPANTS TO PARTICIPATE IN FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION (FGD)

University of the Philippines Open University
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Master of Arts in Nursing –Adult Health Nursing Program

University of the Philippines, Department of Information Communication &
Technology Building Rm. 304
C.P. Garcia Avenue, Diliman, Quezon City, Metro Manila

(Date)

Dear Participant; Greetings!

My name is Frederick E. Orapa. I am a registered nurse and a graduate student of the University of the Philippines where I am currently working with my study about *“Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines”*. This study is a partial fulfillment of the requirements for my Master’s of Arts in Nursing degree. With this, it has always been interesting and exciting. There has always been something new to learn. That is why, I am inviting you to participate in my research study.

In line with this, you are selected as one of the participant to be interviewed for the focus group discussion. Your participation is completely voluntary. Participation or non- participation in this study will not result in any difference in care that you receive in the ICU today.

You will be asked to answer an open-ended questions which will last for about 45 minutes to 1 hour. As you agree to be interviewed, all of your responses will be digitally recorded for the purpose of documentation. Please keep in mind that there are no right or wrong answers upon answering such questions.

There are no risks in participating in this research beyond those experienced in everyday life. All of the information that you have shared will remain confidential. There will be no monetary payment for participation in this research study; however after the interview, you will receive a simple token of appreciation as a sort of my gratitude. Your identity will remain confidential and will not be shared with anyone.

Should you have any concerns about my research study, you can reach me thru
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 161

my mobile phone number at +1 469-714-1727 or my email address:
frederick.orapa@gmail.com . You may also reach out my adviser:

ARACELI O. BALABAGNO, PhD, RN

Professorial Lecturer

University of the Philippines-Open University, and University of the Philippines-
Manila, College of Nursing Tel.no.: +63 (2)523-1633 ; Telefax: +63 (2) 528-4014

Thank you for your participation!

Respectfully yours,

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN

MAN-Adult Health Nursing Student

Appendix J

FGD TRANSCRIPT #01

1 **Principal Researcher:** Good eve, My name is Frederick Orapa,RN. I'm a graduate
2 student from the University of the Philippines-Open University. I'm currently working
3 with my study about Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of
4 Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos
5 City, Philippines. With this, it has always been interesting and exciting. There has
6 always been something new to learn. That is why, I am inviting you to participate in
7 my research study.In line with this, you are selected as one of the participant to be
8 interviewed for the focus group discussion. Your participation is completely voluntary.
9 Participation or non-participation in this study will not result in any difference in care
10 that you receive in the ICU today. You will be asked to answer an open-ended
11 questions which will last for about 45 minutes to 1 hour. As you agree to be interviewed,
12 all of your responses will be digitally recorded for the purpose of documentation.
13 Please keep in mind that there are no right or wrong answers upon answering such
14 questions. There are no risks in participating in this research beyond those
15 experienced in everyday life.

16 All of the information that you have shared will remain confidential. There will be no
17 monetary payment for participation in this research study; however after the interview,
18 you will receive a simple token of appreciation as a sort of my gratitude. Your identity
19 remain confidential and will not be shared with anyone. Also, with me is my co-
20 researcher.

21 **Co-Researcher:** Hello everyone! Good evening! I'm Marc Andreo C Malala, RN,
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines 165

22 MAN. I'm the co-researcher of sir Frederick and will be assisting him in the
23 conduct of his study. Rest assured that all your responses will be treated with utmost
24 confidentiality. Are you ready na po ba?

25 **All Participants:** Yes sir!

26 **Co-researcher:** Okay sir Fred, you may start asking them sir. Time with me is 7:00pm.

27 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you sir Marc! Hmm..may I start with nurse Roy.

28 Can you describe to me your general understanding about the nurse competence on
29 patient safety? How does it affect nurses working in the ICU during the Covid-19
30 pandemic?

31 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** When I hear the word nurse competence, ahmm
32 with regards to patient safety, would tell me that the nurse should be able to acquire
33 skills not just physical skills but also the measured skills that is required being an ICU
34 nurse. Example of these skills will be well-versed of the advanced cardiac life support,
35 basic life support and IVT training. Ahmm and also, you need to be master in giving
36 medications through various channels like intravenous, intra-osseus, Sub-Q,
37 intramuscular. And also to cover up on the part of patient safety, you should also know
38 the patient's condition, the co-morbidities. Also, you should have the understanding
39 about the homeostasis, or what we call in the ICU as the reversibles. Because if you
40 can't reverse the symptoms, the patient can go to serious state. And all of these could
41 not be possible if you don't have great communication skills with your colleagues.
42 Ahmm therapeutic communication. To involve them with the management of their
43 condition. Generally, and technically to be safe, in the environment, you have to factor
44 all of these components and you to practice it one by one in collaboration with your
45 medical team.

46 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po ma'am Taylor? Ano po yung gusto nyong sabihin?

47 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** Ahmm..the way I understand the nurse

48 competence on patient safety po is important sya as it helps yung standard para maka
49 provide ng maayos na patient care at para maka lessen ng errors. Para hindi mo ma-
50 put at risk ang safety ng patient. It affects nurses working in the ICU during the
51 pandemic.

52 Kasi during the pandemic is isolated po ang mga nurses, so parang naga stick parin
53 mo sila sa mga competencies nayun para hindi po sila magkamali. At the same time
54 it affects their general well-being kasi nga away sila sa family nila, isolated sila, at more
55 sila dito sa work. So hindi sila makalabas, so maisolate sila.

56 **Principal Researcher:** Yes maam Dor, do you have something to say?

57 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Yes sir! Additional po, ahhm dapat kasi maging keen
58 observer ka sa pasyente mo. Yung mai something wrong na hindi mo maintindihan,
59 pero alam mo kailangan mo talaga sia marefer sa doctor.

60 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you po maam! How about you nurse Fred, meron
61 kabang gusto i-add sa competence on patient safety?

62 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** ahmm, dapat kilalanin natin ang patient. Dapat alam din
63 natin ang co-morbidity ng patient.

64 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you po sir! Ahmm sir Jon ano po yung mga
65 kailangan na nurse competence dito po sa ICU?

66 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** For me kailangan talaga ang assessment. Kasi mag
67 uumpisa talaga yan sa assessment. Dyan natin malalaman kun ano ang history ng
68 patient and ano yung other symptoms na pwede nating madiscover at marefer natin
69 sa mga doctor.

70 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Taylor?

71 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** Isa sa mga competency na need sa ICU is pagiging
72 one step ahead nia sa akung ano mang mangyayari sa patient nya. Kung anuman
73 mangyari sa patient, parang alam na nia kung ano ang gagawin para ma prevent
74 nia ang mga possible outcomes.

75 **Principal Researcher:** okay salamat ma'am. May I ask again sir Roy. Can you
76 describe to me your general understanding about the work-related quality of life? How
77 does it affect nurses working in the ICU especially during the times of the pandemic?

78 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** When we say work-related quality of life, given the fact
79 that we are under the pandemic, it is also understandable that all healthcare workers
80 are expected to do their part. Halimbawa we are at war, the military will be put in-
81 charge, so this is the different war wherein the nurses are in the battle field , in the
82 forefront of the care situations. Then speaking the work-related quality of life, under
83 the pandemic, we are away, we have to endure wearing PPEs for the longer period of
84 time. We have to endure being away to our loved ones, we can not go home yet. And
85 all we have to do is to be present in our work station. Siguro we as Filipinos, we have
86 this battle cry na ahmmm..like ahmm we can find happiness through little things. Yes
87 it is depressing that we are away from our loved ones, and we have to cut off our
88 pleasures. But as a member of the unit, we have to basically support each other
89 because we are in the same situation. Each of us has a family, ahhm mai mga
90 kailangan din e-meet for our mental health. We list them down and talk each other so
91 that in the end we something to look forward to. And that is to suffice lang on that part.
92 Pero syempre yung pagod, puyat, at pag-aalala...ahmm that's a different story. Some
93 of us may cry to vent out our feelings. Some of us may laugh and some of us may sing.
94 So that's how we express ourselves.

95 **Principal Researcher:** okay thank you sir. Hmmm by the way, sir Jon meron kabang
96 gusting sabihin as what sir Roy have articulated a while ago about doon sa work-
97 related quality of life

98 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** Ahh with regards to work-related quality of life, mas pinipili
99 ko parin yung sa work kasi mas marami tayong ma save na life. Hmm sa family, mai-
100 sacrifice din sia, at sa family ma understand din natin yan sya.

101 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po sir Fred, do you have something to add?

102 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** in addition, yung sa patient safety, e-include din yung
103 nurse sa safety. Tayong mga frontliner kasi naga care sa patients, so we need also
104 to protect ourselves.

105 **Principal Researcher:** Yes ma'am Taylor?

106 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** Ahhh..as I see it po, kasi due to pandemic, hindi po
107 masyado nakakauwi, mai time po na ina isolate po ang mga nurses para hindi
108 maka-spread ng virus kasi naga work sa ospital. So parang stressful at prone ang
109 mga nurse sa burn out. So parang di nila maescape yung work dahil nandito parin
110 sila sa ospital. So, in line with that, minsan mainit ang kanilang ulo at mai mga
111 attitude changes during that time po.

112 **Principal Researcher:** Thanks ma'am Taylor. Can I proceed to ma'am Dor.

113 Ahmmm..ma'am Dor, may I ask , amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, how such situation
114 impacts your overall work condition and well-being? Can you please explain why?

115 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Yes po sir. Actually, Malaki po talaga yung impact kasi
116 limited po kasi ang interactions sa patient. Hindi mo lahat maibigay yung needs
117 Kailangan mo silang kausapin kasi di nila ksama yung mga relatives nila. So parang
118 ikaw yung significant na tao sa paligid nila while admitted sila sa ICU. Ginagawa
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119 namin nung time nay un na kinakausap sila, na di sila nag-iisa.

120 **Principal Researcher:** Thanks sir Ma'am. Yes sir Roy! Meron ka bang gusting
121 sabihin?

122 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** Generally, ahmm the pandemic it shifts directly to
123 isolation care. It's overwhelming. We also an issue of understaffing and we lack of
124 supplies. Since we are in a third world country, we Filipinos compel to ask for
125 donations. We know the fact that everything is to be charged. So syempre, we have
126 this "awa" for our patient. So we don't take off our PPEs kasi it would cost additional
127 charge sa pasyente. So kahit naihi na kami, some of use may use diapers. Some of
128 us may fell ill because of too much exhaustion. Grabeh kasi ang init , mainit sa loob
129 ng PPE. At sa loob ng isolation, very demanding na kasi it is 4-6 hours na staright,
130 tapos pahinga ka lang ng 4 hours, tapos balik kana naman. At yung hours nap ag
131 gabi , ganun na ang maging routine mo. We are not robots na pag tapos ng duty
132 mo, maka tulog ka agad. So, we have the space in the hospitals, so we have to
133 make space. We have to assume other roles. Kami nadin ang parang mag house
134 keeping at assign sa vent. There are other staff not currently at our level, so the
135 adjustment of teaching them is very overwhelming. Also, there's depression inside
136 the unit, both the health worker and the patient because we have isolated inside the
137 unit. The death toll is malaking impact siya sa families and to those of us who are
138 taking care of the patient.

139 **Principal Researcher:** Thank you sir Roy...Yes sir Jon, mai gusto ka bang i-add?
140 How situation impacts your overall work condition and well-being?

141 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** ahmm..na experienced ko po. So far, nakakapagod

142 sya, at meron ding part na ma happy ka like makita mo yung pasyente mo na mai
143 nag bago at lalabas na sya sa ICU. Yung feeling na mai gusto ka pang gawin sa
144 patient mo..hmm mai impact sia sa akin like gusto ko rin gawin sa iba na kung ano
145 man ang natutunan ko dito is magawa ko din sa other patients.

146 **Principal Researcher:** Yes sir Jon, meron Karin bang gusting sabihin about how
147 such situation impacts your overall work condition and well-being?

148 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** yes, it affects me especially balancing agendas and
149 overwhelming working hours.

150 **Principal Researcher:** Okay. Can we hear from ma'am Taylor?

151 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** Yes po kasi during the pandemic malayo ka sa family
152 at hindi ka nakakauwi. Although na makakarest ka naman , pero iba parin yung
153 nakakalabas at nakaka uwi ka sa iyong bahay

154 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you! Another topic is all about caring behaviors.
155 By the way, Ma'am Dor, Can you describe to me about the way you understand
156 caring behaviors? How is it important for nurses working in the ICU? Can you tell me
157 why?

158 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Caring behaviors kasi sir is important sia not only in the
159 ICU but in general yung pagka nurse mo. Kasi kapag hindi mo ititreat mo ang
160 pasyente mo ng maayos, ahmmm..isipin mo na lang kun ano din yung ititreat ng iba
161 sa parents mo, sa family mo, or sa relatives mo in general. So kailangan mong itreat
162 ang patients mo like a family na hindi mo sia pababayaan.

163 **Principal Researcher:** Yes sir Roy. Meron ka bang gusting sabihin?

164 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** Yes sir. Looking back in its self, nursing equates to
165 caring. That is a tricky question..heheheh. because how can you be caring if you bind
166 the patient to the bed, all because you wanted to do to the patient is to calm down.
167 So, you put restraints to the patients so he cannot pull the tubes. There are some
168 points that you have to question yourself if are you doing this for your patient or are
169 you doing this out for your convenience as a caring professional. There are ethical
170 questions you have to ask yourself and you have to face them. Because everyday,
171 pandemic or not is already a battlefield here in the ICU. This is a high dependency
172 unit so we treat our patients with the medical team we can offer because the parents
173 or the patients put their trust in us to keep them alive. You have to explain those
174 things to your patient, put yourself on the shoes of the patients, and be therapeutic.

175 **Principal Researcher:** To sir Jon, may I ask how it is important for nurses working in
176 the ICU? Can you tell me why?

177 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** Ahmm, importante rin kasi ang caring behavior, kasi
178 Kung ano kung pinapakita mo, yun din yung ikaw. Kung gaano mo gina care yung
179 patient, naga reflect din sya sa personal mong pagkatao. So para sa akin, importante
180 talaga nag mag give care sa patient, kasi hindi lang sia para sa sarili mo, para din ito
181 sa family ng patient at sa patient..yung para sa best ng patient mo.

182 **Principal Researcher:** How about you sir Fred? How is it important for nurses
183 working in the ICU? Can you tell me why?

184 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** It is very important sir kasi dito natin nalalaman yung na
185 learn natin sa school yung about sa 21 basic needs sa fundamentals..dyan natin
186 malalaman kung paano natin masatisfy yung needs ng patient. And also yung pag
187 care natin is yung knowledge na natutunan din naming dito sa ICU.

188 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Taylor?

189 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** The way I understand it sir, is yung may compassion
190 ka po sa pag care ng patient at hindi lang yung state or health nya dito sa ospital but
191 holistically mo syang bibigyan ng care..ahhmm hindi lang physically but mentally
192 kung pwede bang maka usap ang patient. Other than that po is if ever wala yung
193 family, then ikaw yung magpoprovide ng sense of touch, kahit hawakan mo yung
194 kanilang kamay , yung parang mai tao paring naga look out para sa kanila.

195 **Principal Researcher:** Ahhh...okay po. .Ahmm...sir Fred follow-up lang po. Can
196 you give me certain factors that can affect the caring behavior of a nurse while
197 working in the ICU? Why do you say so?

198 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** Yes! Factors like there are patient breaks out their IVs,
199 so paano natin maibigay yung gamut nila?

200 **Principal Researcher:** Yes Nurse Dor. Do you have something to say?

201 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Yes sir, same dinpo , yung mai mga patients na
202 natanggal ang NGT at natanggal din ang ET yung kaka intubate lang. Syempre isipin
203 mo din na masakit din sa kanila if iinsert, kasi mai discomfort sya.

204 **Principal Researcher:** Yes ma'am Taylor, meron kaba gusting i-add?

205 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** Siguro po yung attitude. Meron kasi mga patient na
206 restless at matigas ang ulo. At sometime yung nurse na burn out, at hindi rin
207 sometimes nabibigay ang care. So apektado din ang caring behavior ng nurses.

208 **Principal Researcher:** Thanks po mam...Ahmm sir Roy, may ask if what were you
209 feeling and thinking during the last time you cared for a patient with critical care

210 condition especially during the times of Covid-19 pandemic? Can you describe more
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211 how this made you feel?

212 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** Ahh okay... the last patient was a very difficult patient. It
213 was one of the VIPs. Aside as the patient is very demanding, the VIP itself, the
214 patient is associated from the board members of the hospital. She's using her
215 connections and power. Some of the policies of the hospital is overlooked just to
216 satisfy them. We broke the protocols, however that protocol is hindi naman sia ganun
217 naka-cause ng ill sa mga nurses. Syempre maintidihan naman sometimes that she
218 needs to have someone, she needed to vent out her feelings during the pandemic.
219 My feeling was okay...I have to care a lot of patients. So syempre ICU then COVID,
220 so it is 1:2. I have to cover two patients, and then she was very demanding of my
221 time. So, to care for them both, I really asked forgiveness for the second one for
222 caring the second patient. So syempre, tayo we are just employees, we have this
223 fear at the back of our mind that if we don't satisfy this VIP client, our work will be
224 jeopardized. So ayun.

225 **Principal Researcher:** Okay sir Roy thank you!. How about you sir Fred. What were
226 you feeling and thinking during the last time you cared for a patient with critical care
227 condition especially during the times of Covid-19 pandemic? Can you describe more
228 how this made you feel?

229 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** I was feeling worried because the family was
230 aggressive. So, me as nurse, we have to carry out the doctor's order.

231 **Principal Researcher:** Okay sir. How about you ma'am Dor?

232 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Masaya sya! Meron kasi kaming patient na akala
233 naming papunta na kay Lord! Di kasi tumutugil ng pag seizure and then ang hirap

234 niyang tusukan. Then after nabombard na sya ng mga sedatives para hindi na sia
235 mag-seizure, masarap sa feeling na balitaan kami ng attending physician na yung
236 patient namin is naglalakad na, tinatangal na ang tracheostomy, okay na , at
237 nakakapagsalita na. Masaya sa feeling na nilaban mo yung patient at hindi ka
238 nagpabaya sa kanila.

239 **Principal Researcher:** Thanks ma'am Dor. How about you sir Jon? Same question
240 with ma'am Dor.

241 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** So, sa akin, merong part na tiring. Yung part na parang
242 na awa ka pero satisfying na nakita mo yung patient na mai improvement sya. Yung
243 part na naawa, parang pinoprolong mo yung agony ng patient. Sana if gusto niyang
244 mag rest, iparest nalang, pero gusto mo rin sya sanang isave. So parang nasa
245 dilemma ako kung ano ba ang gagawin ko at ano ba ang mas tama. Parang ganun.

246 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Taylor?

247 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** I felt sad and sorry para sa patient. Kasi hindi nya
248 naman ginusto magkaroon ng Covid, at parang malayo sya sa family nya at wala
249 syang makasama. Parang hindi nya alam kung ano ang gagawin nya at parang ang
250 lungkot lungkot ng buhay nya. Kung mag video call sana pero iba lang talaga yung
251 andyan ka para sa kanila at yung mga significant others ng patient.

252 **Principal Researcher:** ahh okay po ma'am... By the way, sir Roy may I ask what
253 you found the most challenging about your experiences in caring patients in the ICU
254 during the times of the Covid-19 pandemic?

255 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** During the time of pandemic..hmmmm...the most
256 challenging is during the admission. Because during the admission, there's a lot

257 things you have to carry out. When the patient is brought to your unit, so syempre
258 within 3 minutes, you have to establish your assessment, you have your mental
259 picture about the case of the patient. Generally, during those hours are the most
260 crucial ..ahhmmm..because the ER had just stabilized the patient, so you have to
261 continue those medications that keep your patient alive by placing them on the
262 ventilator while you give the adequate care physically. I need to check what could
263 they have missed during the assessment in the ER, so let's face it. During the covid,
264 when they stabilized the patient, they sent right up the laboratories delayed. And the
265 moment you see the laboratories, there are a lot of things you need to correct
266 interms of the patient, so that's the hardest time for me during the admission. Kasi
267 sometimes other departments would say na okay lang man ang patient, but in reality
268 in the ICU, there's a lot of thing you need to monitor.

269 **Principal Researcher:** Sir, may I know if paano mo na overcome those challenges
270 you've encountered?

271 **Nurse Roy (Participant A):** Ahh..okay. Since I am a senior, I opt to write a letter to
272 address to my superiors what exactly has happened. So , I have to protect myself.
273 And also would really like to report something that the institution would change.So
274 that it could affect change and in the future it will not happen na.

275 **Principal Researcher:** okay po sir. Ahmm same question po sir Jon , do you have
276 something to say?

277 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** hehehhe(laughing)... ahhmm my experience was yung
278 patient is nag toxic talaga then sabayan pa ng mga attending physicians na toxic
279 din. So hindi ko nakayanan, nag burst out ako, at bigla nalang ako umiyak.

280 **Principal Researcher:** So, paano mo sia naovercome sir?

281 **Nurse Jon (Participant E):** Ahmm...so, during that time nag priority ako.. I mean
282 prioritization, if anong una kong gawin and if anong gawin ko sa patient.

283 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po ma'am Dor, it seems like meron karing gusting
284 ishare?

285 **Nurse Dor (Participant C):** Ano sir..hmmm..minsan kasi mai mga patient na GCS
286 15 or GCS 13, then pagdating dito sa ICU wala ng pulse at BP ang patient. Paano
287 naming naovercome? Baleh tinatawanan na lang namin, pero hind isa harap ng
288 pasyente, heheheh. Kasi every challenges dapat mai learnings syang kasama.
289 Dapat din ready ka kun anu man ibigay sayo ng taga ER or taga floor. So if
290 sasabihin nil ana GCS 15, itothorough assessment ko sia talaga at babalikan ko,
291 hindi pweding hindi, iassess mo talaga.

292 **Principal Researcher:** Yes sir Fred, for one last time, same question parin.

293 **Nurse Fred (Participant D):** Yung challenging din kasi yung pag update mo sa mga
294 attending physician then yung nag worst ulit ang case ng patient, so marami kana
295 naming ikecarry out the orders. So same din ky Nurse Dor, para maovercome ko,
296 you need to do prioritization parin.

297 **Principal Researcher:** Yes ma'am Taylor? Do you have something to share?

298 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** For me, yung pinaka challenging talaga na
299 experience ko during the pandemic is yung nahirapan po ako mag hanap ng IV at
300 kailangan agad maibigay yung gamot ng pasyente.

301 **Principal Researcher:** Paano nyo po ba naovercome po yun?

302 **Nurse Taylor (Participant B):** So nag team work po talaga kami nun, para lang
303 mahanapan ng IV line at para mabigyan ng gamot ang patient. And then very toxic
304 narin kasi yung patient during that time. At since parang papunta sa sya sa kabilang
305 buhay, so parang nasad ako , kasi parang wala ng magawa yung medicine para sa
306 kanya. So, parang palliative care nalang yung binibigay naming para sa kanya.

307 **Principal Researcher:** So, thank you so much po Ma'am Taylor, Sir Fred, Sir Roy,
308 Ma'am Dorr, and Sir Jon. We've ended at 8:02 pm. Thank you so much with your
309 participation. And again, all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

APPENDIX K
FGD TRANSCRIPT #02

1 **Principal Researcher:** Good eve, My name
2 is Frederick Orapa,RN. I'm a graduate student from the University of the
3 Philippines-Open University. I'm currently working with my study about Nurse
4 Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors
5 among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines. With this, it has
6 always been interesting and exciting. There has always been something new to learn.
7 That is why, I am inviting you to participate in my research study.In line with this, you
8 are selected as one of the participant to be interviewed for the focus group discussion.
9 Your participation is completely voluntary. Participation or non-participation in this study
10 will not result in any difference in care that you receive in the ICU today. You will be
11 asked to answer an open-ended questions which will last for about 45 minutes to 1
12 hour. As you agree to be interviewed, all of your responses will be digitally recorded for
13 the purpose of documentation. Please keep in mind that there are no right or wrong
14 answers upon answering such questions. There are no risks in participating in this
15 research beyond those experienced in everyday life. All of the information that you have
16 shared will remain confidential. There will be no monetary payment for participation in
17 this research study; however after the interview, you will receive a simple token of
18 appreciation as a sort of my gratitude. Your identity will remain confidential and will not
19 be shared with anyone. Also, with me is my co-researcher and facilitator.
20 **Co-Researcher:** Hello everyone! Good evening! I'm Marc Andreo C.

21 Malala,RN,MAN. I'm the co-researcher of sir Frederick and will be assisting him in the
22 conduct of his study. Rest assured that all your responses will be treated with utmost
23 confidentiality. Are you ready na po ba?

24 **All Participants:** Yes sir!

25 **Co-researcher:** Okay sir Fred, you may start asking them. By the way, the time
26 with me is 7:05pm.

27 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you sir Marc! I will start with nurse Jo. Ma'am
28 can you describe to me your general understanding about the nurse competence on
29 patient safety? How does it affect nurses working in the ICU during the Covid-19
30 pandemic?

31 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Nurse competence for patients safety based on the
32 IPSG international standard of safety ng JCI (??) First po is, of course, you should know
33 the patient's name... at the same time, right the medications, sa surgical the right site
34 and everything, and of course pinaka-last is the patient risk for fall and the six IPSG...
35 Kato, ang pinaka-importante of course, the nurse should know their patient first. So naa
36 juy patient identification para to have the safety kasi that's the first thing. And of course,
37 in doing some procedures pinaka-importante is to have a consent from the family kasi
38 you cannot (be) able to do things for the patient without the consent of the patient itself
39 and the significant others. So, kato siya mao ra siguro to.

40 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po sir Lek?

41 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** So nurse competency, dapat as much as possible
42 dapat ma-follow yung ideal practice kasi yung iba hindi na nasusunod so, yun.
43 Tatamaan yung ibang nurse sa iba't ibang section.

44 **Principal Researcher:** Yes sir Ney?, do you have something to say?

45 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** For me the most priority is the patient safety regarding
46 is the wellness of the patient, especially in the ICU. For me the basic understanding of
47 the topic is very essential and very top priority in especially restless patient, patient who
48 undergo post traumatic experiences such as vehicular accidents or post surgical
49 procedures. I totally agree the initial top priority in the ICU when it comes to receiving
50 assessment.

51 **Principal Researcher:** How does it affect nurses working in the ICU during
52 COVID 19 Pandemic?

53 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** For me it affects a lot like especially what this, it really
54 affects the habit and pattern usually how to use facemask PPEs etc. We usually adjust
55 to every latest protocol how to do doffing and donning according to DOH mandated. It
56 hussle to our safety, during COVID times it just simple flu. We know that patient COVID
57 positive in ICU. Well just do level 1 or 2 PPES because DOH mandates itself the
58 protocol it depends on them.

59 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you po sir! How about you ma'am Ervs?,
60 meron kabang gusto i-add sa competence on patient safety?

61 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** My understanding about nursing competency is that
62 each nurse should have equipped with skills and understanding regarding the safety for
63 the patient. For example, nurses should have these seminars and trainings before
64 exposed to the nursing field so that safety is really... to be secure, most of the time.
65 Especially when it comes to medical care, situations like emergency situations like
66 situations that needs immediate actions, nurses should know how to handle these

67 situations properly because we're handling life and we are not allowed to commit errors.
68 During the pandemic, that's the time which is very difficult for us. So, during those
69 periods of time most of us undergone this special training for us to be protected against
70 the viruses and the environment. So during that time also, we only had limited patient's
71 care. So, they undergone this test before entering the ICU. So for us also to be safe,
72 each and everyone of us is vaccinated.

73 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you po Ma'am! Ahmm may I ask sir Lek if ano
74 po yung mga kailangan na nurse competence dito po sa ICU?

75 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Regarding sa skills, knowledge, and attitude.

76 **Principal Researcher:** Why do you say so?

77 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Importante ang skills para ma-carry out yung needs
78 ng pasyente, yung orders ng doctor para iwas mali.

79 **Principal Researcher:** How about you Ma'am Jo, can you say something po sa
80 specific competence? Regarding sa specific competence kailangan gawin talaga.

81 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Aside sa skills 'no, you need to have

82 Compassion you cannot serve people without the love of your work kasi kailangan
83 jud na love niimong work as a nurse then doing all the (work). Skills can be earned, having
84 attitude... right attitude is towards the patient is more important.

85 **Principal Researcher:** okay salamat ma'am. May I ask again ma'am Ervs. Can
86 you describe to me your general understanding about the work-related quality of life?
87 How does it affect nurses working in the ICU especially during the times of the
88 pandemic?

89 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** Quality life... it's very difficult during the pandemic
 time

90 because we experienced here that we have these critical patients who were
 tested

91 negative during the COVID times but the problem is that we were exposed for 7 days
 with

92 the patient and we didn't know that patient is still positive (for) COVID. But, how
 many

93 times he undergone the test, it says it's negative. But unfortunately, we were
 exposed

94 because the patient is still manifesting these symptoms. That is very difficult for
 us to

95 handle and we really don't know what to do. So, during those periods are very...
 very

96 tough one. So at that moment when we knew that patient is negative, all of us
 were

97 quarantined. The patient was sent to isolation, it was...because (after) only how
 many

98 hours and the patient also died. And all of us here are shocked, we didn't know what
 to

99 do. So quality of life is very difficult when it comes... when handling the patient who
 are

100 sickly and you really don't know if the patient will survive or not. There is really no
 certain

101 quality of life for the patients.

102 **Principal Researcher:** How about you sir Ney?

103 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** For me, proper work related quality of life, is
essential

104 in a sense that we need to give our wholesome effort especially when it comes to
105 environmental factors, cleanliness, emotional support, safety and security of the
patient

106 and most of all nurse to doctor interaction meaning we don't rely on any doctors order
107 and as much as possible we assess properly because here in this hospital we don't
108 have resident on duty assigned or IM doctors assigned here. So we always really
have

109 our basic skills and knowledge regarding our assessment, usually we are trained
here

110 from our senior nurses our previous areas and previous mentors here that trained us
111 the protocol, teach us knowledge skills and assessment skills and prioritization to our
112 needs of our patient. In giving your best here in ICU in this hospital, we are working
113 here two jobs here ..like our job at the same time to refer to our attending physician
114 which actually not our scope, but it very challenging and all I can you say is to
maintain

115 the quality of life is for you to move fast, to decide fast and refer fast, you know
it...basic

116 skills pa rin ABC.

117 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Minchie?

118 **Nurse Minchie (Participant J):** All I can say to the question, promote holistic

119 care approach to patient. And giving what they need and in terms of what need
during

120 the situation. In terms of proper care, proper referral to the doctor.

121 **Principal Researcher:** yes po ma'am Jo?

122 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Work-related quality of life? Sa akoo pagka-

123 understand? *Opo*. Syempre, it needs to have balance. Whatever problems you have
or

124 whatever kuan, you always compose yourself when you go to your assigned working

125 area kasi we are nurses man, so, we need to be kanang prepared kasi we are taking

126 good care of those people na negative na ang unsa, kumabaga, murag naay negative

127 vibes ba. But since we are taking good care of them, we need to parang polish pud

kasi

128 nga we are giving care, lahi ra jud siya.

129 **Principal Researcher:** yes po sir Lek? What is that?

130 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Ah my understanding, siguro dapat Sir yung mga

131 problema sa bahay hindi dapat dinadala sa trabaho, makakaapekto 'yun sa trabaho

132 namin.

133 **Principal Researcher:** Ma'am Ervs meron ka po iadd?

134 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** Quality life... it's very difficult during the pandemic

time

135 because we experienced here that we have these critical patients who were

tested

136 negative during the COVID times but the problem is that we were exposed for 7 days

with

137 the patient and we didn't know that patient is still positive (for) COVID. But, how
many
138 times he undergone the test, it says it's negative. But unfortunately, we were
exposed
139 because the patient is still manifesting these symptoms. That is very difficult for
us to
140 handle and we really don't know what to do. So, during those periods are very...
very
141 tough one. So at that moment when we knew that patient is negative, all of us
were
142 quarantined. The patient was sent to isolation, it was...because (after) only how
many
143 hours and the patient also died. And all of us here are shocked, we didn't know what
to
144 do. So quality of life is very difficult when it comes... when handling the patient who
are
145 sickly and you really don't know if the patient will survive or not. There is really no
certain
146 quality of life for the patients.

147 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thanks!. May I call again sir Ney. Amidst the
Covid-
148 19 pandemic, how such situation impacts your overall work condition and well-being?
149 Can you please explain why?

150 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** Well it impacts a lot especially usually when I go

151 home and it is so difficult to adjust. I have fear and anxiety when you have a little
cough,
152 it's very bad experience in my part everybody is walking away. More on emotionally
and
153 psychologically in dealing with other people, people are scared. They think that if you
154 are working in the hospital people they think we are the reason why COVID cases
are
155 up. The stigma they are working with the hospital as fist line providers.

156 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thanks! Yes ma'am Minchie, go ahead po.

157 **Nurse Minchie (Participant J):** It is quite stressful and burn out. I need to
158 overcome during Covid 19 the senior nurses what they want to do during the cases
of
159 COVID 19.

160 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Ervs?

161 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** For the us, the impact of COVID-19 is very...
overall
162 condition...Mahirap 'yun siya during those periods kasi we really don't know with
regards
163 of our safety as well as with the... work namin if it's really still permanent, because
during
164 those periods they only told that only the front-liners are the ones who has this fix
and a
165 sure work. Pero, we are still kinakabahan, kasi baka anytime ikaw tamaan ng COVID
or

166 sometimes, yung other namin na kasama they want to quit the job, they want to
resign
167 but unfortunately, they cannot because we are like... forced to work because we are
front-
168 liners. So you are not allowed to quit because it's your profession. So during
those
169 periods, frontliners lang talaga yung nagw-work.

170 **Principal Researcher:** Sir Lek, mai gusto ka ba sabihin?

171 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Siguro Sir, yung heavy workload.

172 **Principal Researcher:** Ahh okay sir Lek... Yes po ma'am Jo?

173 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Ever since pandemic, we are able to work with
people

174 with having COVID. So, first thing, you need to prepare yourself. Not only... kasi
during

175 that time you have this fear to be infected pud. First, you need to prepare yourselves.

176 Pray jud na you'll be okay and of course, you need to... kumbaga, mag-vitamins ka

177 something. And of course, kanang mga vaccines na it (can) really help you na murag

178 tell you, you can fight this pandemic because you are prepared and in facing sa mga

179 struggles sa pag-care sa mga patients with COVID-19.

180 **Principal Researcher:** Okay thank you po! By the way, Ma'am Jo, Can you
181 describe to me about the way you understand caring behaviors? How is it important
for

182 nurses working in the ICU? Can you tell me why?

183 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Caring behaviors? Kuan jud, kanang as what I've
said,

184 compassionate jud ka. Problem is, kanang example, na may patient ka na gahig ulo
or

185 something —hard-headed. Patience, so you can give quality care pud sa patients. If
you

186 don't have patience pud sa imoha, you'll be able to... kanang pasakitan ang patient.

187 **Principal Researcher:** How about you sir Lek?

188 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Same as sagot ni Ma'am Jo. For example dito sa
ICU,

189 may mga pasenyente kami na mga bata at matatanda, kailangan lang na intindihin
para

190 mabigay ang quality care.

191 **Principal Researcher:** Sir Lek, follow-up question lang po. Can you give me
192 certain factors that can affect the caring behavior of a nurse while working in the ICU?
193 Why do you say so?

194 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Heavy workload na hindi na papansin ang ibang
195 patiente. Parang na fofocus ka na sa isang bagay yung isa di ma masaydo mabigyan
196 ng care.

197 **Principal Researcher:** How about you ma'am Jo?

198 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Like what happen last night, we have one patient (of
199 course) , he used to (tangal niya iyang tracheostomy). Like my something problem
na

200 siya, so the tendency is nka focus lang mi sa one patient. Di na mapansin ang uban

in

201 which same lang acuity sa iban patient, so mas malisdan ka. So imong patience ma
test

202 so masuko ka sa patient or something, so mga ing ana na sitwasyon. It tested you in
203 caring your patient.

204 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po m'am Ervs?

205 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** One factor is that... if the nurse is very toxic.
So,

206 supposed to be nurses will not be affected with their emotions, with their
problems.

207 Supposed to be problems of the nurses taking care of critical patients should be
left at

208 home. You return it when you go home, but when during on your work, you should
be on

209 focused so that, 'yung caring mo for sa patient is very whole... holistic. Kasi
mahirap

210 kapag yung nurse mo mismo may problema siya, yung attitude niya nagiging
toxic

211 napapasa niya sa pasyente. So yung patient niya, mas lalong hindi gagaling kasi
anxious

212 **Principal Researcher:** M'am Minchie? Mai i-add ka?

213 **Nurse Minchie (Participant J):** For me don't bring problem at home in the ICU
unit,

214 because you will be affected how you deal with patient care.

215 **Principal Researcher:** Ahmm ma'am Minchie another question for you po
216 ma'am, may ask if what were you feeling and thinking during the last time you cared
for
217 a patient with critical care condition especially during the times of Covid-19
pandemic?

218 Can you describe more how this made you feel?

219 **Nurse Minchie (Participant J):** for me the goal for me is that the patient will
220 be ok during the shift, we need refer as much as possible. Stress sometimes
221 comes from the doctors and patients, so don't be affected.

222 **Principal Researcher:** Sir Ney mai sasabihin po ba kayo?

223 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** In my opinion, I have worked here long time even
224 pandemic. I deal it professionally based on Skills, knowledge, and attitude. I'm not
225 emotionally attached we need to set boundaries. I'm happy when the patient will be
226 discharged in ICU during pandemic.

227 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po ma'am Ervs?

228 **Nurse Ervs (Participant I):** It's very challenging to handle patients with
COVID-

229 19 before. Because... we are used to dealing with critical patients, YES. But, critical
230 patient with COVID is very another thing so, mahirap masyado siya i-manage and...
231 kasi ikaw mismo, you are concerned with your health. Yung parang, there are times
na

232 parang meron limitations to be exposed inside the patient's room, so parang yung
iyong

233 therapeutic nga, parang nababawasan siya. Kasi nga iniisip mo, "ah paano na if ako

234 mahawaan nito, what if this patient yes, hindi siya totally gumaling, tapos ako
nahawaan

235 so, most probably I will die too,” parang ganyan. Yun, mahirap siya during those
236 pandemic time pero masyado lang talaga kami sa sarili namin... na vaccinated
naman

237 kami.

238 **Principal Researcher:** Ahhh ma’am..parang mai gusto ka po ishare.

239 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** It is (kuwan sa no), its weird. Even though you keep
on

240 telling don’t do (kanang), do not sympathized. Empathized lang. Pero you cannot
help it

241 man gud, you will (you will) symphatized with the family lalo na pag ang patient
parents

242 sa imong colleague (ana gud). Makita nimo imong colleague, how affected sa
243 panghitabo or something like that. So kanang dili jud maiwasan so that’s one thing
na

244 ma ano sa isa ka nurse. So naa jud tong usahay, tungod exhausted naka.
Emotionally

245 down kana. Kasi during that time very emotional ang nurse ang naga care sa patient
246 during pandemic kasi murag feeling nimo daghana na nila uy.(murag something).
They

247 are a lot of patient naka admit tpos wala ka kabalo ikaw mismo dili nimo matabangan

248 imong sarili (murag ana gud). So tapos mkita pa nimo na their colleagues parents is

249 dying on that disease (COVID). Pati ikaw (ma kuan ka) ma down sad ka, unya pati

250 pud
mka uli pa ba ko ksi you will be staying in the hospital for 14 days tpos 14 days na
251 pud
(na unsa na). So kato emotionally kanang (emotionally triggered) tungod sa mga
252 pang
hitabo. Not only sa hospital pati pud sa lain pagwas nimo sa hospital thinking pagtan
aw
253 sa tao sa imoha hugaw kaau ka (you're so dirty) because you came from the hospital.
254 So emotionally down ang nurses during pandemic. So dili nimo maiwasan you will
also
255 sympathize. Wala tong empathize, sympathize na. Kahit imong ingnon ang nurse na
256 ayaw pag sympathize kasi dili siya para sa nurses, dapat mg emphatize ka lang but
you
257 can't help it during pandemic.

258 **Principal Researcher:** May I ask po sir Lek?

259 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Ah siyempre yung last time may patiente kami.
Napa
260 isip ko na lang kasi may siyam sia na anak (studyante pa). Umaasa nalang sa papa
261 niya. I feel na ng emphatize na ko sa ilaha.

262 **Principal Researcher:** Okay sir Lek..tanong ko lang din po.. what you found
the
263 most challenging about your experiences in caring patients in the ICU during the
times
264 of the Covid-19 pandemic? Please explain why.

265 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** I think heavy work load at yung attitude ng mga
266 patiente because they are not cooperative, no quality of care.

267 **Principal Researcher:** Ahh..okay po sir Lek.. How about you ma'am Jo?

268 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Kanang nurse patient ratio ba. Dili siya balance kasi
269 nga tendency they keep on admitting pero they don't know the capacity of the nurse
270 kung kaya niya ang mga possible na procedures, Kahit mag ingon kag apat lang siya
na

271 patient. Pero sa apat they are lot of procedures na kailangan, Pareho nahitabo kasi
272 karon full house Ninyo pag human sa isa sudlan ksi apat lang daw patiente, pull
outan

273 pka ug isa kasi apat daw patiente. Kailangan daw. So murag anu siya ba katong gina
274 ingon nila ba (kanang workload nimo dili sya balance sa nurse unsa na). Kasi lalo
275 napag kauban nimo sila bag ohan gud sila. Naga alalay pa mi sa ilaha. Good thing
they

276 are fast learners. Kung baga bag o lang sila nag sulod pero they fast learners.

277 **Principal Researcher:** Yes po sir Ney?

278 **Nurse Ney (Participant H):** We have patient X, thoracic 5 complete fracture sa
279 spine. It is challenging because I always focus the care to him. For me the secret is
time

280 management. No other extracurricular activities just focus on care on the patient.

281 **Principal Researcher:** Ma'am Minchie, mai naexperience Karin ba? At paano
mo

282 ito naovercome?

283 **Nurse Minchie (Participant J):** yes po sir.. it was very challenging when I

284 changed inotropes, then he arrested. I overcome it I did my best nursing care I have
285 with the patient.

286 **Principal Researcher:** Balik ako ulit kay ma'am Jo...Ma'am Jo may ask if
paano

287 mo naovercome yung challenging experience mo?

288 **Nurse Jo (Participant F):** Siyempre di jud maiwasan mikipag away jud ka no.

289 Para na mahibal an that your feeling ba that moment ba. Kailangan na iparamdam
sa

290 ilaha na dili tama na inyong ginabuhay sa amoa dapat inyo pud I consider among

291 situation. So it first we reported sa among nursing service or supervisor. Pinaka worst
is

292 katong isa lang ka patient among (kuan) pero daghan siya ug procedures. Ng code
pa

293 jud siya. Pag human ug code, na pa jud mi OR isa ka patient. Tatlo lang patiente ato.

294 Na code ang isa ka patient. Pa OR pa ang isa tapos pero pabalik na pud daun isya
ky

295 trache man lang. Naa sila gsulod, pilit nila isulod gikan sa gawas kasi daw dili gusto
ang

296 family na dili na siya isulod pero wala nkit an pano mi ka katag dre ba. Nag code pa
gud

297 mi. Naa pa gud ng rounds pa ang doctor. Gisulod pa jud nila ug 7pm na unta that's
for

298 endorsement na. So ongoing endorsement ng seizure ang patient murag daghan
kaau

299 nhitabo. Then of course ang floor nurses nka uli na pero kmi na ICU mi lang mag uli
 ug

300 alas onse sa gabii. Then next time around the series of events, dapat the next time
301 intidihi pud mi nila. Of course mg reklamo jud ka.

302 **Principal Researcher:** Ikaw po sir Lek, same question kay ma'am Jo po.

303 **Nurse Lek (Participant G):** Ahmm....just go with the flow, nasa harap mo na
304 tapusin mo na lang.

305 **Principal Researcher: Okay salamat po sir Lek....**So, thank you so much po
306 Ma'am Jo, Sir Ney, Ma'am Ervs, at ma'am Minchie. We've ended at 8:25 pm. Again,
307 thank you so much with your participation. I'd like to emphasized again po na all your
308 responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

APPENDIX L
GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Gawas – outside. Gikan- starting from.

Gisulod – to take inside. Katag- untidiness.

Kauban- companion.

Kuan- description of one's thoughts, feelings, or actions less assertive or forceful. Synonymous with terms like “Kanang” and “Murag”.

Kung baga – just like.

Masuko- feeling or showing anger or madness.

Panghitabo- a certain events.

Usahay- sometimes.

APPENDIX M

STATISTICAL COMPUTATION VIA SPSS VERSION 27

Case Processing Summary

	N	Valid Percent	N	Cases Missing Percent	N	Total Percent
Caring Behavior	70	100.0%	0	0.0%	70	100.0%
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	70	100.0%	0	0.0%	70	100.0%
Work-Related Quality of Life	70	100.0%	0	0.0%	70	100.0%

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Caring Behavior	Mean	5.6855	.04051	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	5.6047	
		Upper Bound	5.7663	
	5% Trimmed Mean	5.7199		
	Median	5.8094		
	Variance	.115		
	Std. Deviation	.33894		
	Minimum	4.58		
	Maximum	6.00		
	Range	1.42		

Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines

	Interquartile Range		.45	
	Skewness		-1.334	.287
	Kurtosis		1.359	.566
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	Mean		4.7092	.03351
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	4.6423	
		Upper Bound	4.7760	
	5% Trimmed Mean		4.7322	
	Median		4.7964	
	Variance		.079	
	Std. Deviation		.28039	
	Minimum		3.86	
	Maximum		5.00	
	Range		1.14	
	Interquartile Range		.42	
	Skewness		- 1.137	.287
	Kurtosis		.610	.566
	Work-Related Quality of Life	Mean		3.9925
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	3.8666	
		Upper Bound	4.1183	
5% Trimmed Mean			3.9910	
Median			3.9167	

Variance	.279	
Std. Deviation	.52791	
Minimum	2.72	
Maximum	5.00	
Range	2.28	
Interquartile Range	.78	
Skewness	.152	.287
Kurtosis	-.337	.566

	Tests of Normality					
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Caring Behavior	.177	70	.00	.843	70	.000
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	.150	70	.00	.875	70	.000
Work-Related Quality of Life	.079	70	.200 [*]	.977	70	.217

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

*Based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of normality, the Caring Behavior and Nurse Competence on Patient Safety both have a p-values of .000 which are less than the alpha level of significance (.05) indicating that data is not normally distributed. On the other hand, only the Work-related quality of life has a p-value of .200 which is more than .05, indicating a normal distribution of data. However, the rule of thumb is that all variables should have a p-values that are above the alpha level of significance (.05). Therefore, it can be concluded that all data are not normally distributed, which primarily

implies that parametric test of correlation cannot be used. In this case, the Spearman-rho was used to establish a strength of correlation among the variables.

Nonparametric Correlations (Spearman-rho)

Correlations

		Caring Behavior	
Spearman's rho	Caring Behavior	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	70
	Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	Correlation Coefficient	.762**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	70
	Work-Related Quality of Life	Correlation Coefficient	.555**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	70

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
CB_Q1	70	5.81	.75
CB_Q2	70	5.79	.70
CB_Q3	70	5.96	.20
CB_Q4	70	5.37	.76
CB_Q5	70	5.49	.78

CB_Q6	70	5.63	.59
CB_Q7	70	5.51	.74
CB_Q8	70	5.30	.97
CB_Q9	70	5.93	.31
CB_Q10	70	5.74	.61
CB_Q11	70	5.77	.52
CB_Q12	70	5.57	.63
CB_Q13	70	5.76	.46
CB_Q14	70	5.61	.64
CB_Q15	70	5.87	.45
CB_Q16	70	5.64	.54
CB_Q17	70	5.67	.56
CB_Q18	70	5.81	.43
CB_Q19	70	5.66	.54
CB_Q20	70	5.64	.54
CB_Q21	70	5.73	.59
CB_Q22	70	5.90	.30
CB_Q23	70	5.54	.72
CB_Q24	70	5.53	.58
NCPS_Q1	70	4.64	.80

NCPS_Q2	70	4.63	.82
NCPS_Q3	70	4.69	.77
NCPS_Q4	70	4.59	.63
NCPS_Q5	70	4.89	.36
NCPS_Q6	70	4.93	.26
NCPS_Q7	70	4.93	.26
NCPS_Q8	70	4.71	.76
NCPS_Q9	70	4.67	.63
NCPS_Q10	70	3.87	1.18
NCPS_Q11	70	4.73	.56
NCPS_Q12	70	4.80	.40
NCPS_Q13	70	4.74	.47
NCPS_Q14	70	4.76	.46
NCPS_Q15	70	4.76	.43
NCPS_Q16	70	4.64	.48
NCPS_Q17	70	4.63	.49
NCPS_Q18	70	4.77	.42
NCPS_Q19	70	4.90	.30
NCPS_Q20	70	4.83	.38
NCPS_Q21	70	4.74	.50

NCPS_Q22	70	4.79	.41
WRQL_Q1	70	4.64	.54
WRQL_Q2	70	4.17	.76
WRQL_Q3	70	4.51	.61
WRQL_Q4	70	4.19	.87
WRQL_Q5	70	4.09	.76
WRQL_Q6	70	4.06	.96
WRQL_Q7	70	3.99	.91
WRQL_Q8	70	3.91	.83
WRQL_Q9	70	3.37	1.31
WRQL_Q10	70	4.01	.97
WRQL_Q11	70	4.43	.63
WRQL_Q12	70	4.20	.73
WRQL_Q13	70	3.96	.94
WRQL_Q14	70	3.90	.97
WRQL_Q15	70	3.80	.97
WRQL_Q16	70	3.97	.92
WRQL_Q17	70	4.03	.80
WRQL_Q18	70	4.00	.90
WRQL_Q19	70	3.77	1.01

WRQL_Q20	70	3.90	1.01
WRQL_Q21	70	3.83	.87
WRQL_Q22	70	3.77	.85
WRQL_Q23	70	3.80	.84
Assurance of human presence	70	5.61	.45
Knowledge and skills	70	5.75	.39
Respectfulness	70	5.71	.39
Positive connectedness	70	5.67	.43
Decision making	70	4.72	.31
Collaboration	70	4.62	.37
Nursing Intervention	70	4.69	.54
Principles of Nursing Care	70	4.81	.31
Job and career satisfaction	70	4.23	.54
General well-being	70	3.87	.62
Home-work interface	70	4.01	.80
Stress at work	70	3.88	.85
Control at work	70	4.06	.65
Working conditions	70	3.90	.80
Caring Behavior	70	5.69	.34
Nurse Competence on Patient Safety	70	4.71	.28

Work-Related Quality of Life	70	3.99	.53
Valid N (listwise)	70		

Frequencies

	Statistics				
	AGE	SEX	EDUCATION	YRS OF EXPERIENCE	ATTENDANCE IN NURSING CONFERENCE
N Valid	70	70	70	70	70
Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	2.11	1.64	1.13	4.00	1.19
Median	2.00	2.00	1.00	4.00	1.00
Mode	2	2	1	5	1
Std. Deviation	.603	.483	.378	1.251	.392
Sum	148	115	79	280	83

Frequency Table

		AGE			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	21-30 years old	9	12.9	12.9	12.9
	31-40 years old	44	62.9	62.9	75.7
	41-above years old	17	24.3	24.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

		SEX			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	25	35.7	35.7	35.7
	FEMALE	45	64.3	64.3	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

		EDUCATION			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BACHELORS DEGREE	62	88.6	88.6	88.6
	MASTERS DEGREE	7	10.0	10.0	98.6
	PHD DEGREE	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

YRS OF EXPERIENCE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5 YEARS	13	18.6	18.6	18.6
	6-10 YEARS	10	14.3	14.3	32.9
	11-15 YEARS	16	22.9	22.9	55.7
	16-20 YEARS	26	37.1	37.1	92.9
	MORE THAN 20 YEARS	5	7.1	7.1	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

ATTENDANCE IN NURSING CONFERENCE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES	57	81.4	81.4	81.4
	NO	13	18.6	18.6	100.0
	Total	70	100.0	100.0	

Caring Behavior

Nurse Competence on Patient Safety

Work-Related Quality of Life

APPENDIX N
CERTIFICATE OF STATISTICAL TREATMENT

This is to formally certify that the undersigned has been consulted for the statistical treatment of the study with the title **“Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines”**.

Specifically, the following statistical treatments listed below were used in the study by utilizing the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27:

1. Frequency and Percentage.
2. Mean and Standard Deviation.
3. Spearman's correlation coefficient.
4. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test of Normality.

Engr. Joe Nino E. Orapa

Statistician

Date Signed: September 10, 2023

Appendix O DOCUMENTATION

***Courtesy call with Chief Nurse and Medical Director**

***August 15 to 24, 2023**

***Focus Group Discussion Day 1**

***Focus Group Discussion Day 2**

***Tokens of Appreciation for Participants**

Appendix P

Certificate of Completion of Principal Investigator, Researcher Assistant, and
Co-Investigator on Ethical Training

NIDA Clinical Trials Network

Certificate of Completion

is hereby granted to

Marc Andreo Malala

to certify your completion of the six-hour required course on:

GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE

MODULE:

Introduction
Institutional Review Boards
Informed Consent
Confidentiality & Privacy
Participant Safety & Adverse Events
Quality Assurance
The Research Protocol
Documentation & Record-Keeping
Research Misconduct
Roles & Responsibilities
Recruitment & Retention
Investigational New Drugs

STATUS:

N/A
Passed
Passed

Course Completion Date: 26 July 2023

CTN Expiration Date: 26 July 2026

Eve Jelstrom

Eve Jelstrom, Principal Investigator
NDAT CTN Clinical Coordinating Center

Good Clinical Practice, Version 5, effective 03-Mar-2017

This training has been funded in whole or in part with Federal funds from the National Institute on Drug Abuse, National Institutes of Health, Department of Health and Human Services, under Contract No. HHSN27201201000024C.

NIDA Clinical Trials Network

Certificate of Completion

is hereby granted to

Vladimier Lee

to certify your completion of the six-hour required course on:

GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE

MODULE:	STATUS:
Introduction	N/A
Institutional Review Boards	Passed
Informed Consent	Passed
Confidentiality & Privacy	Passed
Participant Safety & Adverse Events	Passed
Quality Assurance	Passed
The Research Protocol	Passed
Documentation & Record-Keeping	Passed
Research Misconduct	Passed
Roles & Responsibilities	Passed
Recruitment & Retention	Passed
Investigational New Drugs	Passed

Course Completion Date: 27 July 2023

CTN Expiration Date: 27 July 2026

Eve Jelstrom

Eve Jelstrom, Principal Investigator
NDAT CTN Clinical Coordinating Center

Good Clinical Practice, Version 5, effective 03-Mar-2017

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HHSN27201201000024C.

Appendix Q

SIMILARITY INDEX RESULT (VIA TURNITIN)

THESIS_BY FREDERICK E. ORAPA, RN

ORIGINALITY REPORT

8%

SIMILARITY INDEX

4%

INTERNET SOURCES

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UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
Master of Arts in Nursing

Nurse Competence on Patient Safety, Work-Related Quality of Life, and Caring Behaviors among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital in General Santos City, Philippines

Frederick E. Orapa, RN

Appendix R
INTERVENTION PROGRAM

Title: Basic Nursing Critical Care Program

A Training Program for Critical Nurses Caring for Critically-ill Patients

I. Rationale:

Using the seventh carita of Watson's theory of caring, this one-day program activity will serve as a caring manual for nurses tending to critically ill patients, helping them to improve the quality of their caregiving. It is anticipated that the participants would get knowledge on how to use the caritas process for them and their patients who are in critical condition.

II. General Objective:

Upon completion of the program, participants will possess the necessary knowledge, abilities, and mindset to cultivate a compassionate relationship with critically ill patients, ultimately restoring their sense of completeness and dignity.

Specifically, it aims to:

1. Define words that are pertinent to the considerate action.
2. Talk about Human Caring Theory.
3. Encourage one-on-one instruction and learning that takes into account the unique requirements and learning preferences of each patient.

III. Learning Outcomes

	Learning Outcomes	Learning Assessment
A	Definition of terms: - caring - caring behavior	Pre-test and post-test Question and answer

B	Watsons theory of human caring, the 7 th caritas process and its application to nursing	Pre-test and post-test Question and answer
C	Activities related to interpersonal Teaching-learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interpretation on caring concepts through visual art (poster making) - participation during small group activity (group discussion) -assessing the comprehension of participants through open forum -identification of caritas processes through video presentation (learning activity) - exchange of ideas and opinions -application of caring concepts through healing modalities (relaxation techniques)

IV. Contents

The learning outline comprise of the following:

1. Caring and caring behavior
2. Watsons theory of human caring, the 7th caritas process and its application to nursing profession.
3. Interpersonal Teaching-learning through the following activities:
 - Interpretation on caring concepts through visual art
 - Participation during small group activity
 - Assessing the comprehension of participants
 - Identification of caritas processes through video presentation
 - Exchange of ideas and opinions
 - Application of caring concepts through healing modalities

V. Methodology

Lecture

Pre- and Post-test

Poster making

Group discussion

Open forum

Video presentation

Relaxation techniques

VI. Procedure:

1. The researcher will draft a letter requesting permission to conduct the training program to be sent to the Medical Director of SOCSARGEN COUNTY

HOSPITAL.

2. Following clearance, the researcher will work with the Training Office to arrange the location and participants in conjunction with the Office of the Chief Nurse.
3. The researcher appoints three assistants to help him with training program facilitation and material preparation.
4. One day before the program is held, the researcher ensures that all required materials are available and complete, guests and participants are notified, slides and lectures are prepared, and the venue is set up.
5. The researcher arrives early on the day of the program to set up the location and the supplies.
6. Each participant will get a pretest one (1) day before to the program. This will evaluate each participant's caring behavior and provide baseline data for the researcher to use when creating the comparison report.
7. Several lectures and exercises will be conducted during the seminar to ensure that every participant fully understands the material.
8. After talking about caring, there will be a poster-making exercise. They will be required to use art to convey their opinion(s) about caring and to present their creations to the group. Through this exercise, the researcher will be able to assess the extent to which participant comprehension is connected to compassion.
9. The participants will be divided into groups by the researcher and his assistants in preparation for the group discussion, and each group will get a pen and some manila paper. Using a SWOT analysis, the researcher will pinpoint issues pertaining to caring, develop remedies, and advance by self-reflecting. After each group has completed its

work, a representative from each group will be invited to present their SWOT analysis in order to foster self-awareness, gather all the information needed about oneself, and offer a more comprehensive picture of all the advantages and disadvantages. Each participant in this exercise may find it easier to make the effort to make good adjustments that will open up new chances.

10. The speaker will question each participant in the Open Forum exercise about how they plan to put the theory into practice in their daily lives.

11. In the Learning Activity, the researcher will present a scenario (via a slide show or video) and explain which caritas procedure was used. Additionally, they will be asked to choose a caritas procedure and explain their choice. In this exercise, the participants will have the chance to voice their opinions and the researcher will evaluate their understanding of the ten caritas processes.

12. Each participant will get an assessment at the conclusion of the event to score the speaker's performance, the presentation, and the location. The participant will receive an assignment from the researcher to complete every day. He will provide links for the attendees to watch or read, and they can use them to create a reflection diary. To complete the training program, two (2) reflection journals must be turned in to the researcher.

13. Participants who turned in two (2) reflection journals will get a posttest. The participant who fulfills all training program requirements—including the post-test, two reflection journals, total attendance, and the pre-test—will get a certificate.

VII. Operational Details

Venue	SOCSARGEN Conference Room	
Category of Participants	Nursing Service Department	
Total Participants/batch: 50	Males:	Females:
Learning Service Providers (LSP)/Facilitators	3	
Support Staff	2	
Proposed Budget	Php 17,000.00	

Expense item	Expense detail	Breakdown details	Cost
Supplies and Materials	Costs of consumable and semi-expendable items to be used during the implementation of a research program.	Specialty paper substance 24 (certificate)	20/pack x3 = Php 60
		Pentel pen	50/piece x5 = Php 250
		Black Ballpen	5/piece x30 = Php 150
		Brown Envelope (Short Size)	3/piece x 30 = Php 90
		Coupon band (Short Size)	150/ream = Php 150
		Manila paper 36/48 inches	9/piece x 5 = Php 45

		Crayons	28/pack x 7 = Php 196
		Total	Php 941
Printing Expenses	Include costs of printing of certificates	Printing	Php 100
Personal Service	Honorarium, fees and other compensation to speakers.	Honorarium/token of appreciation	Php 1,000 /speaker x 3 = Php 3,000
Food expenses	Food for the Speaker, participants and the facilitators	Lunch AM/PM snacks	Php 200/pax x 50 = Php 10,000
Miscellaneous	Reserve fund for unforeseen expenses		Php 2,959
TOTAL			P 20,000

Logistical Requirements:

- a. Training Kits:
 - Training Schedule and Program
 - Final Evaluation Sheets
 - Certificates of Completion

- Extra sheets of paper
- b. Registration Materials
 - Participants Attendance Sheet
 - Ball pens and pentel pens
- c. Equipment
 - Laptop, 1 unit
 - LCD Projector, 1 unit
 - Printer, 1 unit

VIII. Evaluation of Learning Design Intervention

Question and Answer

Pre-test and Posttest

Training Evaluation

CURRICULUM VITAE

FREDERICK E. ORAPA, BSN-RN, PCCN

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Texas U, S. 75454
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WORK EXPERIENCE

- Worked as **Fulltime Registered Nurse – Critical Care** in **The University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center** in Dallas, Texas in a Multispecialty ICU.
- Worked as Crisis Nurse during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Dallas, Texas
- Former Registered Nurse-ICU of **Socsargen County Hospital** (Site of Research Studies) from 2006 to 2008 and 2019 in General Santos City, Philippines.
- Former Registered Nurse-ICU in Private Hospital in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia from 2008 to 2017.

EDUCATION

2001-2005 *Bachelor of Science in Nursing*
Notre Dame of Dadiangas University
General Santos City, Philippines

TRAININGS

July 2023 **Good Clinical Practice**
National Institute on Drug Abuse, National Institutes of Health,
Department of Health, and Human Services

CERTIFICATIONS

(1) BLS American Heart Association expires on September 30, 2025

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- (2) ACLS American Heart Association expires on September 30, 2025
- (3) PALS American Heart Association expires on April 21, 2024
- (4) AACN Course on COVID-19 Pulmonary, ARDS, and Ventilatory Resources:
issued on March 31, 2020
- (5) COVID-19 Pulmonary and Ventilator Care Micro-Credentials certified by American Association of Critical Nurse (AACN) issued on July 13, 2021
- (6) PCCN (Progressive Care Certified Nurse) certified by American Association of Critical Nurse (AACN) issued on February 01, 2024

PROFESSIONAL MEMBERSHIP

Lifetime Philippine Nurses Association

Member 1663 F.T. Benitez Street
Malate, Manila, Philippines 1004

Member American Association of Critical Care Nurse (AACN)

27071 Aliso Creek Road
Aliso Viejo, California, United States 92656-3399